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6.3 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

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D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication
DIS	Direct Injection System
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
MAA	Multi-Actor Approach
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
SFTs	Smart Farming Technologies
TGs	Key Target Groups
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UVP	Unique Value Proposition

Table 1: List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Executive Summary

Smart Droplets seeks to revolutionize crop care by integrating advanced physical and digital technologies to optimize field performance and minimize environmental impact. By leveraging key technological innovations in open-field spraying, the project aims to enhance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical applications, aligning with sustainability targets and the objectives of the EU Green Deal.

The project focuses on developing a holistic system capable of transforming large volumes of data into precise and effective spraying commands in the field. This system integrates autonomous robotic platforms, innovative spraying techniques, digital twin technology, and AI models. To demonstrate the real-world impact and scalability of these cutting-edge solutions, Smart Droplets has established two pilot sites in Spain and Lithuania, chosen for their diverse and complementary agricultural environments. These pilots serve as tangible showcases of the project's innovations, providing critical data and insights into the system's effectiveness under varying conditions.

The third version of the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan and Reports builds upon the foundations laid in previous iterations, refining strategies to maximize the project's reach and impact. It outlines a structured approach for engaging stakeholders, promoting the project's innovations, and ensuring the sustainable exploitation of its results. Key objectives include enhancing internal communication, establishing a distinctive project brand, and implementing targeted dissemination activities such as market events, open days, webinars, and the Smart Droplets Academy.

This deliverable consists of several key chapters, each focusing on a critical aspect of the project's dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategies:

The first introductory chapter offers an overview of the Smart Droplets project, emphasizing its innovative approach to integrating AI, data analytics, and robotics in agriculture to meet EU Green Deal objectives. It also outlines the scope of the document, detailing strategies to maximize the project's impact across different stakeholder groups. The second chapter presents the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation report's methodology. It covers situation analysis, objectives, stakeholder identification, and strategies, along with detailed methods and activities for effective communication. The approach is divided into four phases: Mission, Strategy, Vision, Raise Awareness, Synergies and Network Multipliers, and Post-project Sustainability & Impact. The third chapter presents the dissemination activities, detailing the activities aimed at ensuring the project's outcomes and opportunities are effectively communicated to target communities. It includes activities such as market and industry events, webinars, tech briefs, representation in Working Groups and Alliances, and the Smart Droplets Academy, which aim to introduce the platform, demonstrate its benefits, foster collaborations, and support continuous use and adaptation of the technologies. Chapter four reports on the Smart Droplets communication efforts and focuses on informing, promoting, and sharing the project's impact with a broader audience. It outlines the development of a strong visual identity, use of digital channels like social media and the project website, and production of newsletters and press releases. It also includes KPIs for tracking engagement, such as website pageviews and social media followers. Chapter five, titled Exploitation Activities, describes the strategy for exploiting the project results, both commercially and non-commercially. It includes the identification and validation of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), market analysis, funding opportunities, and the development of joint and individual exploitation plans. The goal is to ensure the innovations are utilized effectively during and beyond the project's lifecycle, focusing on sustainability and scalability. The final chapter summarizes the progress and enhancements made in the DEC plan, highlighting improved strategies based on feedback and evaluation. It emphasizes stakeholder engagement, collaboration with complementary initiatives, detailed exploitation strategies, and a robust framework for monitoring and evaluation, setting a clear path forward to maximize the impact of Smart Droplets innovations in the agricultural sector.

By providing a clear and actionable roadmap, this deliverable aims to secure the long-term impact of Smart Droplets, contributing to environmental sustainability, economic growth, and advancements in agricultural practices. The iterative updates planned for key milestones (at the end of Reporting Period 1 on M12, this version

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at the end of Reporting Period 2 on M24, and at the end of the project on M42) will ensure the plan remains dynamic and responsive, capturing new insights and enhancing the effectiveness of dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities. This continuous refinement process is critical for maintaining the relevance and impact of the Smart Droplets project in achieving the Green Deal goals and supporting the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) reform.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Summary

The Smart Droplets project focuses on supporting the further development of Smart Farming Technologies (SFTs) that are considered key enablers for farmers to better monitor their crops and reduce the use of chemicals (fertilizers and plant protection products) as well as to reduce GHG emissions, to enable reaching the Green Deal targets towards reduction of agrochemicals. To this end, the Smart Droplets project introduces a novel approach for crop care tasks, by connecting key-technological aspects during open field spraying and is committed to advancing both hardware and software capabilities during chemical application, in order to meet the sustainability scope of the EU Green Deal and the recently reformed Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Smart Droplets' solution relies upon implementing the Autonomous retrofit tractors with Direct Injection System (DIS) for intelligent spraying - avoiding exposure of farmers to hazardous chemicals. Through the combination of high-level technologies (>TRL 7), Smart Droplets adopts a hybrid approach for spraying operations, combining Data/AI/Digital Farm Twin technologies designed to translate data into actionable information, and real-time data collected from Field demonstrators evaluating and demonstrating optimized technologies in the real environments. Ensuring replicability and uptake of digital technologies by deploying innovative tools, services, and recommendations while making them relevant and of practical use to farmers, advisors, and policymakers across Europe; Smart Droplets will test the solution on two diversified and complementary environments, namely apple orchard and wheat farms. Moreover, Smart Droplets Academy will run each year, engaging and educating non-experts stakeholders operating within the agricultural vertical on AI, AI ethics, Data and Agrifood Robotics. The Smart Droplets Consortium consists of all agricultural AI, data and robotics value chain actors, and is well-balanced in terms of expertise, entity type, and geographical distribution necessary to meet its objectives.

Project Aim and Outcome

In recent years, agricultural environments are characterized by rapid changes, while **crop care** tasks have always been repetitive, tedious, and potentially hazardous exposing farmers to health risks that should be avoided. Consequently, the sector is shifting towards more selective treatment applications to improve the quality and efficiency of chemical spraying while simultaneously benefiting workers in this sector as well as the planet.

In the case of **crop spraying operations**, AI models, data, and exploitation of autonomous robotic systems have not reached a mature technological level, mainly due to the lack of a holistic approach that combines physical and digital assets for optimal field performance and minimum environmental impact. AI and Data and robotic advances on SFTs can contribute to fulfilling this ambition, bringing benefits in terms of reduced pesticide use, low carbon emissions, low water use, and reduced food waste, thus enabling environmental sustainability.

Smart Droplets' therefore aims to advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical applications for resource optimization and minimization of chemical waste. To accomplish this vision, this project will use already existing technologies (>TRL 7) developed within but not limited to the agricultural industry.

Figure 1: Smart Droplets concept approach

The Smart Droplets consortium consists of **9** partners across **6** countries bringing together experts in **SFTs** (e.g., Direct Injection Spraying (DIS), Digital twins, data infrastructures, AI models), in **agricultural issues** (e.g., CAP, pesticide application, environmental assessment) and **social sciences** (e.g., business performance metrics, communication activities, marketing, training and capacity building).

Smart Droplets will engage a multi-actor approach and feedback-driven solution strengthening utilizing the **2** farm pilot test cases to contribute to the project's key 3 major outcomes grouped in the following dimension:

- **Innovative AI, data and robotics solution:** A mix of robotic and non-robotic components focusing on resource optimization and waste reduction when applying chemicals achieved by using state-of-the-art concepts on planning and navigation for the retrofit tractor along with AI, computer vision and process-based agronomic models.
- **Optimised AI, data and robotics:** The use of AI-assisted techniques to teach the Digital Farm Twin with high generalization capacity across diverse weather conditions and geographic and site-specific, multi-chemical spraying system for better monitoring of sprayers efficiency and targeted crop interventions.
- **Robotics solutions in harsh environments:** Capability of the solution to localize itself in the environment properly through a 3D localization and mapping solution tailored to the challenges found in agriculture.

Figure 2: Smart Droplets timeline

1.2. Document Scope

The scope of the deliverable "D6.3 Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan and Reports v3" is to outline a comprehensive strategy for effectively disseminating, communicating, and exploiting the results and innovations of the Smart Droplets project. This deliverable aims to maximise the project's impact by reaching diverse stakeholder groups, including researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, and the general public. It details the methodologies and approaches used to raise awareness, foster collaborations, and ensure the sustainability of the project outcomes beyond its duration. The plan includes a robust framework for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of dissemination and communication activities, ensuring that the project's advancements in AI, data analytics, and robotics for agriculture are widely recognized and adopted.

1.3. Document Structure

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

Chapter 1: Introduction

The introduction provides an overview of the Smart Droplets project, emphasizing its innovative approach to integrating AI, data analytics, and robotics into agriculture to achieve EU Green Deal goals. It outlines the document's scope, detailing the strategies for dissemination, communication, and exploitation (DEC) to maximize the project's impact across different stakeholder groups.

Chapter 2: DEC Methodology and Approach

This chapter outlines the robust methodology for the DEC plan, which is inspired by the SOSTAC model. It includes a situation analysis, clear objectives, identification of stakeholders and strategies, and detailed methods and activities for effective communication. The approach is divided into four phases: Mission Strategy Vision, Raise Awareness, Synergies and Network Multipliers, and Post-project Sustainability & Impact, each designed to ensure the DEC plan's successful implementation and completion of its objectives.

Chapter 3: Dissemination Activities

The dissemination activities focus on ensuring that the project's outcomes, knowledge, and opportunities are effectively communicated to target communities. This chapter outlines various activities such as market and industry events, open days, webinars, and the Smart Droplets Academy. It aims to introduce the Smart Droplets platform, demonstrate the effectiveness and environmental benefits of its solutions, foster collaborations, and support continuous use and adaptation of the technologies in research and commercial applications.

Chapter 4: Communication Activities

The communication activities are designed to inform, promote, and share the project's impact with a broader audience. This chapter details the development of a strong visual identity, the use of digital channels such as social media and the project website, and the production of newsletters and press releases. It includes KPIs for tracking engagement, such as website pageviews, social media followers, and participation in media events.

Chapter 5: Exploitation Activities

This chapter describes the strategy for exploiting project results, both commercial and non-commercial. It includes the identification and validation of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), market analysis, funding opportunities, and the development of joint and individual exploitation plans. The exploitation strategy aims to ensure the innovations are utilized effectively during and beyond the project's lifecycle, with a focus on sustainability and scalability.

Chapter 6: Conclusions

The conclusions summarize the progress and enhancements made in the DEC plan from previous versions, highlighting improved strategies based on feedback and evaluation. This chapter emphasizes the importance of

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stakeholder engagement, collaboration with complementary initiatives, detailed exploitation strategies, and a robust framework for monitoring and evaluation. It sets a clear path forward to maximize the impact of Smart Droplets innovations in the agricultural sector.

Annex A presents the project's brand book.

Annex B provides the logo variations of Smart Droplets that will be used for different media.

Annex C presents Smart Droplets' social media banners that will be used on the website and social media.

Annex D provides the presentation template.

Annex E provides the deliverable template.

Annex F Provides the text template.

Annex G provides the brochures that have been created to promote Smart Droplets project during partners' participation in events.

Annex H provides the 3 posters that have been developed, one for the project in a nutshell, one for the Spanish pilot and the other one for the Lithuanian pilot.

Annex I provides the factsheets that have been developed during the current reporting period.

Annex J provides the roll-up banner that partners utilise when they are representing the project.

Annex K present the wide variety of communication material that has been created.

Annex L presents the zoom background that has been design in order to promote the project during online meetings, workshops, events.

Annex M provides the template that has been used in order to create the first press release and it will be utilised again for the upcoming ones.

Annex N provides the event planning template to be used for gathering information from partners regarding the events they are already planning on attending.

Annex O provides the synergy mapping template that partners will complete with information on existing projects, networks, alliances etc., that they are currently part of and could be relevant to Smart Droplets.

Annex P provides the publication planning template that partners will complete with information on peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, any other planned publications.

Annex Q provides the template of Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue.

Annex R specifies the strategic analytic tools that will be exploited during the development of the Go-to-market strategy.

Annex S presents the Business model canvas.

Annex T presents the structure of the first Smart Droplets Podcast Season

2. DEC Methodology and Approach

A robust DEC plan is fundamental for creating lasting impact and will provide a concrete roadmap for partners. It aims to boost the growth of the Smart Droplets ecosystem, raise awareness of project activities, and maximise impact among key stakeholders and target groups at the broader social, policy, and industry levels.

The Smart Droplets DEC plan is inspired by the **SOSTAC model**¹ which includes the following key elements: Situation analysis, Objectives, Stakeholders & Strategy, Methods & activities, Control through concrete KPIs.

Figure 3: Smart Droplets DEC methodology

- **Situation Analysis:** A state-of-play analysis will be conducted in which the current challenges to be addressed by the project, the consortium's expertise, the scientific, societal and economic impacts during and after the project, and the potential IPR of the results are identified and explained.
- **Objectives:** The DEC plan will elaborate upon clear and measurable objectives that will be achieved through the implementation of communication, dissemination and exploitation measures.
- **Stakeholders & Strategy:** Identification of target groups and key messages for effective communication strategy.
- **Methods & Activities:** The DEC plan will build upon activities, tools and channels. It includes the contributions expected from partners, and their distribution over the duration of the project. Open Science practices will be factored into all aspects of DEC implementation.
- **Control:** Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) with specific targets will be used to monitor the progress of the DEC implementation. Templates for partner reporting will also be used together with digital tools for record keeping, all of which will be presented in the Chapter 2.5.

¹ <https://prsmith.org/sostac/>

2.1. Smart Droplets DEC Time Plan

2.1.1. Phases

A division of the DEC plan into four phases (Figure 4) is crucial, ensuring both its successful implementation and the completion of the aforementioned objectives. The four phases of the DEC plan—Phase 1: Mission, Strategy, Vision, Phase 2: Raise awareness, Phase 3: Synergies and network multipliers, Phase 4: Post-project sustainability & Impact—span from the beginning of the project until after its end, enhancing post-project sustainability.

Figure 4: Smart Droplets DEC phases

Phase 1: Mission, Strategy, Vision (M01-M06)

During the first six months of the project, the foundation for all subsequent communication, dissemination, and exploitation of results was established. A recognisable project identity has been designed through a strong visual identity (facilitated by a brand book – Annex A) and digital presence (website, social media). This phase will also include creating the first promotional materials (brochure, banner, press release), planning event participation, compiling and evaluating potential synergies. Specific activities have been assigned to partners, and a preliminary schedule has been established. All partners have been informed about the specific guidelines that they need to follow for D&C outreach and reporting.

Phase 2: Awareness, Consideration & Demonstration (M06-M24)

During the second phase and as the project results unfold, the focus will be to:

- generate and retain leads by providing up-to-date valuable content.
- establish ties with other related projects through participatory workshops/events, e-Newsletters, panel discussions, and key umbrella initiatives.

More importantly, during this phase, the 'explore and transform' events will be organised, where value chain partners will network and share knowledge. Additional and updated promotional materials such as brochures, videos, rollups, etc. will be developed to disseminate the findings and engage seafood producers, processors, and other relevant enterprises.

Phase 3: Synergies & Network multipliers (M24-42)

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During the third phase there, the focus will be on exploitation and developing a go-to-market strategy for the project's results such as Smart Droplets solution, Retrofit kit, and Sprayer with a direct injection system. A sustainability plan will be created identifying potential private or public funding, to sustain results beyond the end of the project.

Phase 4: Post-project Sustainability and Impact (Years 5 to 9)

RFF will maintain key dissemination and communication tools after the completion of the project by:

- Maintaining the project's website and social media accounts. This will include reposting relevant research or work done by project partners and posting links to events, and open access publications.
- Updating partner contact details on the website each semester to facilitate engagement with key internal and external stakeholders and potential collaborators, including the co-programmed partnership on AI, Data and Robotics and funded actions related to this partnership.
- Responding to enquiries from the website.
- Continuing to pursue synergies and cooperation with new projects and initiatives.
- Providing links to these projects and initiatives on the website to direct interested parties to the most relevant and up to date entities continue the work begun by Smart Droplets.

These measures aim both to highlight the ongoing use and reuse of the projects results and ensure lasting interest and engagement with the project's broader objectives. They will be expanded upon and further developed in the final iteration of the DEC plan. In addition, a multi-faceted, sustainability plan with tools to maintain and strengthen the ecosystem, ongoing collaborations and support the forward trajectory of Smart Droplets solutions will be created as part of the deliverable Sustainability, Scalability & IPR Management Strategy, which was developed in M06 and will be updated annually (M18, M30, M42).

2.2. Target Groups and messages

The Smart Droplets project recognises that effective engagement extends beyond a mere proclamation of innovation. It necessitates a strategic understanding of diverse stakeholders, each with their distinct interests and aspirations. This awareness prompted an intricate classification of target groups, an endeavour that began with the project's inception and has evolved through the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan.

Smart Droplets' resonance is not limited to a universal message; it's in the precision with which it caters to the specific objectives of each group. While the overarching ambition is to advance agricultural practices through technology, the project acknowledges that real impact is born from customized communication.

Within this framework, Smart Droplets' target groups emerge as focal points, each deserving of a tailored approach:

Smart Droplets has identified **seven (7) key target groups** (TGs) to achieve the D&C objectives:

1. Tech Manufacturers and System Integrators
2. Farmers
3. Agrifood Extension service providers
4. AI/Data/Robotics providers
5. Researchers & Academia
6. EDIH/DIHs/AI, Data and Robotics Innovation Networks
7. Policy Makers and Regulators

More precisely, distinctive key messages have been crafted for each target group, succinctly encapsulating the singular advantages that Smart Droplets and its outcomes offer, presented in a clear and comprehensible statement (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Smart Droplets target groups and their key messages

TG#1: Tech Manufacturers and System Integrators

Developers of industrial automation equipment, robotics, tractors manufacturers, sprayer manufacturers, hardware, robot system integrators, software and middleware.

Message for this TG: *Be at the forefront of digital agriculture, enter new markets, expand portfolios and network with end users, researchers and policy makers.*

TG#2: Farmers

Apple farmers, Wheat farmers, farmers in Spain and Lithuania, European farm managers/administrators/farmers, all types of farmers and farming activities that require/apply fertilization and/or pesticides through spraying.

Message for this TG: *Unlock the potential of SFTs and understand what is truly efficient, sustainable and economical at crop management level.*

TG#3: Agrifood Extension service providers

Public and private service providers, agricultural consultants, and other AKIS actors.

Message for this TG: *Offer clients the most up-to-date knowledge and tools for selecting, using SFTs for crop management.*

TG#4: AI/Data/Robotics providers

AI, Data and Robotics Associations

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Message for this TG: *Support businesses in their digital transformations and promote cooperation between industry and agriculture through AI, data and robotics.*

TG#5: Researchers & Academia

EIP-AGRI and thematic Networks, EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, SWG SCAR-AKIS, Multi-actor projects and Platforms.

Message for this TG: *Contribute to cutting-edge research in digital agriculture and take advantage of interdisciplinary opportunities and collaborations between similar goal-oriented projects.*

TG#6: EDIH/DIHs/AI, Data and Robotics Innovation Networks

Agrifood, Robotics, AI, Deep-tech DIHs, Machinery DIHs, European Robotics Network, the European Robotics Research Infrastructure Network, ELISE.

Message for this TG: *Gain first-hand opportunities to work with and test ground-breaking AI and robotics technologies and bring new opportunities to your DIHs members.*

TG#7: Policy Makers and Regulators

Agricultural & environmental Authorities, CAP governance bodies (e.g., paying agencies and certification bodies), standardisation bodies, EU's DG AGRI, DG ENV and public environmental monitoring authorities.

Message for this TG: *Implement digital agriculture-centred policies based on evidence and farm data. Monitor and evaluate the sustainability and impact of those policy measures at the farm, regional, national level.*

Smart Droplets employs a spectrum of communication channels to engage these groups, with specific tools and channels strategically scheduled to reach the identified target groups as depicted below:

Figure 6: Smart Droplets target groups and corresponding DC activities and channels

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Additionally, to approach furthermore the above-mentioned target groups, the project's multi-actor approach will extend to the creation and implementation of the DEC plan, which means:

- Translating materials into partners' languages when applicable and favourable.
- Focusing on communicating information that matters to the information recipient.
- Using language, vocabulary and communication channels that are appealing and audience appropriate.
- Seeking synergies and collaboration opportunities with other projects, initiatives, networks, with and between academia, industry and government.
- Capitalising on partners' existing connections, networks, and programs.
- Fostering knowledge exchange activities and discussion.

In weaving these strategies, Smart Droplets strives for comprehensive reach and enduring influence. By recognising the specific needs of each target group, the project ensures that its groundbreaking innovations foster transformative change in the agricultural landscape, one droplet at a time.

2.3. Smart Droplets DEC Objectives & KPIs

2.3.1. DEC Objectives

To provide a verifiable trajectory geared towards clear milestones and an estimated deadline, the DEC plan objectives are **S.M.A.R.T** (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-Bound). The objectives below are used as the structural backbone of the DEC plan and are divided into dissemination, communication and exploitation objectives.

Dissemination Objectives

The dissemination activities are expected to diffuse the knowledge generated in the context of the project, aiming to ensure both a both a mid- and long-term impact. More specifically the dissemination activities will be carefully planned to ensure that the project's advancements are widely spread to the intended targeted audiences with appropriate tools and that the key stakeholders are engaged early and actively participate during each of the project's phases. Smart Droplet applies an intensive dissemination strategy that leads all the relevant actions from the very early stages of the project. The intended strategy is aligned with the below dissemination objectives:

- Bringing a critical mass of stakeholders and maximising outreach opportunities for Smart Droplets with targeted messaging and customised content.
- Disseminating scientific and technological knowledge generated during Smart Droplets and putting it to productive use via capacity building.
- Nurturing a collaboration framework for complementarities and synergies with projects, initiatives, and pan European networks of DIHs and capitalise on the results.
- Getting feedback from key stakeholder segments and potential users to ensure the developments are going in the right direction and iterate accordingly.
- Aligning and integrating dissemination, communication, community building activities with exploitation efforts to ensure sustainability of reusable assets.
- Encouraging smooth exploitation of Smart Droplets solution and seamless entry to market.

Communication Objectives

All actions that contribute to the diffusion of the project's results beyond the consortium and the direct stakeholders are considered as communication activities. In essence, communication activities focus on maximising the visibility of the project, through widely attracting a wide range of stakeholders who are invited to embrace the project's results and benefit from its advancements. To achieve this, attention will be paid to adapting the communication means, the measures, and the content to the needs and knowledge levels of the target groups, as well as to the status, progress and needs of the Smart Droplets project. To ensure that the communication measures effectively address the project's expectations, communication objectives have been set:

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- Pair focused content marketing and community-building strategies.
- Raise awareness, facilitate information exchange and capacity building on data-driven sustainability-oriented technology innovations.
- Encourage their acceptability by farmers, their advisors, policymakers.
- Reflect gender equality and inclusivity in the approach, tools and channels.

Exploitation Objectives

The exploitation refers to the action of making use of and benefiting from project results. Hence, Smart Droplets exploitation activities are recognised as the key enabler for success of the project. All the consortium partners are committed to the exploitation of the project's results. Their diverse and complementary research and business contexts provide all potential exploitation modalities and routes to bring Smart Droplets results to all targeted stakeholders, including manufacturers and system integrators, farmers, agrifood extension service providers, AI/data/robotics providers, researchers and academia, EDIH/DIHs/AI, data, robotics innovation networks, policy makers and regulators. A combination of activities will span throughout the project duration and will vary in intensity, based on the amount of information that can be made available and the results that will be produced during the project's lifetime. The main goal of Smart Droplets exploitation actions is to develop an effective way to exploit all commercial and non-commercial project results during and beyond the life of the project. To that end, the Smart Droplets exploitation strategy will focus on the following objectives:

- Setting the ground for the planning of exploitation related WP6 deliverables. This will require to first investigate links and dependencies between other project's WPs and tasks, as well as to capture exploitation related KPIs that should be achieved by the end of the project.
- Identifying and systematically validating Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that are foreseen in the project (commercial and non-commercial) through iterative sprints - with timelines adjusted to follow the timelines of piloting activities.
- Conducting a thorough market analysis to understand the market contexts, challenges, competitive landscapes, target markets and the market positioning of the commercial key exploitable results.
- Exploring various funding sources from both public and private sources in order to help Smart Droplets beneficiaries to secure follow-up investment and funding that can ensure financial sustainability of their business solutions.
- Developing joint and individual exploitation plans for project partners who are foreseen to have market exploitable assets during the project's timeframe (with the focus on both organizational and financial aspects).
- Planning the main actions to be undertaken by the project's consortium to ensure the sustainability of the project and its findings after the end of the project (Sustainability Plan)
- Outlining IPR management strategies to guide the joint and individual exploitation capabilities of the project partners.
- Guiding exploration of the policy and regulatory landscape in the context of the project, as well as to encourage active participation in standardisation processes for relevant topics and items developed by Smart Droplets.

2.3.2. KPI Methodology

To accurately gauge the Smart Droplets project's evolution and achievements, we have established a well-defined set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These KPIs are measurable targets that underpin ongoing monitoring and evaluation, guiding our assessment of the project's trajectory.

KPIs are divided into two main categories:

- **Dissemination KPIs:** Focus on transferring knowledge and making results accessible for practical use or future reference.
- **Communication KPIs:** Aim to inform, promote, and share the transformative impact and benefits of the project with the public.

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KPIs were meticulously crafted during the proposal phase and solidified in the Grant Agreement. They are distributed across the project's reporting periods and assigned to specific partners based on their areas of expertise. This allocation process, endorsed by the project coordinator, ensures that each partner is responsible for KPIs that align with their strengths and contributions. The assignment has been extensively shared with all stakeholders for validation.

Our approach to monitoring KPIs includes:

- **Monthly Reporting:** Partners provide regular updates on their assigned KPIs, ensuring continuous tracking of progress.
- **Social Media Analytics:** Analysing engagement and reach to measure the effectiveness of communication strategies.

Our methodology also extends to identifying potential barriers, mitigating risks, and accounting for gender-related variations to ensure comprehensive monitoring and evaluation.

Annexes N, O, and P provide the event planning, synergy mapping and publication planning templates, that are used for systematically tracking and evaluating KPIs. This holistic approach allows for real-time monitoring and timely adjustments.

We perform bi-annual evaluations to assess progress and make necessary strategic adjustments. This continuous rhythm of progress assessment ensures that we stay on course towards our project goals. The insights gleaned from these evaluations inform whether the project is on track, ready to align strategies with objectives, or if adjustments are warranted to steer towards successful outcomes.

Figure 7: Methodology for the division the KPIs

2.4. Multi Actor Approach methodology

2.4.1. Methodology

The cornerstone of the Smart Droplets project lies in its vibrant and participatory multi-actor approach (MAA), a strategic framework that propels the project beyond conventional boundaries. This approach reflects a profound commitment to harnessing the power of collaboration and diverse expertise to drive innovation in the realm of precision agriculture. The 'multi-actor' approach is key to the interactive innovation model. Interactive innovation "stresses relations between actors and process" where the most important resources are the diverse types of knowledge and their links, and interactive learning is the most valuable process. In this context, the

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multi-actor approach and the way diverse actors work well together is central to effectively delivering unique, impactful results. As so, Smart droplets uses a multi-actor approach, bringing together all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from a diverse set of partners and stakeholders to appraise, gather, cocreate and disseminate practical solutions to real needs and achieve the project's aims. Interactive innovation requires a participatory 'bottom-up approach,' facilitating those at the core of the project to influence project outcomes. This is a social process rather than a 'top-down' scientific approach and allows members to be involved in the entire development process, from decision-making to evaluation.

Figure 8: Smart Droplets stakeholder's groups

Unlike traditional methodologies, the Smart Droplets MAA isn't confined to the project's internal team; rather, it expands to encompass an extensive network of stakeholders. This network includes researchers, farmers, technology enthusiasts, policy makers, and local communities, all interconnected by a shared goal: to revolutionise agricultural spraying practices through technology and knowledge exchange. This approach acknowledges that each stakeholder brings a unique perspective, and by combining these perspectives, a richer tapestry of insights emerges.

Smart Droplets' MAA is characterised by several defining principles:

1. **Inclusivity and Collaboration:** The project is a stage where all stakeholders have a role to play. By inviting diverse actors into the fold, Smart Droplets catalyses meaningful interactions that transcend traditional boundaries. This inclusive environment ensures that all voices are heard, fostering a sense of ownership and commitment to the project's success.
2. **Customisation for Impact:** The approach is rooted in recognising the varied needs and aspirations of different stakeholders. By tailoring solutions to specific contexts and challenges, Smart Droplets ensures that its innovations are not one-size-fits-all but rather attuned to the complexities of the real world.
3. **Demonstration and Application:** Smart Droplets doesn't just stop at theoretical discussions. The project thrives on "proof of concept" demonstration cases that serve as living laboratories for innovation. By collaborating with local actors, new solutions are crafted and tested, igniting a cycle of continuous improvement.

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4. **Geographical Diversity:** The project's reach extends across multiple countries, each offering a unique backdrop for stakeholder engagement. This geographical diversity enriches the approach by bringing together stakeholders from diverse cultural, economic, and environmental backgrounds.
5. **Capacity Building and Learning:** Beyond the immediate project outcomes, Smart Droplets nurtures a culture of learning and empowerment. Capacity-building activities ensure that stakeholders are not just beneficiaries of innovations but active contributors to the evolving agricultural landscape.
6. **Real-world Impact:** The MAA underscores the project's commitment to generating real-world impact. By involving stakeholders across the value chain, from research to policy, Smart Droplets ensures that its innovations resonate with the industry's needs and broader societal objectives.

This dynamic approach echoes throughout every aspect of Smart Droplets. Stakeholders are invited to shape the project's course, engage in collaborative decision-making, and contribute their unique expertise. This active participation ensures that the innovations are grounded, practical, and aligned with the aspirations of those who stand to benefit most.

Furthermore, the project's multi-actor approach extends to communication and dissemination strategies. By sharing knowledge through diverse platforms, Smart Droplets fosters a community of practice that thrives on the exchange of insights and experiences.

In sum, the Smart Droplets MAA embodies the essence of interactive innovation, where the convergence of diverse perspectives fuels a collective journey toward transformative change. By embracing collaboration, customization, and a shared commitment to impact, the project sets a precedent for a more inclusive and effective approach to shaping the future of precision agriculture.

2.4.2. Key Scenarios

The process of interactive innovation followed by Smart Droplets, will involve a series of specific scenarios and tools (based upon the LIAISON project Practitioner Handbook²) which have been identified to ensure interactive innovation and the multi-actor approach are utilized during the project implementation, shown in the figure below. These range from engaging and incentivising actors/stakeholders to become involved, to co-creation, to applying new knowledge on the ground.

Figure 9: Key scenarios in multi-actor approach

² <https://liaison2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/LIAISON-Assessment-Tools.pdf>

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For each of the above mentioned six key scenarios, relevant tools have been identified while some of them have already been tested during the proposal stage:

Scenario 1: ENGAGING

Tool: STAKEHOLDERS PRIORITISATION

The tool is used for the prioritisation of the identified stakeholders' groups assessing the types of actors involved in the multi-actor approach. The prioritisation has already been made by the project partners during the proposal and team-building phase and it was based on the specific needs that Smart Droplets aims to address. An assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of each of the stakeholders' groups was also made. The specific order of this prioritisation process is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Prioritisation of stakeholders

Personas³ are another tool that could be used to gain a better understanding of stakeholders and registering their needs with services design methods to strengthen stakeholder engagement.

Scenario 2: EXAMINING

Tool: JOURNEY MAPPING

The tool is used for understanding the experiences and knowledge of the stakeholders within the project, identifying impacts of the project and their subjective evaluations of the project. The tool intends to assess the extent to which the stakeholder's experiences match with what the project envisaged and intended, pinpointing events and experiences. Journey mapping tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

³ <https://servicedesigntools.org/tools/personas>

The journey mapping tool was applied in the Smart Droplets event planning in the following ways:

- **Identifying Stakeholder Engagement Points:** The Journey Mapping tool was employed to map out critical engagement points, such as the **Spraying Applications Working Groups** held in April and May 2024 and will be employed in the planning of the **Open Day Events**. By analysing the expected journeys of different stakeholders, as well as what they expect from each Smart Droplets event, how they view Smart Droplets and its solution, as the tool helped identify when their input would be most valuable, guiding the timing and focus of these events.
- **Tailoring Events to Stakeholder Needs:** Events like the **Smart Droplets Academy Training Sessions** were designed using insights from the Journey Mapping process. This ensured that each event was structured to address the specific interests of farmers, industry representatives, and policymakers.
- **Anticipating Outcomes:** Before events like the **“Unlocking the Power of Robotics in Agri-Food”** workshop, the tool was used to anticipate likely stakeholder responses and challenges. This allowed us to structure the agendas to address potential concerns proactively, facilitating more effective and focused discussions.
- **Incorporating Feedback:** After these events, the Journey Mapping tool was used to integrate the feedback received back into the stakeholders' journeys. This iterative approach enabled the project team to adjust future engagements, such as refining the content of subsequent **Training Sessions** or modifying the approach to **Technology Demonstrations**, based on real-world stakeholder input.

Scenario 3: CREATING

Tool: GROUND RULES: IDENTIFICATION OF OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF AGREEMENT-BASED COOPERATION

The tool is used for assessing cultural norms, held by different actors involved in multi-actor work, that should be respected in the interactive innovation process to enhance how the potential of a diverse group is realised. The tool has been used during project development stage, but it can be used iteratively throughout the interactive innovation process.

Scenario 4: ADDRESSING

Tool: TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem-Solving)

The tool is used for assessing how actors are examining challenges and opportunities in the interactive innovation process, facilitating them to look at challenges and opportunities from new perspectives as well as engage in new forms of external knowledge to fuel interactive innovation. TRIZ tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 5: APPLYING

Tool: WHAT, WHO, WHY, WHERE, WHEN & HOW

The tool is used for planning multi-actor tasks in advance, identifying:

- Which actors & stakeholders will be involved – Who?
- The tasks they will be involved in – What?
- Why would they want to be involved in such tasks – Why?
- The logistics and approach of the tasks – Where? When? and
- How? The tool has been used during project development stage allowing partners to avoid fatigue, duplication and to maximise opportunities for synergies between tasks.

Scenario 6: EVALUATING

Tool: ‘CAUSES AND EFFECTS’: BUILDING HYPOTHESES: LINKING ACTIONS TO RESULTS

The tool is used for facilitating partners to generate hypotheses regarding the causes and effects of actions leading to actions, then to results and subsequently to objectives and breaking it down, fact-checking and proofing. It also allows participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting their plans. The tool will be used throughout the project implementation.

2.5. Planning and reporting procedures

2.5.1. Event and communication reporting

During the first months of the project, the seamless execution of timely reporting and effective monitoring for all dissemination and communication activities was of paramount importance. To facilitate this process, RFF devised an online form, exemplified below, to systematically gather input from our consortium partners. This form was designed to capture the intricacies of their undertaken measures while ensuring a streamlined reporting structure. Within this framework, partners were entrusted with the responsibility of furnishing comprehensive feedback on their dissemination and communication endeavours on a monthly basis. This practice allowed for a meticulous tracking of project progress and a real-time assessment of the alignment between planned activities and actual implementation.

Figure 11: Smart Droplets old reporting form

However, as the project evolved, it was recognised the need for an even more refined and collaborative approach to KPI reporting. As a result, a transition was made from the initial online form to a more interactive and adaptable tool, constructed using Google Spreadsheets. This solution fostered enhanced communication and collaboration between partners, facilitating a more robust data exchange process for the measured outcomes. This strategic shift empowered partners to provide granular insights into their progress. This iterative process ensures that KPIs remain aligned with project objectives, ultimately contributing to more effective impact measurement and strategic decision-making. Still, each month, all partners are requested to update this online inventory of any communication or dissemination activities and deposit corresponding promoting material such as photos, reports, etc. in a designated folder. This procedure has proven that it reinforces accountability and engagement with the dissemination and communication process. RFF is responsible for monitoring the KPIs on a monthly basis and give updates to the rest of the partners at relevant meetings. In case, significant, or repeated deviations are recorded from certain partners, the coordinator will be officially informed. Deviations will have to be justified, discussed among partners, and changes on the DEC strategy will be reported on the updated versions of the DEC plan. In total, this online google spreadsheet has been developed and uploaded on the project's shared Drive and is available to all partners. The spreadsheet includes the following:

- **Sheet 1: Instructions** - The workbook provides instructions, a description of the KPIs, the breakdown per reporting period and a sheet dedicated to each partner. In each spreadsheet, the respective participating organisation can see the KPIs assigned to them, and the dissemination and communication activities that need to be reported, accordingly, per month of action.

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Instructions
1. This file has been designed for reporting dissemination & communication activities that relate to the KPIs described in the GA and the distributed targets per partner.
The first page provides the total KPI targets and the breakdown per reporting period.
2. Each partner has a dedicated sheet with three tables:
<p>a. KPI distribution:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The overall target for each KPI per partner. <p>b. Dissemination Activities (e.g. events, synergies, publications):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Please use the drop down menu to select the KPI category, then provide the name, date and link. - Please indicate if the activity should be considered a joint activity (external to the consortium), and if yes, please indicate with whom. <p>c. Communications Activities (e.g. social media, interviews):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Please use the drop down menu to select the type of publication or communication channel, then provide the date and a link where it can be found.
3. In case the dissemination/communication activity does not fall under the already existing KPI categories, fill in the drop-down menu with the option " Other ", while filling-in all the other columns.
4. Click on links for each month to upload pictures or relevant materials (e.g., agenda, presentations) from events that may be used for dissemination and communication purposes.
<p>Please note:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * we suggest posts come from your organization's social media account, rather than a personal account and that you tag Smart Droplets * please include the dates and links

Figure 12: Instruction for the new reporting form

- **Sheet 2: KPI Clarification** - To minimise confusion regarding the scope of each KPI and to help partners decide which KPI their activity corresponds to a dedicated sheet is included in the reporting workbook. The focus is on the dissemination KPIs which have greater ambiguity. All descriptions have been validated by the Project Coordinator

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	M1	M12	M13	M24	M25	M42	Clarifications
D1	Co-organization of events								
D1.1	Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid)	10	1	3	6				Events organized or co-organized by the partners to promote Smart Droplets' project and solutions in the targeted market and industry sectors
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	6	-	-	6				Events open for everyone to visit the demo areas and to understand the importance of our project
D1.3	"Spotlight on..." Live & On-Demand webinars	6	1	2	3				Webinars organized or co-organized by the partners that are broadcasted both live and on-demand in fields that align with the project's and partners' areas of expertise.
D1.4	Smart Droplets Solution Showcase and final event	1					1		The final event of the project aiming to present the results of the project.
D1.5	50 hours of physical and online training content	50	-	-	25	25			Physical and online training content produced available after the project is due.
D2	Scientific and technical outreach								
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	5	-	2	3				Scholarly papers and conference contributions that have undergone evaluation by field experts
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	5	-	2	3				Publication of technical briefs in renowned magazines or publications that specialize in the fields of Robotics, Data, and AI
D2.3	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	12	-	-	12				Project's public deliverables available for the general public
D2.4	Competition events (hackathons)	2	-	-	2				Hackathons, competitive events, held within a specific period aiming to generate results that can be utilised by the project.
D3	Networking and synergies and liaison activities								
D3.1	Representation in WGs	3	-	2	1				Establish connections with and participate in working groups dedicated to project-specific topics.
D3.2	Representation in alliances	5	-	3	2				Establish connections and partnerships with alliances to foster collaboration, share resources etc.
D3.3	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	10	-	5	5				Engage in collaborative endeavors with EU initiatives/projects to leverage collective expertise, share best practices, and maximize the impact of efforts in the field of AI, data, and robotics.
D4	Policy measures and standardization efforts								
D4.1	Sets of standardization recommendations	2	-	-	2				Develop comprehensive sets of recommendations for standardization in order to guide and promote the widespread adoption of AI, Robotics, and Data technologies in agriculture.
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	5	-	2	3				Collaborate with digital agriculture technology initiatives and movements to issue joint press releases and statements, aimed at raising awareness, advocating for policy measures, and highlighting the potential benefits of AI, Robotics, and Data technologies in the agricultural sector.
D5	Ecosystem building								
D5.1	MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups	20	-	10	10				Establish agreements (Memorandum of Understanding / Letter of Interest) with industry associations and groups to foster collaboration, knowledge exchange, and joint efforts in promoting the adoption and utilization of the Smart Droplets solution.
D5.2	MoUs/ Lols signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up	5	-	2	3				Forming non-binding agreements (Memorandum of Understanding / Letter of Interest) with investors and other potential partners to secure support and resources for refining, commercializing, and expanding the Smart Droplets solution.
D5.3	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI	5	-	4	1				Establish connections with Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) that are associated with AI, Data, and Robotics to facilitate collaboration, leverage expertise, and ensure sustained uptake of the Smart Droplets solution beyond the duration of public funding.

Figure 13: Clarifications for the KPIs

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- Sheets 3 through 9: Individual Partner Reporting Sheets** – A set of distinct reporting sheets has been crafted for each consortium partner. These tailored sheets serve as a user-friendly and efficient platform for documenting their executed dissemination and communication activities. The process has been streamlined for ease of use and accuracy. Within these sheets, a user-friendly drop-down menu is integrated under the KPI category tab. This intuitive feature empowers partners to conveniently select the relevant category for their executed dissemination or communication action. Subsequent fields facilitate the input of essential information, encompassing data specifics, activity names, associated links, and other pertinent details. To facilitate differentiation between no reporting and non-participation in relevant activities, partners can indicate "Nothing to report" if they have no dissemination or communication activities to report. Additionally, to support visual documentation, each month features clickable links to designated folders for partners to upload photos and other pertinent materials such as agendas, presentations, and minutes. These resources may be leveraged for reporting, dissemination, or communication purposes. This comprehensive framework ensures a holistic approach to tracking, documenting, and sharing project activities. This structured format enhances the clarity and consistency of reporting, ensuring that all vital information is accurately captured. The user-friendly design encourages partners to comprehensively document their activities, fostering an environment of collaboration and data accuracy.

September 2022									
Photos and other material									
Dissemination KPI						Communication KPI			
KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link
Nothing to report						Nothing to report			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
October 2022									
Photos and other material									
Dissemination KPI						Communication KPI			
KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link
Nothing to report						Nothing to report			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
November 2022									
Photos and other material									
Dissemination KPI						Communication KPI			
KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link
Nothing to report						Nothing to report			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼			

Figure 14: Clarifications for the KPIs

Finally, a reminder is sent to each partner at the end of the month reminding them to complete the reporting form by the second week of the following month. The form is also available on project’s google drive, enabling partners to go back and review or add missing activities and it also allows for different members from the same organisation to provide input without redundancy. RFF monitors the reporting form monthly to keep track of engagement, and on a six-month basis consolidates the results of the reporting forms and evaluates them next to the KPIs. The findings of these reports will serve to monitor targets and inform DEC strategies, enabling pivoting when necessary or to inform partners when additional effort is required.

To precision and efficiency in monitoring the KPIs, RFF has meticulously developed and deployed a dedicated monitoring tool to track the progress of partners’ achieved KPIs. This robust tool is constructed utilizing the capabilities of Google Spreadsheets, enabling real-time monitoring of KPI progress across reporting periods and partners. Figure 15 displays the comprehensive monitoring spreadsheet, where dissemination and communication KPIs are thoughtfully categorised into three distinct reporting periods. Within each reporting

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period, two validation statuses have been established to ensure both the timely completion of KPIs and the prompt implementation of mitigation measures, should the need arise.

#	Communication KPIs	M1-M12	1st check	Final check	Status	M13-M24	1st check	Final check	Status	M25-M42	1st check	Final check	Status	Sum	Target	Status
C1 Full Branding & Web Design																
C1.1	Printable brand book	1	1		Completed									1	1	
C1.2	Website	1	1		Completed									1	1	
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6	6		Completed									6	6	
C1.4	Posters	3	3		Completed									3	3	
C1.5	Brochures	3	3		Completed									3	3	
C1.6	Project factsheet	3	3		Completed									3	3	
C1.7	Notepad	1	1		Completed									1	1	
C1.8	Roll-up	1	1		Completed									1	1	
C1.9	Folder	1	1		Completed									1	1	
C1.10	Banner	1	1		Completed									1	1	
C1.11	Stickers	1	1		Completed									1	1	
C1.12	Virtual background	1	1		Completed									1	1	
C1.13	Social Media template	1	1		Completed									1	1	
C2 Digital & Social Media																
C2.1	Unique website pageviews	1000	420	917	Ongoing	3000				5000				1337	5000	
C2.2	No. of views/ downloads													0	450	

Figure 15: Monitoring tool for the KPIs

Moreover, within the same integrated spreadsheet file, individual sheets are thoughtfully allocated to each partner. These dedicated sheets are meticulously updated by RFF based on partners' monthly reports, consolidating their achievements and contributions. This meticulous approach further enhances transparency, collaboration, and accountability, streamlining the process of assessing our collective progress and promptly addressing any potential challenges.

#	KPI	TARGET														
Dissemination KPIs																
D1 Co-organization of events																
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	3														
D2 Scientific and technical outreach																
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	1														
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	2														
D3 Networking and synergies and liaison activities																
D3.2	Representation in alliances	1														
D4 Policy measures and standardization efforts																
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	1														
D5 Ecosystem building																
D5.1	MoUs/ LoIs with industry associations & groups/projects	2														
Communication KPIs																
C2 Digital & Social Media																
C2.3	Blog posts and Social media posts	10														
C3 Press Outreach & Event Planning																
C3.2	Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio, magazines, newspaper)	1														

Figure 16: Monitoring tool for each partner

2.5.2. Event Planning

For the Smart Droplets projects, the necessary event planning takes part in two phases. The initial phase is the logging and documentation phase. Twice a year, that is on a 6-month period, an event planning form is sent to the consortium partners to report on the events that are already in their calendars. Partners are expected to provide the following information: a brief description including the date, location, target groups and a preliminary suggestion as to the role/implication for Smart Droplets (i.e., workshop, booth). Gathering information on relevant events supports decision making of event planning. Nevertheless, the form is sent to partners, and the responses are compiled using an online reporting tool for easy reference and record-keeping. Several potential events have already been identified.

For a clearer visualisation of schedules and details and promotion of effective coordination of activities, a revised planning table has been created. This enhancement streamlines event management, ensuring each event is planned and executed to maximise its impact and reach.

#	Date	Partner	Name of event	Location	Role / Description and Links	Scale, Target Groups

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Table 2: Smart Droplets Event Planning Example

The second phase involves the selection of events based on the guidelines shown in the Figure below. When selecting the events for Smart Droplets to participate in, both the alignment with the project's objectives and budget, on, as well as the need to adapt to each partner's individual activities, should be taken into consideration.

Guidelines for event selection

Figure 17: Guidelines for event selection

The most recently updated list of identified events that are relevant to Smart Droplets is shown in Table 3.

#	Date	Partner	Name of event	Location	Role / Description and Links	Scale, Target Groups
Annual						
1	Annual	RFF	Agrotica (Exhibition)	Thessaloniki, Greece	Workshop, seminar, booth https://agrotica.helexpo.gr/en	Regional; Private sector, agri-rural communities
2	Annual	RFF	Panhellenic Congress on the Development of Greek Agriculture (Congress)	Thessaloniki, Greece	Presentation, Banners https://www.c-gaia.gr/en/conferences/	National; Authorities & Policy Makers
3	Annual	RFF	Panhellenic Young Farmers' Conference (Conference)	Greece	Presentation, Banners Website: N/A	National; Farmers and AgriCooperatives, Extension & Advisory Services,

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						Authorities & Policy Makers
4	Annual	RFF	AgriBusiness Forum	Greece	Presentation, Banners https://agribusinessforum.org/	National; Industry Associations & Groups, Institutional & Private Partners
2022						
5	Sep 29	EUT	AGORA TECNOLÓGICA FIRA DE SAN MIQUEL	Lleida, Catalonia, Spain	Talk, presenter https://www.cambralleida.org/producte/29-09-2022-al-30-09-2022-agra-tecnologica-de-la-fira-agraria-de-sant-miquel-2022/	Regional; Farmers and AgriCooperative, Private sector, government
2023						
6	June 29	FEMAC	X Strategic Immersion of Cluster FEMAC	Tortosa, Spain	Presentation Smart Droplets Project https://www.femac.org/immersio-estrategica/	Local; Cluster Members
7	Aug 29	WU	Workshop on Digital Twins	Wageningen University	https://www.wur.nl/en/calendar-1/show/operationalizing-digital-twins-in-agriculture-with-machine-learning-1.htm	30; Researcher and agricultural experts
8	Sep 29	EUT	ROSCON 2023	Madrid, Spain	Talk, presenter (Autonomous robots in AGRICULTURE: localization and navigation strategies using ROS for different agricultural use-cases) https://roscon.org.es/ROSCONMadrid2023.html	International; Academia, programmers, students
9	Oct 1-5	FEMAC	FRUIT ATTRACTION 2023	Madrid, Spain	Roll-Up Project https://www.ifema.es/fruit-attraction	International; International Growers
10	Oct 4-5	AUA	Conference	Thessaloniki, Greece	Smart Droplets, a visionary EU project, will proudly take part in the highly anticipated Synergy Days conference in Thessaloniki from 4th to 5th October 2023. As an	25 EU funded projects, >3000; digital innovators and experts of the agri-food sector, students

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					essential contributor to the European agri-food sector's digital innovation, Smart Droplets will join an esteemed group of 25 distinguished EU projects, showcasing its revolutionary purpose and the remarkable solutions it has developed. https://www.smartagrihub.eu/synergy-days	
11	Nov 12-18	AGROMA	AGRITECHNICA 2023	Hannover, Germany	https://www.agritechnica.com/	International
12	Nov 22	EUT	ROBOT 2023	Coimbra, Portugal	Talk, presenter https://robot2023.isr.uc.pt	International; Academia mostly
2024						
13	Feb 1-4	AGROMA	Agrotica	Thessaloniki, Greece	https://agrotica.helexpo.gr/en	Regional
14	March 10	WU	Presentation in Workshop on Crop Growth Modelling	Wageningen University	https://www.perc.nl/crop-modelling	30; Researcher and agricultural experts
15	Sep 27	EUT	FIRA SAN MIQUEL	-	Talk, presenter https://firadelleida.com/santmiquel/ca/	Regional; Farmers and AgriCooperative, Private sector, government
16	Nov 6-10	AGROMA	EIMA	Bologna, Italy	www.eima.it	International
17	Nov 6	EUT	ROBOT 2024	Madrid, Spain	Paper submitted, waiting to be accepted https://eventos.upm.es/109808/detail/robot-2024-.html	International; Academia mostly
2025						
18	March 6-9	AGROMA	Agrothessaly	Larissa, Greece	https://agrothessaly.helexpo.gr/en	Regional

Table 3 Identified relevant events for Smart Droplets

2.5.3. Networking and Synergies

Building synergies and expanding the Smart Droplets ecosystem is a significant priority of the DEC plan. Much of the project's work is built upon the experience, knowledge and/or data developed by partners during other projects. This collaborative approach extends to the DEC and will involve a four-step process.

Figure 18: Networking and Synergies Phases

Phase 1: Identification

Potentially mutually beneficial partnerships and synergies are being identified. A new template has been created for partners to complete, requesting information on any other project’s networks or initiatives they are currently participating in that could be relevant to Smart Droplets. This catalogues essential details, which can be seen in the following table.

Smart Droplets Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of Initiative(s)	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities

Table 4: Smart Droplets synergies & liaison mapping template

This template (Table 4) is distributed every six months by RFF to account for new projects that are beginning. Smart Droplets considers both projects that are near completion and those that will run in parallel. Connecting with projects that will be ending provides network expansion opportunities for Smart Droplets while enabling the other projects to meet sustainability goals and keep the momentum of their project going. Projects, networks, and initiatives running in parallel provide several opportunities to strengthen communication pathways and conduct joint activities. The identified projects after the most recent update are shown in Table 5.

Relevant projects for Smart Droplets	
	OPTIMA will develop an eco-friendly Integrated Pest Management (IPM) framework for vineyards, apple orchards, and carrots. The project will enhance disease prediction models, create spectral early detection systems using deep learning, and improve precision

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	<p>spraying techniques with innovative sprayers tailored to each crop. By integrating novel bio-pesticides and optimizing disease control methods, OPTIMA aims to reduce agrochemical use, minimize residues, and lessen health and environmental impacts. The IPM system will be field-tested and assessed for efficacy, with a focus on sustainable and scalable agricultural practices.</p> <p>http://optima-h2020.eu/the-project/</p>
	<p>Agriculture is susceptible to the cost and scarcity of labour, and making cultivation practices more efficient and sustainable is critical. EU-funded ROBS4CROPS is a vital catalyst in accelerating high-tech robotics and automated technologies in the European food and farm industry. Building upon the existing agricultural machinery, standards, and best practices, the 4-year project will shape and deliver a flexible and modular, fully autonomous system ready for large-scale commercial trials. The trials will be conducted in partnership with commercial farms and business leaders from France, Greece, Spain, and the Netherlands. ROBS4CROPS will significantly reduce farmers' dependency on hired labour, increase safety, reduce the use of inputs and the overall carbon footprint of food production.</p> <p>https://robs4crops.eu/</p>
	<p>Europe's agri-food sector is facing a big challenge: ensuring environmentally-friendly production at lower costs and with a shortage of labourers. The solution requires high-tech modernisation of farming. Robotics can play a big role. The agROBOfood project, a consortium of 39 partners aims to accelerate the sector's digital transformation through the adoption of robotic technologies. To boost the uptake of robotic solutions, it will establish a sustainable network of digital innovation hubs (DIHs). At the heart of the project are innovation experiments (IEs) that will be organised and monitored by the DIHs. The European robotics community will be involved throughout the project to ensure maximum synergy. This will maximise the return of investments from the digital transformation of agri-food.</p> <p>https://agrobofood.eu/</p>
	<p>With robotics technologies advancing at breakneck speeds, many industry sectors are eager to welcome them. One of these is agriculture, which is facing the issue of phytopharmaceutical spraying and a need to reduce their over dosage while retaining efficiency and crop yield. The EU-funded SCORPION project will address many of the challenges involved while also developing a modular unmanned tractor in cooperation with several agricultural and robotics associations, institutions and companies. The goal is to reduce phytopharmaceutical usage while maintaining crop yield, efficiency</p>

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	<p>and value. This machine will initially focus on steep-slope vineyards that present more difficulties during spraying.</p> <p>https://scorpion-h2020.eu/</p>
	<p>The project aims to develop a portable, knowledge-based system for on-the-spot food quality sensing and shelf-life prediction. This miniaturized smart system will detect food hazards, spoilage (including early signs), and food fraud by analysing bio-chemical data. It will also perform food component analysis, identification, and shelf-life prediction. Three use cases will be addressed: detecting mycotoxins in grains and nuts, identifying early spoilage in fruits, vegetables, meat, and fish, and detecting food fraud in alcoholic beverages, oil, milk, and meat. The system will integrate three sensors: a MEMS-based near IR spectrometer, a UV-VIS spectrometer, and a micro-camera, supported by UV-LED, white LED, and mini IR emitters. An advanced microcontroller will process spectrum images, with data communicated to a smartphone for further analysis via a cloud-based application. Advanced detection algorithms will be deployed in both the cloud and smartphone app. The PhasmaFOOD system will allow consumers to assess food quality and predict shelf-life on the spot.</p> <p>https://phasmafood.eu/</p>
	<p>The IoF2020 project aims to accelerate the adoption of IoT in agriculture to ensure safe, healthy food and enhance the competitiveness of Europe's farming and food sectors. By fostering a collaborative ecosystem of farmers, the food industry, technology providers, and research institutes, the project seeks to strengthen Europe's leadership in the global IoT industry. Led by Wageningen UR and involving 73 partners, IoF2020 builds on the successes of previous projects like FIWARE and IoT-A. The project centers on 19 use cases across five trials in the Arable, Dairy, Fruits, Vegetables, and Meat sectors, showcasing innovative IoT solutions. A lean multi-actor approach will focus on user acceptance, stakeholder engagement, and sustainable business models to advance technology readiness and adoption. The project promotes an open IoT architecture with reusable components and a security and privacy framework. Agile through dynamic budgeting and adaptive decision-making, IoF2020 includes a €6M mid-term open call for testing and expanding technical solutions. A strong dissemination strategy will ensure market visibility and drive the adoption of data-driven farming, autonomous operations, virtual food chains, and personalized nutrition for European citizens.</p> <p>https://www.iof2020.eu/</p>

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	<p>Most of Europe’s SMEs lag behind in data-driven innovation. To tackle this problem, the EU-funded EUHubs4Data project will build a European federation of Data Innovation Hubs based on existing key players in this area and connecting with data incubators and platforms, SME networks, AI communities, skills and training organisations and open data repositories. A European catalogue of data sources and federated data-driven services and solutions will be made accessible to European SMEs, start-ups and web entrepreneurs through the Data Innovation Hubs. Cross-border and cross-sector data-driven experimentation will be facilitated through data-sharing, as well as data- and service interoperability, becoming a reference instrument for growth in a global data economy and contributing to the creation of common European data spaces.</p> <p>https://euhubs4data.eu/</p>
	<p>Digital technologies in agriculture (DATs) can grow the sector by enhancing sustainability, performance and competitiveness byte by byte, but only if they are designed to support sustainability. In this context, the EU-funded QuantiFarm project will introduce a comprehensive assessment framework for independent qualitative and quantitative assessment of the multiple costs and benefits of DATs, as well as of their sustainability impact. Following a multi-actor approach, QuantiFarm will carry out 30 test cases across 20 European countries. The test cases will all be in commercial farms of different types, sizes, ownership and operating conditions from seven agricultural sectors. The aim is to assess the DATs used in the farms and feed the results to the QuantiFarm Toolkit to increase awareness and support future decision-making.</p> <p>https://quantifarm.eu/</p>
	<p>Food insecurity represents one of the biggest challenges in the 21st century. Edible insects emerge as a potentially sustainable solution for food for humans and animals. To improve mass production and breeding and reduce their costs, the development of research, innovation, farming protocols and standardisation is necessary as well as the robotisation and automation of insect farms. The EU-funded CoRoSect project focuses on the connection of research on bionomics and the life cycle of insects with new robotics tools and protocols for the automatization of insect farming. The project will establish innovative integrated cognitive robotics ecosystems that will replace operations demanding manual labour or continuous human supervision during the insects’ life cycle.</p> <p>https://corosect.eu/</p>

	<p>In an effort to enhance agricultural production, agricultural robots are being increasingly adopted. The number of discreet tasks to be automated, however, significantly reduces the flexibility of current solutions, thus impacting efficiency and limiting their take-up. The EU-funded FLEXIGROBOTS project aims to develop a platform that will help build heterogeneous multi-robot systems, allowing for vastly improved flexibility by using existing robots for multiple tasks. This could help produce higher-value data from a variety of sources and sensors, increasing operational autonomy and precision while greatly reducing costs and encouraging investment in robotics.</p> <p>https://flexigrobots-h2020.eu/</p>
	<p>Labour costs often represent up to 50 % of total production costs in the fresh food industry. Although the sector demands solutions to reduce them, the shift towards robotic automation is obstructed by the complex and contact-rich interactions needed. The EU-funded SoftGrip project will introduce a self-actuating soft gripper for the autonomous picking of delicate white button mushrooms. The project aims for low-cost, intelligent soft robotic grippers with embedded actuation, tactile sensing, recyclable materials and advanced fabrication techniques. It will develop a set of fast-computed modelling algorithms to enhance real-time model-based control schemes and advanced learning capabilities. SoftGrip will develop a learning-by-demonstration framework that will allow the robot to capture human picking skills, extendable to other similar tasks.</p> <p>https://www.softgrip-project.eu/</p>
	<p>Fruit cracking is one of the main physiological disorders limiting fruit quality and yield. It is a peel disorder occurring mainly during the pre-harvest stage due to climatic and environmental conditions and poor orchard management. The EU-funded CrackSense project will develop and upscale sensing technologies providing real-time sensor data through piloting activities concerning the fruit cracking problem in citrus, pomegranate, table grapes and sweet cherries. The Integrated CrackSense Solution will improve the sensor data collected into EU-wide data sets, including Earth Observation Data and other data sets concerning environmental conditions and used to monitor agricultural production. The solution will mitigate the effects of the cracking phenomenon reducing by half the yield losses due to cracking, allowing farmers efficient management and sustainable actions.</p>
	<p>AgML is the AgMIP transdisciplinary community of agricultural and machine learning modellers. AgML aspires to identify key research gaps and opportunities at the intersection of agricultural modelling and machine learning research, support enhanced collaboration and engagement between experts in these disciplines, and conduct and publish protocol-based studies to establish best practices for robust machine learning use in agricultural modelling.</p>

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	<p>https://www.agml.org/</p>
	<p>The Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation (AIOTI) leads, promotes, bridges and collaborates in IoT & Edge Computing and other converging technologies research and innovation, standardisation and ecosystem building providing IoT deployment for European businesses creating benefits for European society. AIOTI cooperates with other global regions to ensure removal of barriers to development of the IoT & Edge Computing market, while preserving the European values, including privacy and consumer protection.</p> <p>https://aioti.eu/</p>
	<p>BioSense Institute was founded to conduct multidisciplinary, needs-driven research and share it with a global network of forward-thinking stakeholders. The institute integrates Serbia's two promising sectors—ICT and agriculture—by conducting research in micro and nanoelectronics, communications, signal processing, remote sensing, big data, robotics, and biosystems. The goal is to support sustainable agriculture and positively impact people's lives. Recognized for its commitment to open innovation, BioSense engages strategically with regional stakeholders to drive economic growth. The institute collaborates with the agricultural community, government, businesses, and citizens to co-create the future of the agrifood sector, promoting integrated collaboration, shared value, and rapid adoption of advanced ICT in traditional farming and food production. BioSense believes innovation can be a widely practiced discipline, and this belief guides its research efforts.</p> <p>https://www.biosens.rs/en</p>
	<p>The BDVA is an industry-driven, international non-profit organization with over 240 members across Europe, including large corporations, SMEs, start-ups, research organizations, and academia. Focused on industry-led research and innovation in Data and AI, BDVA supports collaboration at the European level by providing tools and expertise for the co-creation and development of data-driven and AI applications. It advances key areas like data platforms, privacy, Industrial AI, business models, standardization, and high-performance computing. BDVA plays a significant role in European initiatives, being part of the H2020 Big Data Value cPPP, EuroHPC JU, and the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership. It has strong ties with Gaia-X, IDSA, and FIWARE through the Data Spaces Business Alliance and collaborates with various national AI initiatives and European communities. With its established community, BDVA is central to discussions on data, AI, and business opportunities, driving impact and innovation in the European economy.</p> <p>https://bdva.eu/</p>
	<p>The FUTURAL project is dedicated to empowering rural communities through innovative digital solutions aimed at overcoming social, environmental, and economic challenges. By developing and</p>

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	<p>implementing smart solutions tailored to rural needs, FUTURAL seeks to foster sustainable growth and resilience. Key initiatives include a Metasearch Platform that integrates various digital resources for easy access and Multi-Actor Pilots (MAPs) that engage local stakeholders in co-creating and testing these solutions. Additionally, FUTURAL has an Open Call to fund new smart solutions, enhancing the project's impact. These efforts aim to foster sustainable growth, resilience, and improved well-being in rural areas.</p> <p>https://futural-project.eu/</p>
	<p>The STELLA project aims to enhance plant health management through a digital system (STELLA PSS) that integrates AI, IoT sensors, and drones for early detection and monitoring of plant pests. This system will be tested in six Use Case Pilots (UCPs) across diverse regions including vineyards in France, wild forests in Greece, arable lands in Lithuania and Italy, and orchards in New Zealand and Greece. By focusing on eight significant quarantine and regulated non-quarantine pest (RNQP) diseases, the project promotes eco-friendly practices and aims to influence EU policies on pesticide reduction and agricultural digitalization. STELLA also includes capacity-building initiatives to equip stakeholders with necessary skills and fosters networking for knowledge exchange and policy support, thereby advancing sustainable pest management practices across Europe and New Zealand</p> <p>https://stella-pss.eu/</p>
	<p>ICAERUS is a European project dedicated to enhancing rural life through advanced drone applications in agriculture, forestry, and logistics. It showcases diverse use cases such as precision crop monitoring to improve agricultural practices, targeted drone spraying for effective pest control, livestock health monitoring over large areas, forestry management for biodiversity and health assessments, and enhancing rural logistics with efficient delivery systems. The project involves large-scale demonstrations, stakeholder engagement, and educational activities to ensure safe and efficient drone deployment, addressing potential risks and highlighting benefits. ICAERUS also promotes innovation through open calls, inviting stakeholders to propose new drone applications and solutions, fostering collaboration and advancing technological development. This initiative aims to improve operational efficiency and sustainability in rural areas, leveraging cutting-edge drone technology.</p> <p>https://icaerus.eu/</p>

Table 5: Relevant projects for Smart Droplets

Phase 2: Evaluation

To ensure synergies will benefit the project and align with Smart Droplets objectives, each potential project, initiatives and network is assessed against qualitative/quantitative indicators such as:

- Relevance.
- Estimated impact (e.g., visibility, added value).

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- Feasibility (e.g., timeline and resources).
- Terms for collaboration, etc.

The results of the evaluation are consolidated with the information provided by partners and a final decision will be made by the consortium.

Phase 3: Contact

Once it has been agreed upon that a synergy should be established, the most appropriate approach for making contact will be decided on a case-by-case basis.

Phase 4: Action

Communication pathways and joint activities will be decided after discussions with their representatives and the Smart Droplets consortium and will include (but are not limited to):

- Joint communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.
- Joint policy events.
- Coordinating research and/or joint publications.
- Sharing data, inputs and/or outputs.
- Participation in the other's events.
- Links to project and project events on website, social media.

To have a fully developed communication and dissemination portfolio, Smart Droplets takes into account the much-needed impact to be generated in the scientific domain, and more importantly will integrate itself into the development of several scientific, industry and policy publications as well as practice abstracts. Such publication will target the more technical experts of the targeted stakeholder groups and thus promote the projects and its findings among them. The consortium will put an effort for the majority of publications to implement Open Access and open peer review, in accordance with current EU regulations on Open Access and Open Science. Thus, publications will be potentially published in Open Research Europe and/or open-access journals (green or gold). A key aspect for Open Science is to make collected data available for future research and analysis, while avoiding the exposure of any personal data without consent. The availability of project outputs as Open Access will ensure:

1. far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports.
2. greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community (in this project above all farmers and advisors).
3. improve the likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse our results rather than start ab initio, thereby helping in terms of the reproducibility and continuity of research results.

2.5.4. Planning Article Submissions

Besides the creation of Press Releases and scientific publications, Smart Droplets aims to publish **10** articles in agriculture and related impactful industry magazines; to make the project and its results are known to the industrial stakeholders. Project partners are asked to complete the publication planning template by RFF every 6 months (Annex P). To maximize impact, guidelines and timing for identifying, selecting and producing publications using have been defined:

Guidelines for article submission

Figure 19: Smart Droplets article submission process

2.5.5. EC Tools

Smart Droplets will take advantage of several the tools offered by the European Commission to support dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and communication (C) of the project’s results (Figure 20).

Figure 20 Channels and Value EC tools for Smart Droplets

3. Dissemination Activities

The main objective of the Smart Droplets dissemination strategy is to ensure the project's outcomes, knowledge, and opportunities are effectively communicated to the appropriate target communities, making research results widely accessible. Shaped by the project's high technological readiness level (TRL >7), the dissemination strategy's objectives are to:

1. **Introduce** the Smart Droplets platform to showcase advanced AI and robotic technologies for sustainable agriculture and increase visibility among key stakeholders.
2. **Highlight** the results of field tests to demonstrate the effectiveness and environmental benefits of Smart Droplets solutions, thereby raising awareness.
3. **Foster** collaborations with other agri-tech research, policy, and innovation initiatives by leveraging existing networks and channels to maximize the dissemination reach.
4. **Engage** with farmers, agricultural businesses, policymakers, and researchers to gather feedback, validate findings, and ensure the solutions are practical, scalable, and meet real-world needs.
5. **Integrate** dissemination, communication, and ecosystem-building activities with exploitation and business strategies to facilitate market entry and scale-up of the project's outcomes.
6. **Support** the continuous use and adaptation of Smart Droplets technologies in ongoing research, policy development, and commercial applications.

The strategy emphasizes the project's high TRL by:

1. Highlighting the project's **maturity** to build trust among potential users and investors, demonstrating readiness for market deployment.
2. Engaging **end-users, industry stakeholders, and policymakers** to gather feedback, validate the technology, and refine the solutions for broader market applicability.
3. Leveraging existing **networks** and establishing **new partnerships** to promote the Smart Droplets solutions within the relevant ecosystems.
4. Clearly communicating the **environmental, economic, and operational benefits** observed during in-field tests to target audiences.
5. Providing stakeholders with comprehensive **information, case studies, and demonstrations** to facilitate the adoption and integration of Smart Droplets technologies into existing agricultural practices.

The Smart Droplets dissemination strategy ensures a wide reach and enduring impact, working towards transformative changes in the agricultural landscape.

3.1. Dissemination KPIs

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target
D1	Co-organization of events	
D1.1	Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid)	10
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	6
D1.3	"Spotlight on..."Live & On-Demand webinars	6
D1.4	Smart Droplets Solution Showcase and final event	1
D1.5	50 hours of physical and online training content	50
D2	Scientific and technical outreach	
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	5
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	5
D2.3	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	12
D2.4	Competition events (hackathons)	2
D3	Networking and synergies and liaison activities	
D3.1	Representation in WGs	3
D3.2	Representation in alliances	5
D3.3	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	10
D4	Policy measures and standardization efforts	
D4.1	Sets of standardization recommendations	2
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	5
D5	Ecosystem building	
D5.1	MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups	20
D5.2	MoUs/ Lols signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up	5
D5.3	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI	5

Figure 21: Dissemination KPIs

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	M1 - M12	M13 - M24	M25 - M42
D1	Co-organization of events				
D1.1	Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid)	10	1	3	6
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	6	-	0	6
D1.3	"Spotlight on..."Live & On-Demand webinars	6	1	2	3
D1.4	Smart Droplets Solution Showcase and final event	1			1
D1.5	50 hours of physical and online training content	50	-	25	25
D2	Scientific and technical outreach				
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	5	-	2	3
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	5	-	2	3
D2.3	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	12	-	-	12
D2.4	Competition events (hackathons)	2	-	0	2
D3	Networking and synergies and liaison activities				
D3.1	Representation in WGs	3	-	2	1
D3.2	Representation in alliances	5	-	3	2
D3.3	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	10	-	5	5
D4	Policy measures and standardization efforts				
D4.1	Sets of standardization recommendations	2	-	0	2
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	5	-	2	3
D5	Ecosystem building				
D5.1	MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups	20	-	10	10
D5.2	MoUs/ Lols signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up	5	-	2	3
D5.3	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI	5	-	4	1

Figure 22: Dissemination KPIs per reporting period

#	PMs	Target	AUA	WU	EUT	VLF	RFF	AGC	AFL	AGROMA SA	FEMAC
D1	Co-organization of events		12	8	4	3	52	45	9	5	4
D1.1	Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid)	10	2	2			2	1	2	1	
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	6			3				3		
D1.3	"Spotlight on..."Live & On-Demand webinars	6	2	2			2				
D1.4	Smart Droplets Solution Showcase and final event	1					1				
D1.5	50 hours of physical and online training content	50	20	15	15						
D2	Scientific and technical outreach										
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	5	2	2	1						
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	5	1	1	2	1					
D2.3	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	12					12				
D2.4	Competition events (hackathons)	2									
D3	Networking and synergies and liaison activities										
D3.1	Representation in WGs	3						1	1		1
D3.2	Representation in alliances	5	1	1	1		1		1		
D3.3	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	10	5	2			2		1		
D4	Policy measures and standardization efforts										
D4.1	Sets of standardization recommendations	2					2				
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	5	1	1	1				1		1
D5	Ecosystem building										
D5.1	MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups/projects	20	4		2	2	4	2	2	2	2
D5.2	MoUs/ Lols signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up	5	1				1	1	1	1	
D5.3	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI	5	1			2			2		

Figure 23: Dissemination KPIs per partner

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	M1 - M12	Achieved M1-M12	M13 - M24	Achieved M13-M24	M25 - M42	Achieved	Planned Goal
D1.1	Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid)	10	1	2	3	2	6	4	Achieved
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	6	-	-	0	0	2	0	Achieved
D1.3	*Spotlight on... *Live & On-Demand webinars	6	1	1	2	7	3	8	Achieved
D1.4	Smart Droplets Solution Showcase and final event	1	-	-	-	-	1	0	Achieved
D1.5	50 hours of physical and online training content	50	-	9	25	21	25	30	Achieved
D2 Scientific and technical outreach									
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	5	-	2	2	1	3	3	Achieved
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	5	-	-	2	2	3	2	Achieved
D2.3	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	12	-	-	-	-	12	0	Achieved
D2.4	Competition events (hackathons)	2	-	-	0	0	2	0	Achieved
D3 Networking and synergies and liaison activities									
D3.1	Representation in W/Gs	3	-	-	2	4	1	4	Achieved
D3.2	Representation in alliances	5	-	2	3	2	2	4	Achieved
D3.3	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	10	-	2	5	3	5	5	Achieved
D4 Policy measures and standardization efforts									
D4.1	Sets of standardization recommendations	2	-	0	0	0	2	0	Achieved
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	5	-	0	2	2	3	2	Achieved
D5 Ecosystem building									
D5.1	MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups	20	-	0	10	10	10	10	Achieved
D5.2	MoUs/ Lols signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up	5	-	0	2	6	3	6	Achieved
D5.3	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI	5	-	0	4	4	1	4	Achieved

Figure 24: Achieved Dissemination KPIs

Action Points – KPIs that have been achieved and exceeded

As we conclude the second reporting period, the Smart Droplets project has made significant strides in meeting and exceeding its KPI targets. Deliverables such as brochures, project factsheets, and posters have been successfully completed, from the previous reporting period, contributing to our outreach and dissemination objectives. Live and on demand webinars, representation in working groups and alliances, collaboration with EU initiatives, signed MoUs with investors have all surpassed initial expectations. These accomplishments reflect our strategic commitment to expanding the project's impact and visibility. Three KPIs – Open Days, Competitive Events, and Sets of standardization recommendations – had their scheduling updated and they were transferred to the third reporting period, based mainly on the progress of the project's pilots. The following table presents a short rundown of each dissemination KPI's status, while more comprehensive updates for each KPI can be found in the following sub-chapters.

- D1.1 Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid):** Smart Droplets actively engaged in key market and industry events co-organized by consortium partners, enhancing visibility and collaboration within the agrifood sector. The Smart Droplets partners organised or co-organised 4 market & industry events. Additionally, Smart Droplets participated in another 10 market and industry events, further broadening our engagement and impact within the sector.
- D1.2 Opens Days (3 showcase events per demo) (Updated Target):** The project's pilots, both the wheat field and the apple orchard, were delayed due to the shortage of components for the Direct Injection Spraying system and delays in the integration of the autonomous modules to the retrofit tractor. This led to the decision to move the Open Day events, compared to the initial distribution per reporting period, to the 3rd reporting period, to ensure they are more impactful in disseminating the project's results.
- D1.3 "Spotlight on..." Live & On-Demand webinars:** Smart Droplets hosted eight impactful webinars to enhance collaboration and knowledge sharing, a data management workshop by VLF, and seven specialized data webinars in the context of the Smart Droplets Academy, have been crucial in promoting the successful integration and sustainability of the Smart Droplets platform.
- D1.5 50 hours of physical and online training content:** Overall 30 hours of physical and online training were completed surpassing the target that was set for this reporting period.
- D2.1 Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions:** Smart Droplets has exceeded its target for the second reporting period. WUR contributed significantly by presenting two posters and publishing a peer-reviewed article, bringing the total number of academic outputs to three

- **D2.2 Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI Magazines/publications:** EUT and VLF created one tech brief each showcasing their technological advancements within Smart Droplets, successfully meeting the target for this reporting period.
- **D2.4 Competition events (hackathons) (Updated Target):** The first Smart Droplets hackathon was moved to the third reporting period and will be held online this fall, aiming to foster innovation and collaboration in the agricultural technology sector. This timing aligns with the academic calendar, facilitating participation from students and researchers. Additionally, it fits within the project's timeline, providing an opportunity to showcase progress and gather valuable feedback from the community.
- **D3.1 Representation in WGs:** Smart Droplets has actively participated in four working groups, surpassing the target set for this period. These engagements have included presentations of the project's data management platform, discussions on innovative methodologies, and focused sessions on precision spraying applications, bringing together key stakeholders and experts to drive advancements in agricultural practices.
- **D3.2 Representation in alliances:** Smart Droplets exceeded its target by being represented in four alliances through its active participation to relevant events.
- **D3.3 Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects:** Smart Droplets has met its KPI target of five joint activities with EU projects and initiatives, through joint workshops and joint participation in physical events.
- **D4.1 Sets of standardization recommendations (Updated Target):** The rescheduling of both sets of standardization recommendations to the end of the third reporting period is primarily due to delays in the Smart Droplets pilots. This strategic adjustment is anticipated to significantly improve the quality and holistic approach of the recommendations, by incorporating more complete data and insights from both the apple orchard and wheat field pilots. By consolidating feedback from both pilots, the project ensures that the recommendations are well-informed and address a broader range of real-world scenarios, and are at a higher maturity level allowing the consortium to approach regulatory and policy stakeholders.
- **D4.2 Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements:** One joint statement was issued on the project's social media accounts and another through the project's 6th Press Release, successfully reaching the goal set for this reporting period.
- **D5.1 MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups:** Ten Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) and Letters of Interest (Lols) have been signed between Smart Droplets and various relevant groups and initiatives. These agreements reflect a strong collaborative effort to enhance the project's impact and reach within the agricultural and technological sectors.
- **D5.2 MoUs/ Lols signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up:** Six Letters of Interest (Lols) have been signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up of Smart Droplets' innovations exceeding the goal that was set for this reporting period.
- **D5.3 Connections established with DIHs connected to AI:** During its second reporting period, Smart Droplets connected meaningfully with four Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs): HSBooster, ADRA-e, AI-on-Demand and Smart Agro Hub.

3.2. Dissemination Measures and Tools

3.2.1. Market & Industry Events

Smart Droplets showcased its innovative approaches in sustainable agriculture at the **Inno Panorama 2022** exhibition, held from September 22-24, 2022, at Vytautas Magnus University's Agriculture Academy. This event, focused on sustainability, ecology, and the European Green Deal, provided an excellent platform for the project to demonstrate its advanced technologies for efficient water and nutrient management. The exhibition facilitated the exchange of cutting-edge solutions, strengthened science-business partnerships, and inspired new strategies for sustainable agricultural development.

<https://zua.vdu.lt/renginiai/paroda-inno-panorama-2022-paroda-konferencija-ekolink/>

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Figure 25 Smart Droplets at AFL's booth at Inno Panorama 2022

Smart Droplets participated in the **AgriFood Forum 2022**, held on December 29, 2022, both online and on-site, organized by AgriFood Lithuania DIH and other key partners. This major event focused on addressing the multifaceted challenges in the agrifood sector, emphasizing digital transformation and innovation. By showcasing their advanced agricultural technology solutions, Smart Droplets engaged with a wide range of stakeholders, including industry leaders, policymakers, and researchers, to discuss sustainable practices and technological advancements.

<https://www.digitalfarm.lt/>

Figure 26 Smart Droplets at the AgriFood Forum 2022

Smart Droplets participated in the International **Startup Village Networking Event** on February 7, 2023, both online and on-site in Vilnius, organized by AgriFood Lithuania. This event brought together science, business, startups, and policymakers to discuss innovative and resilient regional development. By participating, Smart Droplets engaged with key players in the agrifood sector, enhanced their visibility, explored new funding opportunities, and contributed to discussions on the long-term development of rural areas.

<https://www.eitfood.eu/events/international-startup-village-networking-event-online-on-site-in-vilnius>

Figure 27 Smart Droplets featured in the Startup Village Networking Event

On March 23, 2023, Smart Droplets was featured at the **Open Day on Technological Infrastructures** for the Digitalization of the Agricultural Sector, organized by Eurecat. During this event, a presentation highlighted the integration of digital twin technology in smart spraying machines, demonstrating how it enhances precision agriculture and promotes sustainability. The event, which included various stakeholders from the agricultural sector, provided a platform for showcasing innovative digital solutions and discussing their real-world applications in improving agricultural practices.

<https://eurecat.org/en/services/eurecatevents/open-day-technological-infrastructures-digitalization-agricultural-sector/>

On September 29, 2023, Smart Droplets had the pleasure of attending **ROSCon Madrid 2023**, an event that was co-organized by EUT. The event featured many interesting talks by the Spanish ROS community. Eurecat presented the challenges faced in agricultural robotics and the solutions developed within the frameworks of the Robs4Crops, SCORPION EU Project, and Smart Droplets projects. The discussions highlighted innovative approaches and technological advancements aimed at addressing key issues in agricultural robotics. We look forward to future editions of this fantastic event.

<https://roscon.ros.org/>

Figure 28 EUT presenting Smart Droplets at ROSCon Madrid 2023

Smart Droplets participated in the **Synergy Days** event, organized by Smart Agrihubs, held on October 4 & 5, 2023, in Thessaloniki, Greece. This event provided an excellent opportunity for Smart Droplets to engage with

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various stakeholders in the agrifood sector and showcase our innovative solutions aimed at sustainable farming. Our booth attracted a diverse audience interested in our autonomous robotic technology, innovative spraying techniques, digital twin, and AI models. The discussions were insightful, and the feedback received was invaluable, furthering our mission to reduce pesticide and fertilizer use in alignment with the EU Green Deal's sustainability goals.

<https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/latest-events/synergy-days-2023>

Figure 29 The Smart Droplets Booth at the Synergy Days event

AGROMA SA and AGC represented the Smart Droplets project at **Agritechnica 2023**, held from November 12 to 18 in Hannover, Germany. Known as the world's leading trade fair for agricultural machinery, Agritechnica provided an ideal platform for showcasing Smart Droplets' advancements in agricultural automation and machinery, emphasizing sustainable farming practices through AI and robotic technologies. The event's focus on "Green Productivity" resonated with Smart Droplets' mission to enhance efficiency and sustainability in agriculture. Participation allowed Smart Droplets to engage with a global audience, industry leaders, and potential partners, reinforcing its position at the forefront of agricultural innovation.

<https://www.agritechnica.com/en/programme/news/smart-farming-at-agritechnica-2023>

Figure 30 AGROMA SA's booth at Agritechnica 2023 featuring Smart Droplets

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Smart Droplets participated in **SITEVI 2023**, held from November 28 to 30, 2023, an international exhibition for the vine, wine, fruit, and olive-growing sectors. At the event, Smart Droplets showcased its innovative digital twin technology for smart spraying machines, emphasizing their role in optimizing pesticide and fertilizer use to enhance precision agriculture and promote sustainability. This participation provided a valuable opportunity for networking, collaboration, and sharing advancements with industry professionals and stakeholders.

<https://www.sitevi.com/>

On November 23, 2023, our partner VizLore LLC attended the **Data Science Conference 2023** in Belgrade, Serbia. Mihailo Ilic, representing VLF, presented the Smart Droplets Project, focusing on “Scalable and Interoperable Data Flow Management for Digital Twin Frameworks in Smart Farming.” His presentation provided valuable insights into developing a sustainable farming model, highlighting the project's role in advancing digital twin technology in agriculture. This event underscored the importance of scalable and interoperable data management in creating efficient and sustainable agricultural practices.

<https://datasciconference.com/>

Figure 31 Mihailo presenting Smart Droplets at the Data Science Conference 2023

In early February (1-4) 2024, **AGROMA SA**, an active partner of the Smart Droplets project, attended the "Agrotica 2024 Expo" in Thessaloniki, Greece. Recognized as a significant event for the agricultural sector in Southeast Europe, Agrotica 2024 provided an excellent platform for showcasing the latest advancements in agriculture. At AGROMA's booth, the Smart Droplets poster prominently stood out, attracting considerable attention and highlighting the project's innovative contributions to sustainable farming practices.

<https://www.agrotica-expo.gr/en/>

Figure 32 AGROMA SA's booth at the Agrotica 2024 Expo

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On March 12, 2024, at the **European Robotics Forum**, Carlos Rizzo from Eurecat - Technology Centre presented the Smart Droplets project's advancements in robotics for sustainable agriculture. His presentation emphasized the transformative impact of digital twins and autonomous navigation on pesticide use, highlighting how these technologies optimize pesticide application, reduce environmental impact, and contribute to more efficient and eco-friendly farming practices. This event underscored the significant role of Smart Droplets in promoting sustainable agricultural innovations.

<https://erf2024.eu/>

Figure 33 Presentation of Smart Droplets by EUT at the European Robotics Forum 2024

Smart Droplets participated in the inaugural **Automation & Robotic EXPO** held in Athens, Greece, from April 12 to 14, 2024, represented by AUA and RFF. This event provided a platform for us to showcase our solutions in agricultural automation and robotics. Attendees explored advancements in the field, engaged with our technologies, and interacted with our team. The expo featured educational seminars, day conferences, and workshops hosted by exhibitors, supporters, and associations, offering insights into the latest trends and developments in robotics. We were pleased to connect with visitors, share our vision, and demonstrate how Smart Droplets is contributing to sustainable agriculture through AI and robotic technologies.

<https://ar-expo.gr/en/homepage/>

Figure 34 Smart Droplets at the 1st Automation & Robotic EXPO

3.2.2. Open Days

The Open Days events will serve as key opportunities to showcase the innovations and achievements of the Smart Droplets project. These events will provide hands-on demonstrations of our cutting-edge technologies in real-world agricultural settings, allowing stakeholders, including farmers, technologists, and policymakers, to witness firsthand the benefits and applications of our solutions. The Open Days will feature interactive sessions, live demonstrations, and opportunities for attendees to engage directly with the project team, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation of the project's impact.

The decision to move the Open Days to the third reporting period was driven by the need to ensure that our pilots were fully functional and ready for demonstration. This adjustment allows us to present a more polished and complete showcase of our work, incorporating the latest advances and feedback from earlier phases of the

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project, and allowing each standardisation recommendation to focus on the specifics of each pilot. By rescheduling, we aim to maximize the impact and effectiveness of these events, ensuring that all attendees can experience the full potential of the Smart Droplets innovations, and that potentially interested stakeholders, investors and industry groups see the full potential of the Smart Droplets solution.

3.2.3. Live & On-Demand Webinars

Smart Droplets has already exceeded the originally set target of six webinars, organized or co-organized by project partners. These webinars cover topics relevant to the project's and partners' areas of expertise. They are and will be both live and on-demand, allowing for flexible access to the content. The webinars aim to share knowledge, discuss advancements, and engage with stakeholders in fields aligned with the Smart Droplets initiative.

A comprehensive workshop focused on **data management** within the Smart Droplets project, addressing key topics such as specifications, integration strategies, the NGSI framework, and selected data models/ontologies. This workshop facilitated collaboration and knowledge exchange among partners, driving progress in integrating the Smart Droplets platform with field systems. Participants gained insights into effective data management practices, essential for enhancing the efficiency and functionality of the Smart Droplets platform. The webinar was attended live by the consortium members, and it is available to them on-demand.

Figure 35 The Data Management workshop by VLF

The Smart Droplets Academy, led by the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA), hosted seven webinars on various machine learning and computer vision techniques relevant to agriculture. Topics included image classification techniques, the use of transformers for weed identification, transfer learning for small datasets, object detection using Faster R-CNN and YOLO, and advanced computer vision techniques. The full list of webinars appears in Table 6.

Webinar Title	Date
Introduction to Machine Learning	9/12/2023
Image Classification: From Fully Connected Networks to CNNs. A Weed Detection Approach.	10/10/2023
Image Classification: From CNNs to Transformers. A use case for Weed Identification.	11/13/2023
Transfer Learning for small datasets in Weed Identification	12/11/2023
Object Detection (Faster R-CNN and YOLO)	1/15/2023
Annotations Strategies and Techniques/Intro to Object Detection	2/12/2023

Improving Performance: Advanced Computer Vision Techniques	3/11/2023
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Table 6 Smart Droplets Academy Webinars

Figure 36 Introduction to Machine Learning Webinar

Figure 37 Image Classification: From CNNs to Transformers. A use case for weed identification webinar

3.2.4. Smart Droplets Academy

The Smart Droplets Academy has successfully completed 30 hours of training, with 15 hours conducted by AUA and 15 hours by WU. The recordings of these training sessions are being uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel and are accessible through the project website’s knowledge base along with additional information for future reference and accessibility. More information about the Smart Droplets Academy seminars can be found through the respective Smart Droplets Academy – Program, Timeline & Activities reports.

3.2.5. Peer-reviewed papers & conference contributions

Smart Droplets will strive to publish at least 5 peer-reviewed papers & conference contributions in respected and highly rated journals and scientific magazines. Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project’s results to the research community and providing scientific credibility for the project’s work. This task will be undertaken mostly by the university and research partners and publications will cover several fields of the work performed within the Smart Droplets project, including but not limited to the results of the two pilots, the testing and success of the developed technologies.

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During the reporting period, our partner, WUR, has demonstrated noteworthy contributions. At the AgMIP9 event held at Columbia University in New York, NY, USA, on June 26, 2023, WUR presented a poster titled "Optimizing Nitrogen Management in Winter Wheat: A Reinforcement Learning Approach with Crop Growth Models." This insightful contribution highlights our dedication to refining nitrogen management practices through innovative reinforcement learning methods.

Figure 38 Poster titled "Optimizing Nitrogen Management in Winter Wheat: A Reinforcement Learning Approach with Crop Growth Models."

Moreover, another impactful poster presentation titled "Integrating Process-Based Models and Machine Learning for Crop Yield Prediction" was showcased at the International Conference on Machine Learning held in New York on July 23. These presentations signify our ongoing commitment to advancing the field of precision agriculture and sharing our discoveries with the broader scientific community.

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.13466>

Figure 39 Poster titled "Integrating Process-Based Models and Machine Learning for Crop Yield Prediction."

The article "Nitrogen Management with Reinforcement Learning and Crop Growth Models" authored by the team at WU contributes to the dissemination efforts of the Smart Droplets project. This paper explores the integration of reinforcement learning algorithms with crop growth models to optimize nitrogen application, enhancing both crop yields and sustainability. By leveraging advanced data science techniques, the authors present a novel approach to precision agriculture, aligning with Smart Droplets' objectives to promote sustainable farming practices through technological innovation.

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/environmental-data-science/article/nitrogen-management-with-reinforcement-learning-and-crop-growth-models/358749FAFAA4990B1448DAB7F48D641C>

Nitrogen management with reinforcement learning and crop growth models

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Keywords: Crop growth models; nitrogen; reinforcement learning; smart farming; winter wheat

Figure 40 WU's paper titled "Nitrogen management with reinforcement learning and crop growth models"

Smart Droplets partners are periodically asked to identify a list of journals that might be potentially interesting for future peer-reviewed publications. The most recent list is shown in Table 7.

#	Journal Title	Journal Website	Field of Research	Partner
1	Computer and Electronics in Agriculture	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/computers-and-electronics-in-agriculture/about/call-for-papers#advanced-technologies-for-precision-nutrient-management	AI in agriculture	WU
2	Environmental Datascience	https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/environmental-data-science	Data science in environmental sciences	WU

Table 7 Identified Journals for Publication

3.2.6. Tech Briefs

Smart Droplets will produce 5 tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications. The goal is to develop short summaries that describe the main information/recommendation/practice regarding the deployment of deep-tech in agriculture that can be used by the end-users in order to enhance the sustainability performance and competitiveness of the agricultural sector.

EUT has published a tech brief on Medium, aiming to showcase their cutting-edge methodology for autonomous navigation in agricultural environments. This publication highlights EUT's commitment to advancing agricultural technology and seeks to increase the visibility and impact of their research. By sharing this innovative approach publicly, EUT hopes to engage a broader audience, including agricultural professionals and technology enthusiasts, and to spark discussions around the future of autonomous farming solutions. The tech brief is part of a broader dissemination strategy to promote EUT's contributions to the field and to drive interest in sustainable agricultural practices.

Figure 41 EUT's Tech Brief on the autonomous navigation technology that has been developed in Smart Droplets

A tech brief by VLF focuses on the interoperability of technologies used within the Smart Droplets project. This brief will discuss the integration strategies that ensure seamless communication and data exchange between various systems and tools employed in the project. Highlighting the challenges and solutions in achieving interoperability, the brief will cover the implementation of standardized protocols and frameworks that facilitate the cohesive functioning of diverse technological components. This effort aims to optimize the overall performance and efficiency of the Smart Droplets platform, promoting better user experiences and more effective agricultural practices.

Figure 42 VLF's Tech Brief on data management and interoperability

3.2.7. Competition events

The first Smart Droplets hackathon, to be held online this coming fall, will serve as a catalyst for innovation and collaboration in the agricultural technology sector. The decision to host the event in the fall aligns with several strategic considerations:

1. The fall timing coincides with the academic calendar, facilitating the **participation of students and researchers** who can bring fresh perspectives and innovative ideas to the hackathon.
2. The fall season often marks a period of reflection and planning for the agricultural industry, making it an opportune time to engage with stakeholders and foster collaboration between academia, industry, and technology providers.
3. Hosting the hackathon in the fall aligns with the project's timeline, providing an opportunity to **showcase the progress** made in developing the Smart Droplets solution and gather valuable feedback from the wider community.

3.2.8. Representation in Working Groups

Smart Droplets has set the goal of participating in 4 working groups dedicated to project-specific topics. Engaging in these working groups is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, it provides an opportunity to influence policy-making, ensuring that the regulations and standards developed are aligned with the innovative approaches and technologies of the Smart Droplets project. Secondly, participation in these groups allows us to share our findings and insights, contributing to the broader scientific and technological discourse. Lastly, it fosters collaboration and networking with other experts and stakeholders, enhancing the impact and reach of our project. By being active in these working groups, Smart Droplets aims to shape the future of agricultural technology and promote sustainable practices across the sector.

Our partner VLF, on the 26th of May 2023, presented Smart Droplets project and its data management platform in the Agrifood Working Group of AIOTI.

On October 12, 2023, AFL, representing Smart Droplets, participated and was presented at the working group convened as part of the "System for Remote Analysis of Organic Matter in Soil (NOMEDA)." project. The event brought together EIP project partners and key stakeholders to discuss and present the NOMEDA project's innovative methodologies for soil analysis. The working group facilitated in-depth discussions, collaborative exchanges, and a Q&A session, ensuring active participation and knowledge sharing among the attendees.

Figure 43 AFL presenting Smart Droplets at the NOMEDA working group

On April 4, 2024 Kalliopi Kounani, Project Manager of Smart Droplets, hosted a working group focused on spraying applications. The event was attended by 40 participants, including representatives from the Hellenic Crop Protection Association, Pegasus Hellenic Cooperative, academia, and ELGO Demeter. The working group discussed the latest advancements in spraying technologies, with a focus on practical applications in agriculture. The participants shared their experiences and insights, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the current state and future prospects of spraying applications.

On May 12, 2024 Kalliopi Kounani organized the second working group on precision spraying applications, highlighting the progress of the Smart Droplets Project. This session included 17 participants and featured presentations from seven HE Projects. The presentations covered recent developments in precision spraying technologies and their implementation. The working group facilitated a technical exchange of knowledge and methodologies, aiming to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of spraying applications in agricultural practices. The insights gained from this session are expected to drive further advancements in the field.

Figure 44 AUA's participation in the precision spraying application Working Group

3.2.9. Representation in Alliances

From February 27 to March 1, 2023, Prof. Spyros Fountas from the Agricultural University of Athens presented the Smart Droplets project at the **14th Dahlia Greidinger International Symposium** in Israel. The symposium, attended by over 160 participants, focused on fertilization and fertilizers, providing a platform for international collaboration and knowledge exchange. The presentation of Smart Droplets' goals and objectives emphasized its impact on digital agriculture, big data, and deep tech solutions for sustainable farming, reflecting the project's integration into a broader network of global agricultural research and innovation.

Figure 45 Professor Spyros Fountas, Smart Droplet's coordinator, presenting the project at the 14th Dahlia Greidinger International Symposium

Smart Droplets actively participated in the **"Unlocking the Power of Robotics in Agri-Food"** event hosted by the agROBOfood project on 11 and 12 May, 2023. Held at the Agricultural University of Athens, the event featured a session on "Mapping Innovations Across the EU," where coordinators and WP leaders from multiple projects presented their innovations and discussed community engagement and implementation challenges in agricultural robotics. This gathering underscored the transformative potential of collaborative efforts and highlighted the critical role of alliances in advancing agricultural technology through shared knowledge and coordinated action.

<https://old.agrobofood.eu/unlocking-the-power-of-robotics-in-agri-food/>

Figure 46 "Unlocking the power of robotics in Agri-Food" event by the agROBOfood project

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

On March 27, 2024, Smart Droplets participated in the inaugural **Oper-8 Cooperation Meeting**, a virtual gathering aimed at fostering collaboration among six pioneering projects in the agri-food sector. The meeting facilitated discussions on various topics related to innovation and collaboration, establishing a foundation for future cooperative efforts and knowledge exchange. This event highlighted the importance of structured partnerships and collective progress, bringing together key stakeholders to drive innovation and address common challenges in the agri-food industry.

Figure 47 Oper-8 Cooperation Meeting

On May 18th 2024, Cluster FEMAC and EURECAT Lleida hosted a delegation from the Wuxi New District Industry and Information Technology Bureau, marking a significant step in fostering international collaboration and technological exchange. The delegation toured the facilities and engaged in insightful discussions with experts, with a key highlight being a presentation by Xavier Domingo i Albin, head of the Applied Artificial Intelligence Unit. He showcased various projects, including the H2020 Project Smart Droplets led by the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA), which focuses on developing a digital twin for a smart spraying machine. The delegation expressed keen interest in the Smart Droplets project, recognizing its potential to enhance precision agriculture and promote sustainability globally. The visit concluded with a fruitful exchange of ideas and potential avenues for future collaboration.

Figure 48 EUT presenting Smart Droplets to the delegation from the Wuxi New District Industry and Information Technology Bureau

3.2.10. Joint activities with EU initiatives and projects

In March 2023, Wageningen University & Research (WUR) organized a workshop in **collaboration with the H2020 Optima project**. This dynamic session facilitated discussions on shared objectives and synergies between the two projects, laying the groundwork for productive collaboration. The workshop highlighted the common goals and innovative approaches of both projects, fostering an environment of mutual learning and potential joint efforts.

In May 2023, VLF further contributed to the dissemination efforts by presenting the Smart Droplets project at the **Crack Sense project event**. This presentation not only highlighted the potential and progress of Smart Droplets but also explored avenues for future collaboration. The event provided a platform for networking and exchanging ideas, enhancing the visibility and impact of the Smart Droplets project within the broader scientific and technological community.

On November 29th, 2023, Wageningen University & Research hosted 36 PhDs and postdocs from the **Cluster of Excellence "PhenoRob"** for a workshop on sensing, vision, and robotics. Among the many projects presented, Smart Droplets stood out thanks to an insightful presentation by Michiel Kallenberg, a PhD researcher at WUR. His presentation focused on the decision support AI engine for nitrogen management in the fields, utilizing reinforcement learning. This event marked another significant step towards resilient and sustainable agriculture.

Figure 49 Presenting Smart Droplets at the PhenoRob workshop

At the inaugural **Automation & Robotic EXPO** held in Athens, Greece, from April 12 to 14, 2024, Smart Droplets shared a booth with the ICAERUS project. This joint presentation showcased our complementary technologies and innovations in agricultural automation and robotics. The collaboration highlighted our shared commitment to advancing sustainable agriculture through AI and robotic technologies. Visitors to the booth had the opportunity to learn about both projects, explore synergies, and discuss potential collaborative efforts. This event was a valuable opportunity to demonstrate how Smart Droplets and ICAERUS are contributing to sustainable agriculture and to foster ongoing conversations and collaborations.

Figure 50 Smart Droplets' and ICAERUS' booth at the Automation & Robotic EXPO

On June 4, 2024, **AgriBITH2020**, in collaboration with Wikifarmer, hosted a webinar featuring new technologies from six top EU-funded research projects. Kalliopi Kounani from AUA presented the Smart Droplets project, detailing its holistic approach to crop spraying and its potential to transition agriculture towards more sustainable practices. The webinar facilitated a productive exchange of innovative ideas among participants.

Figure 51 Participation in the Agtech Innovations webinar

Figure 52 Presentation of Smart Droplets at the webinar

3.2.11. Sets of standardization recommendations

The uptake of agricultural innovations is in need for the bottom-up approaches of feedback and recommendation integration in order to design the needed policy measures. In that sense Smart Droplets will produce **2** sets of standardization recommendations from findings developed and tested during the project in order to enable an understating and positive impact of deep tech in agricultural environments while targeting policy personnel and experts.

Due to delays in the pilot studies, both sets of standardization recommendations have been rescheduled to the end of the third reporting period. This strategic adjustment is expected to significantly enhance the quality and comprehensiveness of the recommendations, as it will allow for the incorporation of robust data and insights from both the apple orchard and wheat field pilots. By consolidating the feedback from both pilots, the project can ensure that the recommendations are well-informed and address a broader range of real-world scenarios.

To facilitate a structured and efficient process for developing these recommendations, a standardized template will be utilized to gather feedback from all relevant partners. This template will systematically document the entire pilot procedure, capturing crucial details such as:

- Experimental setup and methodology
- Data collection and analysis protocols
- Key findings and observations
- Lessons learned and potential areas for improvement

By employing this structured approach, the project can streamline the collection and analysis of feedback, ensuring that all pertinent information is considered in the formulation of the final standardization recommendations. This collaborative effort will not only enhance the quality of the recommendations but also foster a sense of ownership and commitment among the partners, ultimately contributing to the successful implementation and adoption of the proposed standards.

3.2.12. Joint press release/statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives and movements

During the project Smart Droplets consortium will create **5** joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & networks to further influence decision-making and development in agricultural value chains.

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

Smart Droplets and QuantiFarm recently announced a MoU to enhance collaboration on sustainable agriculture. The coordinators from both projects emphasized their shared commitment to advancing Digital Agriculture Technologies and precision agriculture. By leveraging AI and robotics, they aim to optimize resource use and reduce environmental impact, furthering their mutual goals of sustainability and competitiveness in the agricultural sector.

Figure 53 Common statement from the Smart Droplets and QuantiFarm coordinators

The Smart Droplets 6th Press Release, featuring a joint statement with the ICAERUS project, highlighted the importance of collaboration and innovation in sustainable agriculture. Both projects emphasised their commitment to using technologies such as artificial intelligence, robotics, and data analytics to reduce the environmental impact of farming. The PR included a message from the ICAERUS project manager, reinforcing the value of cross-project cooperation in addressing global challenges.

3.2.13. Memoranda of Understanding and Letters of Interest

The MoUs and Lols facilitate cooperation, knowledge exchange, and the integration of innovative solutions developed by Smart Droplets. They also ensure that the project's advancements in AI, data, and robotic technologies are effectively utilized and supported by key stakeholders, fostering a sustainable and scalable implementation of Smart Droplets' objectives.

Smart Droplets has successfully signed four Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) with various industry associations and groups, reinforcing our commitment to collaboration and innovation in the agrifood sector. Additionally, we have received six letters of interest from industry players and associations, highlighting their support for our initiatives. Furthermore, we have received six letters of interest from investors and other potential partners, which will be instrumental in fine-tuning our commercialization strategies and scaling up our operations. These partnerships and expressions of interest are crucial steps towards driving the successful implementation and expansion of our advanced agricultural technologies. The MoUs and Lols signed and the category they fall into are show in Table 8.

#	Type of document	Signed by/with	Category
1	MoU	Quantifarm Project	Associations & Groups
2	MoU	Icaerus Project	Associations & Groups
3	LoI	EdenCore Technologies	Associations & Groups
4	MoU	Farmtopia Project	Associations & Groups
5	MoU	4Growth Project	Associations & Groups
6	MoU	FS4Africa Project	Associations & Groups
7	LoI	Agrotehnik & Ko	Investor & Other potential partners
8	LoI	IPM ADVICE SL	Investor & Other potential partners

9	LoI	AMP SPRAYERS SL	Investor & Other potential partners
10	LoI	Aragonese Cluster of Agricultural and Livestock Means of Production	Associations & Groups
11	LoI	Talleres Corbins, SL	Investor & Other potential partners
12	LoI	solteka air technical solutions	Investor & Other potential partners
13	LoI	TEYME	Investor & Other potential partners
14	LoI	Smart Agro Hub	Associations & Groups
15	LoI	Hellenic Association of Agricultural Affairs (PSATH)	Associations & Groups
16	LoI	Farmer's Union	Associations & Groups

Table 8 MoUs and Lols signed during Smart Droplets

3.2.14. Connections with DIHs connected to AI

During its second reporting period Smart Droplets connected in a meaningful way with four(4) DIHs (Digital Innovation Hubs); HSBooster, ADRA-e, AI-on-demand and the Smart Farming Technology Group.

HSBooster is a 30-month EU initiative that supports Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, and Digital Europe projects in contributing to and creating standards. It provides expert services to integrate project results into standardisation processes, enhancing their impact.

By connecting research projects with Standards Developing Organisations (SDOs), HSBooster helps create efficient standards that drive technological innovation and support a resilient, green, and digital economy. It also upholds democratic values in technology.

HSBooster offers consultancy and guidance to help projects engage with standardisation groups and committees, ensuring their research outcomes have a lasting impact through standardisation.

Smart Droplets is listed in the HSbooster.eu Project Hub, showcasing its collaboration with HSBooster. This connection provides Smart Droplets with valuable access to expert guidance on standardisation, helping to integrate its research outcomes into official standards. This partnership supports Smart Droplets in enhancing its project results and market readiness.

Figure 54 Smart Droplets' page on the Hsbooster site

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

ADRA-e (AI, Data, and Robotics Ecosystem) is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project aimed at fostering a comprehensive European AI, Data, and Robotics ecosystem. Running from July 1st, 2022, to June 30th, 2025, ADRA-e promotes cross-border and cross-sector collaborations to enhance innovation and trust in these technologies. Key activities include facilitating multi-stakeholder dialogues, mapping the ADR landscape, stimulating collaboration to overcome technology roadblocks, and raising awareness about AI's trustworthiness. Additionally, ADRA-e supports the development of standards and regulations to ensure European technological sovereignty. The project collaborates with key initiatives and organizations like BDVA, CLAIRE, ELLIS, EurAI, EuRobotics, and AI4Europe to drive innovation and build a thriving AI, Data, and Robotics ecosystem in Europe (<https://adra-e.eu/>).

Figure 55 Smart Droplets' participation in an Adra-e event

Smart Droplets is actively connected to ADRA-e through its participation in key ADRA-e events. For instance, during the "Paving the Way Towards the Next Generation of R&I Excellence in AI, Data, and Robotics" event, Smart Droplets was featured as one of the projects contributing to the AI, Data, and Robotics agenda. This connection provides Smart Droplets with a platform to showcase its advancements and engage with other leading projects and stakeholders in the field. By being part of the ADRA-e ecosystem, Smart Droplets benefits from increased visibility, collaborative opportunities, and access to a network of experts and resources dedicated to advancing AI and robotics innovation in Europe (ADRA-E).

The **AI-on-Demand (AIoD)** platform is a community-driven initiative supporting European AI research and innovation. It offers an open, accessible digital platform for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and experimentation among AI researchers, developers, and stakeholders.

AIoD aims to create a thriving AI research ecosystem in Europe by providing high-quality datasets, algorithms, and tools. It fosters excellence, accelerates AI adoption, and supports upskilling and innovation, contributing to the European AI strategy for quality and trustworthiness.

Governed by a collaborative model aligned with European values, AIoD ensures fairness and sustainability. Success relies on active engagement from the European AI community, inviting contributions and participation to shape its future (<https://www.ai4europe.eu/>).

Smart Droplets is actively connected to the AI-on-Demand platform, benefiting from its resources and collaborative environment. By being featured on AIoD, Smart Droplets gains visibility and access to a broad network of AI professionals and resources. This connection supports the project's goals by providing a platform for sharing research outputs, engaging in collaborative efforts, and leveraging AIoD's extensive catalogue of AI assets and tools. This integration helps Smart Droplets in advancing its research and application in AI-driven agricultural innovations, aligning with the broader European objectives for AI development and deployment.

Figure 56 Smart Droplets' page on the AI-on-demand website

Lastly, Smart Droplets has established a meaningful connection with the Smart Agro Hub Digital Innovation Hub (DIH), resulting in a letter of intent expressing their enthusiasm for the project. This letter highlights the promising potential for future collaborations, underscoring the alignment of both initiatives in advancing smart agricultural technologies.

4. Communication Activities

Smart Droplets aims to increase public awareness of the project through a series of strategically planned actions that engage internal and external stakeholders, the media, and the general public. These actions will:

- Communicate the impacts and benefits of the project and its outcomes throughout its duration and beyond, using a variety of activities, tools, and channels.
- Tailor communication efforts for different countries, regions, and specific population subgroups.

The communication plan for Smart Droplets is vital for:

- Highlighting the potential of its innovative solutions to enhance agricultural practices and support sustainable farming,
- Promoting knowledge sharing and inclusivity,
- Engaging target groups and the broader public with solutions that address pressing social and environmental issues.

4.1. Communication KPIs

#	Communication KPIs	Target
C1	Full Branding & Web Design	
C1.1	Printable brand book	1
C1.2	Website	1
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6
C1.4	Posters	3
C1.5	Brochures	3
C1.6	Project factsheet	3
C1.7	Notebook	1
C1.8	Roll-up	1
C1.9	Folder	1
C1.10	Banner	1
C1.11	Stickers	1
C1.12	Virtual background	1
C1.13	Social Media template	1
C2	Digital & Social Media	
C2.1	Unique website pageviews	5000
C2.2	No. of views/ downloads	450
C2.3	Blog posts and Social media posts	250
C2.4	No. of Social media followers	1500
C2.5	No. of newsletter subscribers	500
C2.6	Newsletter (quarterly edition)	14
C2.7	Average click-to-open rate	20-30%
C3	Press Outreach & Event Planning	
C3.1	Press releases	10
C3.2	Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio, magazines, newspaper)	5
C3.3	Articles in agriculture and industry magazines	10
C3.4	2 Digital Ag 360° podcast learning series/seasons	14

Figure 57: Communication KPIs

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

#	Communication KPIs	Target	M1 - M12	M13 - M24	M25 - M42
C1	Full Branding & Web Design				
C1.1	Printable brand book	1	1		
C1.2	Website	1	1		
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6	6		
C1.4	Posters	3	3		
C1.5	Brochures	3	3		
C1.6	Project factsheet	3	3		
C1.7	Notebook	1	1		
C1.8	Roll-up	1	1		
C1.9	Folder	1	1		
C1.10	Banner	1	1		
C1.11	Stickers	1	1		
C1.12	Virtual background	1	1		
C1.13	Social Media template	1	1		
C2	Digital & Social Media				
C2.1	Unique website pageviews	5000	1000	3000	5000
C2.2	No. of views/ downloads	450	-	50	400
C2.3	Blog posts and Social media posts	250	50	100	100
C2.4	No. of Social media followers	1500	700	1200	1500
C2.5	No. of newsletter subscribers	500	100	300	500
C2.6	Newsletter (quarterly edition)	14	4	4	6
C2.7	Average click-to-open rate	20-30%		20-30%	
C3	Press Outreach & Event Planning				
C3.1	Press releases	10	2	4	4
C3.2	Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio, magazines,	5	1	2	2
C3.3	Articles in agriculture and industry magazines	10	1	4	5
C3.4	2 Digital Ag 360° podcast learning series/seasons	14	-	7	7

Figure 58: Communication KPIs per reporting period

#	Communication KPIs	Target	AUA	WU	EUT	VLF	RFF	AGC	AFL	AGROMA SA	FEMAC
C1	Full Branding & Web Design		12	8	4	3	52	4.5	9	5	4
C1.1	Printable brand book	1					1				
C1.2	Website	1					1				
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6					6				
C1.4	Posters	3					3				
C1.5	Brochures	3					3				
C1.6	Project factsheet	3					3				
C1.7	Notebook	1					1				
C1.8	Roll-up	1					1				
C1.9	Folder	1					1				
C1.10	Banner	1					1				
C1.11	Stickers	1					1				
C1.12	Virtual background	1					1				
C1.13	Social Media template	1					1				
C2	Digital & Social Media										
C2.1	Unique website pageviews	5000					5000				
C2.2	No. of views/ downloads	450					450				
C2.3	Blog posts and Social media posts	250	10	10	10	10	170	10	10	10	10
C2.4	No. of Social media followers	1500					1500				
C2.5	No. of newsletter subscribers	500					500				
C2.6	Newsletter (quarterly edition)	14					14				
C2.7	Average click-to-open rate	20-30%					20-30%				
C3	Press Outreach & Event Planning										
C3.1	Press releases published to the website	10					10				
C3.2	Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio, magazines, newspaper)	5	1		1		1		1		1
C3.3	Articles in agriculture and industry magazines	10	2	1		1	3		1		2
C3.4	2 Digital Ag 360° podcast learning series/seasons	14					14				

Figure 59: Communication KPIs per partner

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

#	Communication KPIs	Target	M1 - M12	Achieved M1-M12	M13 - M24	Achieved M13-M24	M25 - M42	Achieved	Planned Goal
C1	Full Branding & Web Design								
C1.1	Printable brand book	1	1	1				1	Achieved
C1.2	Website	1	1	1				1	Achieved
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6	6	6				6	Achieved
C1.4	Posters	3	3	3				3	Achieved
C1.5	Brochures	3	3	3				3	Achieved
C1.6	Project factsheet	3	3	3				3	Achieved
C1.7	Notebook	1	1	1				1	Achieved
C1.8	Roll-up	1	1	1				1	Achieved
C1.9	Folder	1	1	1				1	Achieved
C1.10	Banner	1	1	1				1	Achieved
C1.11	Stickers	1	1	1				1	Achieved
C1.12	Virtual background	1	1	1				1	Achieved
C1.13	Social Media template	1	1	1				1	Achieved
C2	Digital & Social Media								
C2.1	Unique website pageviews	5000	1000	1600	3000	2640	5000	4240	Achieved
C2.2	No. of views/ downloads	450	-	-	50	70	400	70	Achieved
C2.3	Blog posts and Social media posts	250	50	169	100	250	100	419	Achieved
C2.4	No. of Social media followers	1500	700	979	1200	556	1500	1535	Achieved
C2.5	No. of newsletter subscribers	500	100	101	300	200	500	301	Achieved
C2.6	Newsletter (quarterly edition)	14	4	3	4	5	6	8	Achieved
C2.7	Average click-to-open rate	20-30%			20-30%				Achieved
C3	Press Outreach & Event Planning								
C3.1	Press releases	10	2	1	4	5	4	6	Achieved
C3.2	Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio, magazines, newspaper)	5	1	1	2	3	2	4	Achieved
C3.3	Articles in agriculture and industry magazines	10	1	0	4	6	5	6	Achieved
C3.4	2 Digital Ag 360° podcast learning series/seasons	14	-	-	7	7	7	7	Achieved

Figure 60: Achieved Communication KPIs

Action Points – KPIs that have been achieved and exceeded

- **C1 Full Branding & Web Design:** RFF developed all the relevant material during the first 6 months and more specifically 1 Printable brand book, 1 Website, 6 Social Media accounts, 3 Posters, 3 Brochures, 3 Project factsheet, 1 Notebook, 1 Roll-up, 1 Folder, 1 Banner, 1 Stickers, 1 Virtual background, 1 social media template.
- **C2.1 Unique website pageviews:** The project's "unique website pageviews" KPI has been updated to track the "Sessions" metric, as the former has been removed from the latest version of the Google Analytics platform. This new metric is considered a more conservative and accurate measure of website engagement. We are pleased to report that our targets have been reached and exceeded, with more than 4,200 sessions recorded. This demonstrates strong and consistent interest in the Smart Droplets project.
- **C2.2 No. of views/downloads:** The project's promotional materials have garnered significant attention on the Smart Droplets website, with 70 views/downloads. This engagement reflects the strong interest in the project's initiatives and underscores the value of the information provided to stakeholders and the general public.
- **C2.3 Blog posts & social media posts:** All the Smart Droplets partners contributed in order to exceed this KPI, driving to the creation of engaging and interesting content which led to several re-tweets and re-posts from several interested parties.
- **C2.4 No. of Social media followers:** The development of high-quality content significantly boosted our social media presence, resulting in 1,535 followers—surpassing our initial target of 1,200 and exceeding the end-of-project goal. LinkedIn emerged as our primary platform with the highest number of followers, followed by X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, YouTube, and SlideShare.
- **C2.5 No. of newsletter subscribers:** Smart Droplets has successfully reached over 300 newsletter subscribers through targeted networking, dissemination, and communication activities.
- **C2.6 Newsletter (quarterly edition):** All eight newsletters for the Smart Droplets project have been published.
- **C2.7 Average click-to-open ratio:** The current average click-to-open ratio is 30%. Although the early issues of the project's newsletter had a lower ratio, targeted efforts and enhanced promotion have significantly boosted audience engagement in the most recent editions.
- **C3.1 Press releases:** Following the Smart Droplets inaugural Press Release there have been another five (5) press releases in the project's second reporting period. The Smart Droplets content that is expected to take place during the first months of the 3rd Reporting Period is expected to produce

multiple upcoming press releases, that will reach and overall exceed the project's overall press release target (Press Releases about the project's pilots, the hackathons etc.).

- **C3.2 Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio):** Smart Droplets was featured in four interviews and speeches across various media outlets, including TV shows, radio stations, newspapers, and agricultural schools.
- **C3.3 Articles in agriculture and industry magazines:** Smart Droplets has been featured in six articles in relative industry magazines – Agro.tech Magazine, Ypaithros Chora, Greek Farmer, AgroCapital, Mokslo Lietuva, and Inovacijos.lt – three by RFF, two by AFL, and one by AUA.

4.2. Communication Measures and Tools

4.2.1. Visual Identity

To target the broadest possible audience, Smart Droplets has created a strong, memorable brand that visually reflects the unique identity and objectives of the project. The visual identity guidelines are in line with the obligations of beneficiaries regarding information and communication and dissemination measures included in Article 17.2 — Visibility — European flag and funding statement and 17.3 Quality of information — Disclaimer of the Grant Agreement Nr.

Smart Droplets will exploit multiple digital platforms to share updates and results and to stimulate ongoing dialogue with stakeholders. Posts and other inputs will be curated to the target audiences at a frequency of once a week, to demonstrate consistency and accessibility.

The project's visual identity includes a logo, as well as relevant templates and guidelines for the partners on the rules of using the communication elements aimed at promoting the Smart Droplets project and properly acknowledging EU funding.

The visual identity is the visible representation of the project. A strong visual identity combines images, colours and shapes to create a powerful, memorable message to the viewer. Smart Droplets' visual identity was created considering the following:

- **Simplicity:** The selected visual identity must be able to tell the story of the project in a simple manner
- **Relevance:** An appropriate aesthetic that can be easily correlated with the project's objectives
- **Uniqueness:** The elements selected must lead to the design of a recognisable and unique visual identity
- **Versatility:** A logo that can be easily used in different communication channels (digital and printed)
- **Memorability:** Colours and design of the logo should make it easy to remember

4.2.1.1. Logo, colours and brandbook

Logo

The logo will be used in all internal and external communication and dissemination activities (project website, presentations, flyers, press releases, etc.) to help enhance brand continuity and raise awareness. 3 logo variations have been selected for different uses (Annex B). The Smart Droplets logo includes the name of the project as its main concept, with the usage of a clear and modern font, and icons representing digital technologies/innovations, that can be easily correlated with the agricultural sector. The most frequently used logo for the communication and dissemination material is shown in the figure below.

Figure 61: Smart Droplets most used logo

Colour Palette

The colour palette was selected to represent the project’s values: agriculture, technology, open communication, and courage. The colours are optimized for use on both screen (RGB) and print (CMYK) and the contrast is optimal for black and white printing.

Figure 62: Smart Droplets colours

To increase project’s recognition, extra graphics (covers), that accompany the Smart Droplet’s logo on the website and the social media accounts of the project, have been designed (Annex C) to create a maximum recognition value for our target audiences. This coherent visual communication makes Smart Droplets recognisable and easily differentiable in the social media domain.

Brand Book

The Smart Droplets brand book outlines the visual and communicative identity of the project, ensuring consistency across all materials. It includes guidelines for the logo, typography, imagery, and a specific colour palette for print and web, detailed in **Annex A**. This guide helps partners and stakeholders maintain a cohesive and professional representation of the Smart Droplets project.

Figure 63 The Smart Droplets Brand Book

4.2.1.2. EU Emblem

All Smart Droplets dissemination and communication material will acknowledge the requirements set out by the European Union and include the EU flag, the source of funding at the Grant agreement number 101070496.

Figure 64: EU recognition visual

The ready-to-use EU emblem including the funding statement can be downloaded in all EU languages.⁴

4.2.1.3. Disclaimer for publications

In addition to the EU Emblem, all dissemination and communication material must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Additionally, the following text is used for publications that involve research done in the project or relate to the project:

“Funding for this research has been provided by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme Smart Droplets (Grant Agreement Number 101070496).”

4.2.1.4. Templates

Smart Droplets will be presented in numerous events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results.

A **presentation template (ppt)** (Annex D) has been designed in line with the Smart Droplets graphic identity to maintain consistency, and professionalism and promote its recognition. The presentation template can be seen below.

The Smart Droplets **Deliverable Template (doc)** (Annex E) is also consistent with communication and dissemination material graphic identity and will be used by the consortium partners for the development of all

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

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project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project's logo in a prominent position, its name, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number, and title), as well as the writer's information.

An additional **text template (doc)** (Annex F) for written communication includes the logo and the EU emblem to maintain consistency with the project's visual identity.

A **Press Release** template (doc) has been created to communicate the project's latest news and for dissemination of the latest developments and scientific data. The PR has the logo of the project and maintains the brand identity of it by using the colours of the brand book. Press releases are sent to the media and are published on the project's website. The PR template can be found in Annex K.

4.2.1.5. Brochure

Brochures will be distributed at the project's events (regional and national workshops) to provide concise project information relevant to the target groups. Three 3-fold brochures have been created in total for this purpose, and each of these are available for distribution during the three different phases of the project. All the brochures have been uploaded in the common drive of the project, in order all the partners to be able to find them and translate them in their languages in case they organise or participate in national events. All 3 brochures can be found in the Annex G.

On 13 April 2024, Smart Droplets participated in the 1st Automation and Robotics Expo, held at the Metropolitan Expo in Athens. Smart Droplets was showcased in RFF's kiosk, along with two other projects, ICAERUS and Robs4Crops. During the exhibition, the Smart Droplets representative shared 60 brochures and communicated the project to those who visited RFF's kiosk.

Figure 65 Smart Droplets Brochure

4.2.1.6. Posters and Factsheets

For the Smart Droplets project, we have designed all three posters, each one representing a different case study. The 1st poster is showcasing the project's main expected impact and purposes. The 2nd poster is presenting Apple Orchard Pilot Facts, while the 3rd focuses on Wheat Farm Pilot Facts (Annex H). Additionally, a set of three informative factsheets has been developed, providing project at a glance (overall budget, Coordinator, Grant Agreement ID, start and end date of the project), as well as its objectives, challenges and its consortium (Annex I).

4.2.1.7. Banner

During the project, a banner was expected to be designed by RFF and printed for the partners that require it. The banners should be appealing to the eyes and in contrast with the brochure, they will provide the Smart Droplets community and stakeholders with updates and specific topics. Aligned with these design principles, four banners were developed and printed. Two banners that provide a general overview of the project and two banners for the two pilots, the apple orchard and the wheat field pilot. The four different banners can be seen below:

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Figure 66 Smart Droplets Banners

The four banners were displayed in the “Synergy Days” event in Thessaloniki on 4 and 5/10/2023.

On 12-14 April 2024, Smart Droplets participated in the 1st Automation and Robotics Expo, held at the Metropolitan Expo in Athens. Smart Droplets was showcased in RFF’s kiosk, along with two other projects, ICAERUS and Robs4Crops. Two banners (one “general overview” and one for the apple orchard pilot) were also displayed on 3 and 4 October 2024, at the 1st Automation and Robotics Expo in Athens, as it can be seen below:

Figure 67 Smart Droplets banners (first on the left and third in the middle) at the 1st Robotics and Automation Expo in Athens (12-14/04/24)

4.2.2. Website

The Smart Droplets website (<https://smartdroplets.eu/>) has already been developed and the landing page of the website was released on (M2). The project’s website serves the purpose of the primary communication and dissemination platform and enables target groups and Smart Droplets’ stakeholders access to the project development and results, and to see and assess the added-value and the impact of digital solutions in agriculture. The site was developed and officially released on M6 with all the partners contributing for its successful updating. The project website hosts all public dissemination deliverables, and promote relevant content (news, editorials, videos, events, etc.) for key stakeholder groups, thus engaging them in the content

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and objectives of the project. The website also hosts digital visualizations of project processes and results, to make them accessible to a wider audience. The addition of this content relies fully on the progress of the project and will thus be updated and expanded as the project evolves. **In the forthcoming months, we anticipate further enhancements to the website, aimed at integrating additional pertinent project-related information, such as live updates and features on the project of the Smart Droplets pilots.** Finally, the website is also mobile-friendly, increasing accessibility and maximizing the impact of the project.

The Smart Droplets website has a twofold role:

- it will serve as the principal reference point, explaining the project's aims, providing new updates, and documents for download, and enabling access to social media accounts of the project.
- it will act as a resource centre for research on topics related to digital agricultural technologies, providing important updates that have an impact.

Delivered in M3 and within the scope of this deliverable, the Smart Droplets website is hosted at <https://smartdroplets.eu> and contains the following sections and features.

Home/Landing page

Includes the project logo, image, project graphics, social media icons (LinkedIn, Facebook, X, SlideShare, YouTube, Instagram), a button for sign-up in the Smart Droplets newsletter and a navigation menu providing easy access to information on the project.

About us

This section of the website has quick facts about the project, the expected impact that is to be updated as the project evolves, and objectives.

Our partners

A list of consortium partners, accompanied by a short description of their role in the project, their expertise is provided in this section of the website.

Pilots

A short description of all the two pilots that will assess SFTs and spraying solutions under real conditions is explained. This part of the website is envisioned as a live and continuously growing section that is to be expanded once the project enters the pilot-driven months.

Figure 68 Smart Droplets website, landing page, about us, and partners section

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Resources

This section of the website will house all 'ready-to-print material including posters, brochures, project factsheets, notebook, folder, roll-ups, banners, stickers, and a printable brand book and guidelines. Additionally, this segment will house links to public project deliverables deposited on Zenodo as well as the Open Access publications that will be created during the project's lifespan, ensuring far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports, greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community and improve the likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse project's results rather than start ab initio, thereby helping in terms of reproductivity and continuity of research results.

Newsroom

Press releases and posts will be the main content presented here and will inform stakeholders of all project's activities and upcoming events.

Knowledge Base

The Smart Droplets Knowledge Base is an online resource hub offering on-demand educational materials through the Smart Droplets Academy. This initiative aims to provide training on advanced technologies relevant to agriculture, such as artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, precision agriculture, digital twins, and reinforcement learning. The Academy's webinars and workshops cater to a diverse audience, including students, farmers, researchers, and IT professionals, with instruction from experts at top universities and research institutions. The Knowledge Base includes course descriptions, video lectures, presentations, and code notebooks, empowering stakeholders in the agri-food sector to adopt new technologies and enhance agricultural practices.

Figure 69 Smart Droplets Pilots, Newsroom, Resources, and Knowledge Base tabs

Contact us

All the contact information of the Smart Droplets project will be available under this section enabling the easiest communication with our stakeholders through email (info@smartdroplets.eu).

The **Privacy Policy**, together with the **Terms and Conditions** have also been included in the Smart Droplets website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

Figure 70 Smart Droplets Contact Us, Cookies, and Privacy policy sections

As mentioned above, partners played a pivotal role in curating the website's content. RFF provided templates that served as a foundation, enabling partners to contribute pertinent information aligned with their expertise. By utilizing these templates, partners efficiently contributed to the site's content, ensuring uniformity and coherence across various sections. The templates that have been provided to the partners, depending on their role in the project, were the following:

Work Package description for the website	
WPx	
WP leader	
Duration	
Short description of the WPx	

Figure 71: Template for WPs description

Partner description for the website	
Full name of the partner	
Short name of the partner	
Country	
Webpage	
Contact person	
Contact person Title	
Contact's email	
Short description of the partner	
Short description of partner's role in the project	
Link to the logo of the institution in high resolution	

Figure 72 Template for Partners description

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From the beginning of the Smart Droplets project's website and up to M24 of the Second Reporting Period the website demonstrated remarkable performance and engagement. The captivating and insightful content drew substantial interest, as evidenced by the significant number of clicks and visits. Visitors displayed genuine curiosity in exploring the project's innovative approaches and solutions, underscoring the effectiveness of the presented information. This highlights the relevance of the content and also signifies the growing recognition of Smart Droplets as a leading initiative in the field of precision agriculture. Based on the analytics below, 2,282 unique users have visited the project's website and explored its content for 45 seconds.

Figure 73 Smart Droplets website analytics (1/09/2022-24/08/2024)

The KPI C2.1 (Unique website pageviews) 4 is no longer available in Google Analytics. This KPI has been updated to track the "Sessions" metric, which is considered a more conservative and accurate measure of website engagement. Based on the analytics below, the target for RP 2 (3000 unique website pageviews) has been exceeded, with more than 4,200 sessions recorded. This demonstrates strong and consistent interest in the Smart Droplets project.

Figure 74 Smart Droplets Website Sessions

4.2.3. Digital Media

Digital media have been crafted to deliver engaging and valuable content in a format that is both compelling and easily understandable for non-experts, especially for social media platforms. Our digital media strategy provides up-to-date information on project activities and results to both direct and indirect target groups.

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Additionally, multimedia materials have been produced to create a self-explanatory and captivating presentation of Smart Droplets, which will be leveraged through various distribution channels for promotional purposes.

To maximise the visibility and impact of the project's events and outcomes, Smart Droplets utilises the consortium's established social media networks. Consortium partners share, publish, and retweet content from the Smart Droplets social media accounts and website, thereby increasing traction for project-related work and driving traffic to partner websites and social media channels. Partners are also encouraged to create relevant content about the project's actions and share it through their own channels. Social media accounts have been collected from all partners to create a cohesive social network and to further promote Smart Droplets' activities and results, enhancing the project's online visibility.

After selecting the appropriate channels, several parameters are considered for distributing the consortium's social media content:

- **Interactivity:** This is the cornerstone of our content strategy. Posts are designed to be easily understood by non-specialists to facilitate interaction and engagement.
- **Visual Appeal:** Eye-catching posts are prioritised, with a focus on visuals and graphics to make each piece unique and increase conversion rates.
- **Adaptability:** Social media assets are tailored to the format and functionality of various devices. Ensuring optimal placement, particularly on mobile devices, is key to maximising their impact.

4.2.3.1. Social Media Channels

The project aims to have a strong social media presence and establish two-way communication channels, to better reach out and interact with target audiences and the broader public. To enhance interactive communication, six (6) media channels were selected based on the following three factors:

1. The most **cost-effective** set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholders' groups.
2. The most **adequate, valid, and powerful** media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and number of key-stakeholders, and
3. The most **popular** social media platforms used by Smart Droplets' partners, to communicate and interact with their customers and other stakeholders.

Smart Droplets is registered and active (M3) on LinkedIn, Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), SlideShare, YouTube and Instagram, and has established metrics for each channel to monitor its effectiveness and implement mitigation measures when necessary.

Figure 75: Smart Droplets Social Media Channels

The social media described above have been selected to further enhance the multi-actor approach of the project. Different kinds of stakeholders require different means of approach. In that sense, the following characteristics have been considered.

- **LinkedIn:** This channel is used mainly for creating awareness and generating networking and collaboration opportunities, due to its professional character and style of communication. Smart Droplets will use this channel to reach all identified target groups, by sharing updates about project key activities.
- **YouTube:** This channel is mainly used for awareness and training purposes due to its nature and features. Smart Droplets will use this channel to reach any stakeholder interested in data in agriculture, by making available: webinars, testimonial videos on the identified case studies, interviews and outreach videos. Similarly, the content of this social media platform is targeted to all identified target groups of the project.
- **X (formerly Twitter):** This channel is used mainly for building awareness and enhancing public relations. X is also often used to provide real time updates and quickly spread information regarding all fields of interest. Smart Droplets will use this channel to reach all identified target groups by focusing on workshops and events that will be happening throughout its course.
- **Facebook:** This channel is used mainly for building relationships and maintaining connections with peers and contacts. It is a good platform to build loyalty to the existing network base. Because of the plain language and messages, the content can reach out to several target groups, regardless of social and business backgrounds. Smart Droplets will use this channel to reach all identified target groups.
- **SlideShare:** This channel is mainly used for communication and education purposes. Project presentations will be uploaded for easy access to anyone interested.

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To maximise visibility and impact of the project, Smart Droplets exploits the consortium's already developed social media networks (both private and businesses related). In this context consortium members are sharing, comment, publish, and retweet - this depends on the form of social media outlet - content from the Smart Droplets social media accounts and website. Such partner-driven communication efforts also positively result in increased traction for project-related work and as well as increased traffic on partner's websites and social media. Partners are also encouraged to create relevant content to the project's actions and share it through their channels. A template was created to gather all the needed information from each partner such as the links to their official social media accounts.

After selecting the most favourable and appropriate channels for Smart Droplets several parameters listed below should be considered and used as guidelines when creating social media content and they go as follows:

- I. **Interactivity** is the main pillar of the generated content and is the best way to reach and engage an audience. Posts will be easily understood by different target groups, including non-specialists, creating traction and engagement.
- II. **Eye catching posts** will lead to higher conversions. By prioritising the creation of visuals and graphics with informative content, Smart Droplets will gain a unique dimension online and will overall lead to higher post engagement.
- III. **Adaptability** is important as users can access online content from various devices. Thus, the adaptability of social media assets to the format and functioning of several devices is necessary to ensure the maximization of asset placement, especially considering the use of mobile phones.

4.2.3.1.1. Social Media DOs & DON'Ts

A set of recommendations for effective social media engagement has been created to support Smart Droplets partners. This will facilitate the processes followed by partners regarding social media communication, and will boost the project's performance in its social media channels. Figure 76 provides a concise list of DOs and DON'Ts.

Figure 76: Social Media Recommended actions

Social Media Strategy and Key Points

Social media posts are published on project’s social media accounts on LinkedIn, Facebook, X, Instagram, SlideShare and YouTube with a standard frequency of one post per week, and adjusted according to the project’s needs. This social media strategy aims to maintain the audience’s engagement and inform about various topics related to the project, which are presented below:

- Updates regarding Smart Droplets partners’ event participation and activities, including conferences, webinars, workshops, etc.
- Smart Droplets Case Studies
- Smart Droplets internal meetings insights and important updates
- Interesting reads, articles, or news related to the project’s main concepts, namely data spaces, food systems, and data economy.
- Smart Droplets featured in media outlets
- Newsletter & blog posts updates
- Relevant International Days

All followers/ subscribers of the Smart Droplets social media channels are given the opportunity to react in posts, comment and spark conversations or repost the project’s content, depending on the respective social media platform.

Additionally, to effectively share information on social media our consortium will design posts based on how the audience consumes the message, considering user responses and engagements. The following figure explains the steps that a visually appropriate social media post shall contain and based on these high-efficiency posts will be created during project’s lifespan:

Figure 77: Assessment and criteria used for Smart Droplets Social Media posts

4.2.3.1.2. Hashtags

Another important tool for enhanced social media presence is the use of hashtags. Creating hashtags that are relevant helps users stay in touch with the project and its outcomes while also making it easy to find Smart Droplets-generated knowledge. Hashtags convey the main topics of Smart Droplets into easily digestible and engaging keyword phrases that help increase visibility in the social media environment while making key messages stand out and influence the relevant communities. Hashtags also have internal benefits to the consortium, as they help track and analyse quantitative and qualitative data generated on the above-mentioned social media platforms. For the generation of hashtags, feedback was asked for and received by all project partners to ensure that the bulk of concepts, ideas, tools/services were captured and incorporated. The project has official distinctive hashtags seen in the Figure below, which are used to monitor the posts related to the project. The hashtags used in Smart Droplets communication are as follows:

Figure 78: Smart Droplets Hashtag cloud

In addition, the hashtags #HorizonEurope, #ResearchImpactEU, suggested by the European Commission, accompany each post to emphasise the EU direction of the project.

4.2.3.1.3. LinkedIn

A **LinkedIn profile** (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/smart-droplets/>) was created, aiming to facilitate networking with the Smart Droplets target audiences and promoting the project’s activities, updates and interesting news. As such, all the project’s news are published on its LinkedIn profile, and partners will have the opportunity to start conversations on particular topics, to attract wider audiences. Figure 79 provides an overview of the Smart Droplets LinkedIn profile.

Figure 79: Smart Droplets LinkedIn Profile

LinkedIn analytics helps us evaluate the success of our professional networking and information dissemination efforts. Figure 80 provides an overview of the number of followers gained over the course of the last year (M12 to M24). During this period, the account has gained 345 followers, showing a significant improvement in growing our social media network. Followers’ numbers cannot be retrieved more than a year prior due to recent changes

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in LinkedIn’s policy. The total number of LinkedIn followers has increased by more than 42% compared to the previous reporting period.

Figure 80: Smart Droplets LinkedIn Metrics: Followers

From M12 (August 2023) to M24 (August 2024) Smart Droplets LinkedIn page has recorded exceptional engagement rates, with the lowest being 8.5% and the highest 18.1%, which is a clear indication of the compelling nature of our content and the high degree of audience interaction. This figure underscores the resonance of our initiatives with the professional community on LinkedIn. Given the platform’s user base of professionals, academics and industry leaders, this engagement is significant.

Figure 81: Smart Droplets LinkedIn Metrics: Engagement Rate

4.2.3.1.4. Facebook

Smart Droplets’ Facebook account (<https://www.facebook.com/SmartDroplets>) was created to communicate directly with target audiences on an individual level. Facebook is used to raise awareness for the Smart Droplets

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project and results targeting the general public and farmers who are mainly using the particular social media channel. Figure 82 provides an overview of Smart Droplet’s Facebook profile.

Figure 82: Smart Droplets Facebook Account

Reviewing Facebook analytics provides essential insights into the reach and effectiveness of our project. These metrics show how our posts are interacting with the public and farmers, demonstrating the level of awareness we've created. Below is an overview of the page’s metrics from M1 of the project (September 2022) up to M24 of the project (August 2024). The content has made significant progress in terms of audience reach, as illustrated below. In addition, approximately 1,600 interactions have been recorded, reflecting strong interest from both followers and non-followers of the Smart Droplets Facebook account.

Figure 83: Smart Droplets Facebook Metrics Overview

4.2.3.1.5. Instagram

Smart Droplets’ Instagram account (<https://www.instagram.com/smartdroplets/>) is being used for targeting similar, but also different demographics compared to Facebook. To effectively utilise this social media platform for communicating the scope and objectives of the project, Smart Droplets has been publishing posts concerning

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the news, the developments, and the events of the project (meetings and summarised events, including that of the two pilot cases once the timeline fits).

Figure 84: Smart Droplets Instagram Account

The progress of the content’s reach as well as the significant increase in terms of content interactions, can be seen in the table below:

Figure 85 Instagram reach and interactions

4.2.3.1.6. X (formerly Twitter)

An X (formerly Twitter) account was created (<https://twitter.com/SmartDroplets>) to increase the visibility of the project and engage specific audiences, such as policymakers and advisors. Smart Droplets will use short messages (less than 280 characters) to interact with them and post news, events, and updates on the project’s status.

X’s popularity and concise, simple format make it extremely important and useful for informing and engaging with our targeted audiences and their respective communities. X can also be used to connect to “high-esteemed influencers” in the research and business topics of the Smart Droplets project to successfully build an active community.

Figure 86: Smart Droplets X (formerly Twitter) Account

In June 2024, X (formerly Twitter) removed access to analytics from free accounts. By M24 (August 2024), our X account had reached more than 130 followers, achieving an increase of 26% during the last semester (M18 to M24). Compared to M13 (September 2023), the increase in M24 equals to more than 176% (130 to 47 X followers).

4.2.3.1.7. SlideShare

A SlideShare account (<https://www.slideshare.net/SmartDroplets>) has been created, and the material that is projected to be uploaded are visual formats that will help to resonate more with our readers, reach an audience that is interested in our content and cultivate more opportunities for future collaborations.

Figure 87: Smart Droplets SlideShare Page

4.2.3.1.8. YouTube

A YouTube account (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4e1fcol5HBhXLvMfAWdvA>) for the Smart Droplets project will be used in order to host and promote the project’s various videos (e.g interviews, promotional videos, insights from the real-life demonstrations, podcast videos / vodcasts etc). Up to the end of the second Reporting Period eight (8) videos had been uploaded. A video presentation of the project from the Automation & Robotics Expo in Athens (April 2024) and the first series of seven (7) vodcast episodes.

Figure 88 Smart Droplets YouTube

Regarding the KPI target of 100 blog posts and social media posts expected by the end of RP2, this target was significantly surpassed by a far margin, as by the end of M24 the total number of blog posts and social media posts had reached 419.

4.2.3.2. Newsletter

An electronic newsletter is published on a quarterly basis, to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members. This includes the latest developments, partners features, test case results and activities as well as upcoming events, workshops, demonstrations and where to find recent reports and publications.

Fourteen (14) E-newsletters will be created and distributed quarterly throughout the duration of the Smart Droplets project. An online newsletter will be published (starting in M04) to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members. This will include the latest developments, Pilots' activities and results, as well as upcoming events, workshops, demonstrations and where to find recent reports and publications.

Subscriptions can be signed up mainly through the Smart Droplets website, but also through various events (e.g., presentations of the project, workshops, etc). Upon Newsletter registration, Smart Droplets will pay special attention to security and respect the privacy and confidentiality of the users' personal data. Newsletter recipients will be asked to provide their consent prior to sending any information related to the project. All relevant activities and aspects related to personal data will be fully compliant with the applicable national, European, and international legal framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798. Interested parties will be able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the Smart Droplets newsletters. Furthermore, to achieve broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, Smart Droplets partners will be encouraged to promote newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project.

Four (4) e-newsletters were created and distributed quarterly during M1 to M12, four (4) e-newsletters during M13 to M24 and six (6) e-newsletters will be created from M25 to M42. RFF is responsible for creating and distributing the e-newsletters at M3, M6, M9, M12, M15, M18, M21, M24, M26, M29, M32, M35, M38, M41

4.2.3.2.1. Subscriptions to E-newsletters

Five hundred (500) subscriptions to E-newsletters are expected throughout the duration of the Smart Droplets project. A hundred (100) subscriptions to E-newsletters were expected during M1 to M12, 200 additional subscriptions to E-newsletters are expected during M13 to M24 (300 in total), and 200 subscriptions to E-

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newsletters will be expected during M25 to M42 (500 in total). RFF is responsible for following up on the number of e-newsletter subscriptions.

By the end of the second reporting period, newsletter subscribers surpassed 300. Our efforts included engaging stakeholders at industry conferences, conducting webinars, and leveraging social media to share project updates. Additionally, we collaborated with partner organizations to extend our reach and invited participants from workshops and pilot programs to subscribe. These activities ensured a diverse and engaged audience, keeping them informed about the latest developments and achievements of the Smart Droplets initiative.

4.2.3.2.2. Interactions to E-newsletters

An average of 20%-30% click-to-open rate is expected for the newsletters throughout the project. There has been a steady improvement of the click-to-open rate for each published newsletter, bringing the current average to 30%.

The image shows a subscription form for Smart Droplets. It features a green header with the text "Subscribe to get all information, latest news & other insights about Smart Droplets". Below this is a white input field labeled "Your email address" and a blue "Get started" button. At the bottom, there is a blue footer containing contact information for Project Coordination (Dr. Spyros Fountas, Associate Professor, Agricultural University of Athens) and Project Communication (Grigoris Chatzikostas, VP for Business Development, Foodscale Hub). It also includes the European Union logo and a note that the project is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme.

Figure 89: Smart Droplets Subscription form

Eight (8) newsletters were released as of M24. Newsletter #1 was released on 30/12/2022. Newsletter #2 was released on 28/04/2023. Newsletter #3 was released on 27/06/2023. Newsletter #4 was released on 24/10/2023. Newsletter #5 was released on 15/1/2024. Newsletter #6 was released on 4/4/2024. Newsletter #7 was released on 28/6/2024. Newsletter #8 was released on 29/8/2024.

The uploaded content is informative, providing knowledge on relevant to the project topics as well as the latest updates of Smart Droplets. The high quality of content resulted in the completion of another KPI goal, and this time of C2.5 - No. of newsletter subscribers. The target for the RP1 was 100 and has already been achieved. Up to M24 more than 300 subscribers had signed up to the project's newsletter, achieving the target for RP2.

Figure 90 Smart Droplets newsletter subscribers

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Newsletter [Issue 01](#)

Issue 01 of the newsletter was released on 30/12/2022 and was focused on introducing the project and presenting the main actions taken by the project partners in the first 3 months since its kick-off meeting. The topics it included were:

- Smart Droplets Introduction
- Smart Droplets Kick-Off Meeting
- 1st Press Release
- Participation in Paving the way towards the next generation of R&I Excellence in AI, Data and Robotics
- Introduction of Consortium Partners

Figure 91: Smart Droplets 1st Newsletter

Figure 92 presents an overview of the first newsletter analytics regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens, and total clicks.

Successful deliveries	47	92.2%	Clicks per unique opens	0%
Total opens	35		Total clicks	0

Figure 92: Newsletter Issue 01 Analytics

Newsletter [Issue 2](#)

The 2nd issue, released on 28/04/2023, was focused on informing the public, including non-specialists, regarding the role of data and AI in agriculture through blog posts published on the Smart Droplets website. More specifically, the topics included:

- Data-driven agriculture.
- Introduction to Digital Twins.
- “How can AI change spraying?”
- Digital skills and why they are necessary in agriculture.

In Figure 94, there is an overview of the 2nd newsletter analytics regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens, and total clicks.

Figure 93 Smart Droplets 2nd Newsletter

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48 Opened	6 Clicked	7 Bounced	0 Unsubscribed
--------------	--------------	--------------	-------------------

Successful deliveries 95 93.1% Clicks per unique opens 12.5%
 Total opens 80 Total clicks 6

Figure 94: Newsletter Issue 02 Analytics

Newsletter Issue 03

The image shows a preview of the Smart Droplets Newsletter Issue 03. It features the Smart Droplets logo at the top left. The main content includes several articles: 'How can autonomous tractors benefit farmers and SMEs?', 'Agricultural sprayers: from handheld to high-tech', 'Benefits of Direct Injection Spraying (DIS)', and 'Smart Droplets at agROBOfood Network Event!'. There are also images of agricultural machinery, a person speaking at a podium, and a video player showing a person speaking. A 'Learn About Next-Gen Sprayers' button is visible at the bottom left.

Figure 95 Smart Droplets Newsletter Issue 03

The 3rd Issue, released on 27/06/2023, was focused on educational content regarding the usage of autonomous tractor and agricultural sprayers, as well as Direct Injection Spraying. Additionally, a special section was devoted to the events & TV Shows the Smart Droplets project was presented at. In detail, the updated included were:

- “How can autonomous tractors benefit farmers and SMEs?”
- “Agricultural sprayers: from handheld to high-tech”
- “Benefits of Direct Injection Spraying (DIS)”
- Smart Droplets presentation at AgROBOfood Network Event
- Smart Droplets on “Exypni Oikonomia” TV show

In the following figure, an overview of the 3rd issue analytics is provided, regarding the audience’s location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens, and total clicks.

48 Opened	6 Clicked	2 Bounced	0 Unsubscribed
--------------	--------------	--------------	-------------------

Successful deliveries 99 98.0% Clicks per unique opens 12.5%
 Total opens 73 Total clicks 8

Figure 96 Newsletter Issue 03 Analytics

Newsletter [Issue 04](#)

Welcome to the 4th edition of the Smart Droplets newsletter!

Dive into this edition to explore new blog posts on AI & Data, updates from partners and useful workshops that took place over the past couple of months!

Read our latest blog posts

Hybrid approaches have emerged as a promising solution in crop care, fusing data, artificial intelligence (AI), digital farm twins, and real-time information to optimise spraying operations. [How can we explore their potential?](#)

How can data interoperability enhance farming operations? It facilitates the harmonious integration and analysis of data derived from sensors, satellites, weather stations, and machinery. Read more [here](#)

Exciting updates from Wageningen University & Research

The research paper "Nitrogen management with reinforcement learning and crop growth

The 4th Issue, released on 24/10/2023, highlighted the project's representation at the reputed "Synergy Days" event held in Thessaloniki on the 4th and 5th of October 2023. A special section was also devoted to the latest Smart Droplets blog posts. There was also a section with the latest activities of the consortium's partners. In detail, the content included the following:

- The Future of Crop Care: Exploring the Potential of Hybrid Approaches in Agriculture
- The Role of Data Interoperability in Smart Farming: Unlocking Insights for Optimal Crop Care
- Exciting updates from Wageningen University & Research
- Knowledge Exchange: Partner-Organized Sessions
- Smart Droplets participated in the Synergy Days Conference!

Figure 97 Smart Droplets Newsletter Issue 4

In the following figure, an overview of the 4th issue analytics is provided.

108 Recipients

Audience: Smart Droplets

Subject: Smart Droplets Newsletter | Issue #4

Delivered: Tue, October 24 2023 3:17 AM

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57 Opened	7 Clicked	6 Bounced	1 Unsubscribed
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Successful deliveries	102	94.4%	Clicks per unique opens	12.3%
Total opens	89		Total clicks	26
Last opened	12/21/23 1:11PM		Last clicked	10/30/23 9:09AM
Forwarded	0		Abuse reports	0

Figure 98 Issue 04 Analytics

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

Newsletter [Issue 05](#)

Welcome to the 5th edition of the Smart Droplets newsletter

In the new edition of our newsletter you can catch up on the developments of the Smart Droplets project, the activities of our partners and get updated on AI in crop spraying from our latest blog posts.

🔥 Exciting updates from our partners!

During November and December 2023 our partners helped to raise the awareness of Smart Droplets by attending events and presenting various aspects of the project. With their inspiring presentations and their scientific insights, they fueled the project's progress.

On November 23th, our partner, VizLoi LLC, attended the Data Science Conference 2023, in Belgrade, Serbia. Mihailo Ilic, presented the SmartDroplets Project.

In particular, he spoke on the topic of "Scalable and Interoperable Data Flow Management for Digital Twin Frameworks in Smart Farming". We thank him for his contribution. [Read more here](#).

The 5th Issue was released on 15/01/24. Among its highlights, the Smart Droplets Academy stood out. The newsletter consisted of the following topics:

- Exciting updates from our partners!
- Smart Droplets Academy: The latest seminars
- Read our new blog posts!
- Smart Droplets Annual Project Meeting
- AI in agriculture: What is available and what is expected

Figure 99 Smart Droplets Newsletter Issue 5

In the following figure, an overview of the 5th issue analytics is provided

123 Recipients

Audience: Smart Droplets

Delivered: Mon, January 15 2024 5:55 AM

Subject: Smart Droplets Newsletter | Issue #5

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63 Opened	3 Clicked	6 Bounced	1 Unsubscribed
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Successful deliveries	117	95.1%	Clicks per unique opens	4.8%
Total opens	91		Total clicks	9
Last opened	4/29/24 4:18PM		Last clicked	1/15/24 6:16AM
Forwarded	0		Abuse reports	0

Figure 100 Issue 05 Analytics

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

Newsletter [Issue 06](#)

The 6th Issue was released on 04/04/24. The most important topic of the newsletter was the project's participation in the Automation & Robotics exposition in Athens. In detail, the topics were the following:

Welcome to the 6th edition of the Smart Droplets newsletter

In our latest newsletter edition, you can stay informed about the progress of the Smart Droplets project, discover the initiatives of our partners, and stay current on AI applications in crop spraying through our newest blog entries!

- Smart Droplets IP Workshop
- Our partners' news!
- Our latest blog posts!
- Smart Droplets at the A & R Expo in Athens!

The first three months of 2024 included a notable array of events. From January to March, partners of Smart Droplets enthusiastically participated in initiatives aimed at raising awareness of the project. Leveraging their positive energy and expertise, they propelled the project's advancement further! Also during this period, the first IP workshop was organised with success.

Figure 101 Newsletter Issue 6

Smart Droplets IP Workshop

On January 29th, Foodscale Hub successfully organised the first **Smart Droplets Intellectual Property (IP) workshop**. The main topics discussed were: 1) Intellectual Property and Intellectual Property Rights, 2) IP Protection Measures, and 3) IP in EU funded Projects / IP Management in Smart Droplets.

125 Recipients

Audience: Smart Droplets

Delivered: Thu, April 4 2024 4:37 AM

Subject: Smart Droplets Newsletter | Issue #6

[View email](#) · [Download](#) · [Print](#) · [Share](#)

76 Opened	9 Clicked	2 Bounced	1 Unsubscribed
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Successful deliveries	123	98.4%	Clicks per unique opens	11.8%
Total opens	110		Total clicks	53
Last opened	7/11/24 5:11AM		Last clicked	4/5/24 2:10AM
Forwarded	0		Abuse reports	0

Figure 102 Issue 06 Analytics

Newsletter [Issue 07](#)

Welcome to the 7th edition of our newsletter!

Time flies! From April until mid-June of 2024, Smart Droplets continued its exciting journey. The project was showcased at an important exposition on Robotics in Athens, Greece. Our team presented the project before the enthusiastic students of American Farm School of Thessaloniki. Also, we joined forces with five other innovative projects!

The 7th Issue was released on 28/6/2024. It highlighted the project’s showcase at the Automation & Robotics exposition in Athens. The following topics were also included:

- Smart Droplets at the 1st Automation and Robotics Expo!
- Our visit to the American Farm School!
- An elite team of six!
- Sustainability leads the way: an innovative new tool!

Smart Droplets at the 1st Automation and Robotics Expo!

mid-April, we participated in the **1st Automation & Robotic EXPO** in Athens, Greece. It was a great opportunity for visitors to explore the latest trends in agricultural automation and robotics, and meet our team! During the event, our Project Manager, Kalliopi Kounani delivered an enlightening presentation on Smart Droplets!

Figure 103 Newsletter Issue 7

72 Opened	14 Clicked	4 Bounced	1 Unsubscribed
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Successful deliveries	132	97.1%	Clicks per unique opens	19.4%
Total opens	112		Total clicks	81
Last opened	8/21/24	4:26AM	Last clicked	8/9/24 10:57AM
Forwarded	0		Abuse reports	0

Figure 104 Issue 07 Analytics

Newsletter [Issue 08](#)

The 8th Issue was released on 29/8/2024. It highlighted the first season of the Smart Droplets Podcast series. The following topics were also included:

- Smart Droplets tech briefs are online!
- Smart Droplets makes a splash in the news!
- Smart Droplets joined forces with Quantifarm!

Figure 105 Newsletter Issue 8

The 8th issue of the Smart Droplets newsletter was just released before the submission of this report, making reliable analytics unavailable. The analytics for the 8th issue of the newsletter will be included in the 4th version of the Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports.

4.2.3.3. Press Outreach

Press releases will be produced and distributed for publication among national/regional/EU press to further promote the project, its latest activities, and developments to a broader audience as well as address more specific stakeholders. The press releases are available on the Smart Droplets website under the tab Newsroom, and all related publications will be shared on social media channels to disseminate the information. Thus, a press release template has been developed (Annex K) during M3. To maximize our influence on local stakeholders, the consortium is advised to translate all press releases into all 6 of the consortium partners' languages. More specifically:

Number of partners covered by language	Language
3	Greek
1	Dutch
2	Spanish
2	Serbia
1	French
1	Lithuanian

Table 9: Number of different languages Smart Droplets press releases can be translated into

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

A Press Release concerning the project's launch was released on 26/10/2022. The PR was uploaded to the project's website and hosted a statement from the project Coordinator, Prof. Spyros Fountas from the Agricultural University of Athens.

Figure 106 Smart Droplets 1st Press Release

On 10/04/2024, a second press release was distributed and published in Greek media and uploaded to the project's website in English for translation into the partners' native languages. The PR presented the Smart Droplets Academy initiative.

Figure 107 Smart Droplets 2nd Press Release

A third Press Release regarding the Innovation Radar's assessment of the project's key technologies was published on 18/07/2024. The PR was distributed and published in Greek media and uploaded to the project's website in English for translation into the partners' native languages.

Figure 108 Smart Droplets 3rd Press Release

Three more PRs were released on M23 and M24. A fourth Press Release regarding the launch and the successful production of the first seven (7) Smart Droplets Vodcast episodes was published on the website.

Figure 109 Smart Droplets 4th Press Release

A fifth Press Release was distributed to the partners and uploaded on the project’s website. The PR underscores the technological readiness of the project’s innovations for real-world deployment, featuring the successful testing of the autonomous tractor. This milestone demonstrates significant progress in autonomy and operational efficiency, positioning the developed technologies for imminent integration into agricultural practices.

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

Figure 110 Smart Droplets 5th Press Release

A sixth Press Release was uploaded on the project’s website. The PR highlights the forming of connections between Smart Droplets and key stakeholders and innovative research projects. The PR was distributed and published in Greek media and uploaded in the project’s website in English for translation into the partners’ native languages.

Figure 111 Smart Droplets 6th Press Release

4.2.4. Speeches/interviews/Participation in media

The Smart Droplets project was featured on the "Smart Economy" TV show on May 3rd 2023, where representatives from reframe.food, elaborated on its mission to foster a more sustainable future in farming. The presentation highlighted how Smart Droplets aims to reduce chemical usage in agriculture through the

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

integration of advanced data and technology. The show provided an overview of the innovative approaches employed by the project, such as leveraging AI and robotics, to improve farming practices and promote environmental sustainability. The segment underscored the project's commitment to enhancing agricultural efficiency and reducing environmental impact, engaging a wider audience in its vision for sustainable agriculture.

Figure 112 Smart Droplets featured on the "Smart Economy" show

Giannis Fyrogenis and Antonis Andronikakis from RFF presented Smart Droplets to students of the American Farm School in Thessaloniki on May 20, 2024, focusing on the project's scope, vision, and technological components. The presentation covered advanced technologies such as AI, robotics, and digital twins, demonstrating how these are integrated to enhance crop spraying efficiency and promote sustainability. The session provided an in-depth exploration of these innovations, followed by an interactive discussion where students engaged with the Smart Droplets team, gaining valuable insights into the practical applications and benefits of these technologies in agriculture.

Figure 113 Speech presenting Smart Droplets at the American Farm School

Smart Droplets project manager Kalliopi Kounani of AUA gave an interview to the agricultural newspaper Ypaithros Chora, explaining the core idea behind the project's sustainable crop spraying solution and the key technologies involved. The interview led to the publication of an article on the project.

On August 7, AFL appeared on the Lithuanian radio station FM99 to discuss the Smart Droplets project. During the interview, AFL highlighted the project's efforts to reduce pesticide and fertilizer use through AI and robotic technologies, emphasizing its importance in advancing sustainable agriculture. The broadcast helped raise awareness about the project's impact among the Lithuanian public.

Figure 114 AFL's radio interview presenting Smart Droplets

4.2.5. Smart Droplets Podcast Series

Season 1 of the Smart Droplets podcast series is structured around seven episodes, each focusing on a key aspect of the project, aimed at showcasing technological innovations and practical implementations in precision and digital agriculture. The episodes were developed through in-depth interviews with experts and partners involved in the project, providing an overview of various themes and advancements. In order to improve the quality of the end result, and the interactions between the interviewees and the interviewer the series was shot as a vodcast series. Due to limitations of partners' availability and the absence of an event that could physically gather all partners, the first episode of the Smart Droplets podcast was shot with the physical presence of the project manager, Kalliopi Kounani, while the remaining episodes were recorded online using the Zoom platform. A professional videographer was present throughout the entire process to ensure high-quality production. Interviewee partners were provided with detailed guidelines to facilitate smooth and effective participation. Additionally, professional recording equipment was used to capture clear audio and video, ensuring that each episode maintained a professional standard despite the remote recording setup. This planning and execution were essential in delivering a polished and informative vodcast series.

- **Episode 1:** Core Concept and Consortium - Introduces the Smart Droplets project, the role of the coordinator, and the various technologies developed by consortium partners.
- **Episode 2:** Autonomous Technology - Focuses on the autonomous movement of retrofit tractors, detailing the technologies and development challenges.
- **Episode 3:** Digital Twins and AI - Explores the use of digital twins and artificial intelligence in agriculture, highlighting their benefits and success stories.
- **Episode 4:** Internet of Things (IoT) - Discusses IoT and data collection in Smart Droplets, showcasing how these technologies improve farming practices.
- **Episode 5:** Direct Injection Spraying - Covers the technology and benefits of direct injection spraying for precision agriculture.
- **Episode 6:** User Requirements Mapping - Details the process of identifying user requirements and insights from farmers and industry stakeholders.
- **Episode 7:** Retrofit Kit Development - Highlights the development and benefits of retrofit tractors equipped with autonomous navigation systems.

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This season aims to provide listeners with educational material on cutting edge digital agriculture technologies by offering a detailed understanding of the Smart Droplets project's innovations, challenges, and real-world applications, promoting sustainable and efficient farming practices through advanced technology. Each episode was meticulously developed to ensure valuable insights and practical knowledge for the audience, enhancing the project's visibility and engagement with the agricultural community. A comprehensive breakdown of all the questions in the first season of the Smart Droplets vodcast series can be found in **Annex T**.

Figure 115 The first season of the Smart Droplets Vodcast series

4.2.6. Smart Droplets Articles

As an Innovation Action focused on developing high-TRL solutions with a robust go-to-market strategy, featuring Smart Droplets in relevant industry magazines is crucial for the successful exploitation of the project's results.

An article in **Agro.tech Magazine**, on 05/07/2024, provides a comprehensive overview of the Smart Droplets project, detailing its objectives, technological innovations, and consortium members. It highlights the project's focus on reducing pesticide and fertilizer use through advanced technologies like AI, digital twins, and robotics to improve agricultural performance and sustainability.

Figure 116 Smart Droplets featured in Agro.tech magazine (the article is in Greek)

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

One more article about Smart Droplets by RFF has been featured on **AgroCapital**, one of the most popular Greek agricultural websites on 01/08/2024. The article showcases the project's innovations in autonomous tractor technology, which play a crucial role in enhancing crop care efficiency and supporting environmental sustainability.

Figure 117 Article on AgroCapital.gr focusing on the autonomous tractor technology developed in the project

The recent feature on Smart Droplets in the **Ypaithros Chora** agricultural newspaper on 02/08/2024 provides a comprehensive overview of our innovative approach to sustainable crop-spraying. Highlighted in both the high-profile agricultural newspaper and the ypaithros.gr website, the article focuses on the key technologies driving the project, as explained by our project manager, Kalliopi Kounani. This coverage significantly boosts Smart Droplets' visibility within the agricultural community.

Figure 118 The Smart Droplet's project manager's, Kalliopi Kounani's interview, featured in Ypaithros Chora magazine

Another article featuring Smart Droplets was published on **Mokslo Lietuva**, a Lithuanian platform focused on science, technology, and innovation. The article highlights the advancements in sustainable agriculture technology being developed through the Smart Droplets project. It discusses efforts to reduce the use of pesticides and fertilizers by utilizing AI, data, and robotics to optimize agricultural practices, supporting broader environmental sustainability goals.

Figure 119 AFL's article on the Mokslo Lietuva magazine featuring Smart Droplets

An article by AFL was published on the **Inovacijos.It** platform on 06/08/2024, highlighting the recognition of the Smart Droplets project by the European Commission's Innovation Radar. The article emphasizes the project's market potential, particularly its innovative approach to reducing pesticide and fertilizer use through advanced AI, data, and robotic technologies.

Figure 120 AFL's article on the Inovacijos.It platform

An additional article featuring the Smart Droplets project's development of the Direct Injection System, written by the RFF team, has been published in the **Greek Farmer (Ellinas Agrotis)**, a new entry in national agricultural newspapers, on 14/08/2024. The article highlights how this innovative system is designed to optimize pesticide application, reducing waste and environmental impact while improving crop care efficiency.

Figure 121 Smart Droplets article on the Greek agricultural newspaper "Greek Farmer"

These articles collectively aim to increase the visibility and awareness of the Smart Droplets project, showcasing its technological advancements and contributions to sustainable agriculture across various European regions.

5. Exploitation Activities

5.1. Smart Droplets Exploitation Strategy and Measures

The Smart Droplets project is designed to integrate advanced technologies such as AI, data analytics, and robotics into agricultural practices to enhance efficiency, sustainability, and scalability. The exploitation strategy encompasses several core objectives aimed at ensuring the project's innovations are effectively utilised during and beyond its lifecycle.

The strategy involves planning deliverables, validating Key Exploitable Results (KERs), conducting market analysis, exploring funding sources, and developing comprehensive exploitation plans. By systematically validating KERs through iterative sprints, the project aligns its outputs with market needs and project objectives. Market analysis provides insights into competitive landscapes, market contexts, and potential growth areas, facilitating informed decision-making for commercializing innovations. Funding sources from public and private sectors are explored to secure financial sustainability.

The development of joint and individual exploitation plans ensures that each partner has a clear roadmap for utilizing project results. The sustainability plan focuses on actions that ensure long-term impact, while the IPR management strategies protect and manage intellectual property effectively. Additionally, the strategy includes exploring the policy and regulatory landscape, encouraging participation in standardization processes to align with industry standards and regulations.

A robust methodology underpins these objectives. The methodology emphasizes a multi-actor approach, ensuring that various stakeholders are engaged throughout the project lifecycle. This approach fosters collaboration and knowledge exchange among project partners, enhancing the overall impact of the project's results. The exploitation strategy is closely linked with other work packages, particularly those related to market analysis, technology development, and pilot implementation. This integrated approach ensures that the project's outputs are not only innovative but also practically applicable in real-world agricultural settings.

The project sets out clear KPIs to monitor and evaluate the success of exploitation activities:

- 7,000 stakeholders following the project progress
- Up to 7 Smart Droplets products/services reaching the market
- 24 MoUs/Lois signed with industry associations and groups, as well as potential investors or partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up
- 2 sets of standardization recommendations

Regular monitoring and evaluation against these KPIs ensure that the project remains on track to achieve its exploitation goals.

Furthermore, sustainability is a key focus of the exploitation strategy. The project aims to ensure that the innovations developed are not only impactful during the project but also have a lasting influence on the agricultural sector, after the project's conclusion. To achieve this, the project includes a detailed sustainability plan outlining specific activities to be implemented post-project. These activities include further research and development, commercialization efforts, and continuous engagement with stakeholders. The project also explores various scalability avenues, ensuring that the solutions developed can be adapted and scaled to different agricultural contexts and regions. These considerations, along with IPR management for Smart Droplets are elaborated in much greater detail in the existing and upcoming iterations of the project's Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy Deliverables (the already published D6.5 & D6.6 and the forthcoming D6.7 and D6.8).

The following sections will now explore the commercial and non-commercial pathways in detail, outlining how project results will be leveraged for market entry, scientific research, and policy development.

5.1.1. Commercial and Non-commercial Exploitation

Commercial exploitation

Regarding the **commercial exploitation**, a comprehensive **Market Analysis** is crucial for effectively positioning Smart Droplets' prime offerings, including the Smart Droplets Solution and its technological components. The market analysis methodology detailed in D6.6 uses tools such as TAM, SAM, and SOM assessments to define market potential, concentration ratios to assess market dominance, the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index to quantify market concentration, and Porter's Five Forces to analyse industry competition and strategic positioning. It also includes target user identification to pinpoint end-users, PESTELE analysis to examine political, economic, social, technological, environmental, legal, and ethical factors, and SWOT and competitive analysis to evaluate strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. Compliance with legislative and regulatory frameworks ensures data protection and adherence to regulations, while identifying funding opportunities aligns project goals with EU initiatives and stays updated on grants and investments. The results of those tools will be presented based on the project's ongoing needs in the upcoming D6.7.

Non-commercial exploitation

Smart Droplets identifies two types of project results – commercial and non-commercial. Not all results from the project are intended for commercial exploitation. Significant attention is given to the investigation and elaboration of exploitation routes for non-commercial project results. Potential non-commercial KERs include publications (papers, books), presentations, data supporting further research activities, specific reports, and policy papers and recommendations for EU and Member States' directives or regulations.

The exploitation pathways for non-commercial results may appear in various dimensions, referencing individual or joint exploitation plans. These non-commercial outcomes span scientific, educational, societal, and political spheres:

- **Scientific Progress and Reusability:** The project generates scientific outputs, including models, methodologies, prototypes, and datasets, which the broader scientific community can use for subsequent research. These outputs foster continuity and build upon existing knowledge, significantly bolstering future scientific endeavours.
- **Policymaking:** Project results provide empirically grounded insights for policymakers and regulatory bodies. This evidence-based information is crucial for formulating new policies or refining existing ones, thus guiding policy decisions with robust empirical data.
- **Educational and Training Synergy:** Some project outcomes contribute to creating educational and training modules for students, professionals, and the public. These materials disseminate project insights, enhancing knowledge dissemination and skill acquisition within relevant domains.
- **Catalysing Standards in Agriculture:** The project's outputs can instigate new benchmarks and standards in agricultural practices and technologies, leading to positive transformations and advancements in the broader agricultural landscape.

Harnessing the scientific breakthroughs pioneered by Smart Droplets reveals several exploitation avenues. These include integrating our innovations into ongoing research activities, initiating new research collaborations, and developing educational and training initiatives. However, to protect their economic interests, private project partners may impose certain restrictions on scientific utilization. These limitations, such as time-bound usage restrictions, apply to knowledge generated through collaborations between commercial enterprises and research institutions, balancing the need for scientific progress with economic priorities.

5.2. Smart Droplets Key Exploitable Results

During the Proposal Preparation Phase, Smart Droplets had foreseen the development of a set of Key Exploitable Results (KERs). This sub-chapter reflects as a sequel of the former section of the Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1) imprinting the identified seven final key exploitable results, whilst respecting and aligning with the processes and measures described within the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR

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management strategy v1 & v2 (D6.5 & D.6.6). Figure 122 imprints the seven results, as identified in the Proposal Preparation Phase and Grant Agreement phase, whereas Figure 123 describes, more detailed, each result, regardless of form or nature, tangibility or intangibility, commercialisation, or non-commercialisation, who is responsible for it, who it will benefit, as well as its Unique Value Proposition (UVP), as captured in the in the initial plan of the Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1).

Figure 122: Smart Droplets KERs

Figure 123: Smart Droplets KERs

5.2.1. Identification of new exploitable results

While the initial capturing of Smart Droplets' KERs was initiated early on, the validation phase towards developing the final list of commercial KERs has now been completed. Although no additional KERs have been identified since the initial capture, the comprehensive, iterative, and ongoing process for compiling Smart Droplets' non-commercial KERs continues. For this reason, a methodology consisting of five steps was established, as depicted in Figure 124.

Figure 124: Methodology for the identification and inclusion of a new KER

To support the continuous capturing, monitoring, and management of KERs throughout the project's lifecycle, the Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue (Annex Q) was developed. This Catalogue serves as a tool for validating and mapping both commercial and non-commercial KERs. While the mapping of commercial KERs was concluded during the first validation phase, non-commercial KERs that may emerge can still be mapped in future iterations. The Catalogue aims to include both tangible and intangible outcomes with potential for exploitation post-project, encompassing scientific, societal, and economic applications, and outlining partners' future strategies and intentions.

The first edition of the Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue v1 has been completed and validated by the consortium. The results are presented in detail in D6.6: Sustainability, Scalability and IPR Management. Given the ongoing nature of the KERs compilation process, the Catalogue is scheduled to be updated three times during the project, aligning with key milestones. Specifically, the second and third updates will be included in the third and fourth iterations of the Sustainability, Scalability, and IPR Management Strategy (D6.7 and D6.8) at M30 and M42, coinciding with the end of each MVP phase.

In summary, the Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue includes key information such as:

- Description of the exploitable result
- Nature of the exploitable result (tangible, intangible)
- Unique Value Proposition (UVP)
- Status of exploitation (commercial, non-commercial)
- Scope of exploitation (scientific, educational, societal, political, economic)
- Target groups (to whom)
- Means of exploitation
- IPR(s) linked to the KER, if relevant

5.2.2. Individual Exploitation Plans

Smart Droplets is making substantial progress in developing and refining individual exploitation plans for each partner, ensuring that every organization can effectively leverage the project's innovations for long-term success. This ongoing effort is designed to tailor strategies to each partner's unique strengths, market positions, and KERs, providing a solid and usable framework for sustainable exploitation.

The development of these plans began with a focus on offering market insights that identify the target markets, competitive landscapes, and specific challenges each partner might encounter. These insights have enabled partners to better understand the intricacies of their respective markets, allowing them to develop strategies that align with their goals and the project's overarching objectives.

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

Each partner has been actively engaged in identifying key activities crucial for the successful commercialization of their KERs. These activities include development, field testing, integration, and training delivery, with a focus on utilizing key resources such as research teams, computational infrastructure, and field sites. By measuring success through specific metrics like resource efficiency, increased yield, user adoption rates, and training completion rates, partners can track their progress and adjust strategies accordingly.

The financial aspect of the exploitation plans focuses on outlining cost structures, identifying revenue streams, and exploring fundraising opportunities. While the plans provide a foundation for financial sustainability, they emphasize practical steps such as licensing, consultancy, and grants, rather than extensive financial forecasting. By identifying potential funding sources through EU programs and industry partnerships, the plans aim to support the viability of each partner's exploitation activities.

Intellectual property management is another critical area where significant progress has been made. Partners are equipped with strategies for IP protection, identifying potential rights, and leveraging them to safeguard and commercialize their innovations effectively.

The ongoing development of these individual exploitation plans is a collaborative effort. As part of this process, Lean Business Models will be created and validated with each individual partner. These models provide a clear and structured approach to commercializing project outputs, including detailed representations of their business models, value propositions, customer segments, and key activities.

The progress made in these activities highlights the project's commitment to comprehensive and strategic exploitation planning. This work will be included in deliverable D6.7, where the detailed plans and jointly developed Lean Business Models will be thoroughly documented. This inclusion demonstrates the extensive work being done to ensure the project's innovations are effectively utilized and sustained, showcasing Smart Droplets' dedication to fostering innovation and scalability in agriculture.

5.2.3. Innovation Radar

Following the necessary procedures, three innovations from the Smart Droplets project have been analysed by the European Commission's Innovation Radar, each demonstrating significant potential and market readiness:

1. **Catalog of Digital Farm Twins for Apples and Winter Wheat Crops**
 - **Market Maturity:** Exploring
 - **Market Creation Potential:** Addresses needs of existing markets
 - **Key Innovators Identified:** FONDACIJA VIZLORE LABS, GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY
2. **DIS - Direct Injection System on Agricultural Sprayers**
 - **Market Maturity:** Tech Ready
 - **Market Creation Potential:** Addresses needs of existing markets
 - **Key Innovators Identified:** PETKOS ANONYMI ETAIREIA, FUNDACIO EURECAT, GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON
3. **Digital Platform for Creating and Managing High-Quality (Reference) Data Sets for Digital Twins and AI Models in Agriculture**
 - **Market Maturity:** Tech Ready
 - **Market Creation Potential:** High
 - **Key Innovators Identified:** FONDACIJA VIZLORE LABS, GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY

The details of these innovations, including the market maturity and creation potential, will be published on the European Commission's Innovation Radar platform. The publication will include the names of the beneficiary organizations identified as key innovators, along with basic project information such as the project acronym, title, description, and end date.

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

Inclusion in the Innovation Radar platform opens up several strategic opportunities for the recognized innovators:

1. **Claiming and Enhancing Visibility:** Innovator organizations featured on the platform can enhance their visibility and showcase their capabilities to potential partners, customers, and investors.
2. **Access to Market Training and Support:** Innovators can apply for "go to market" training and support from Dealflow.eu, a support action financed by Horizon Europe. Dealflow.eu offers tailored support to help innovators commercialize their EU-funded innovations. This includes services such as business mentoring, investor matchmaking, and strategic advisory, enhancing the market readiness of the innovations.
3. **Horizon Results Booster Services:** Innovators can benefit from Horizon Results Booster services, which include "Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy," "Business Plan Development," and "Go to Market" support. These services are available at no cost.
4. **Networking and Partnership Opportunities:** Being featured on the Innovation Radar platform can trigger interest from potential business or academic partners, as well as investors, fostering new collaborations and partnerships that can drive further innovation and commercialization.

The recognition of Smart Droplets innovations by the European Commission's Innovation Radar underscores the project's impact and potential in the agricultural technology sector. By leveraging the visibility and support offered by the Innovation Radar platform, Smart Droplets and its partners can enhance their market engagement, attract investment, and accelerate the commercialization of their innovative solutions, ultimately contributing to the advancement of sustainable agricultural practices across Europe.

5.3. IPR Strategy

Building upon the dedicated Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v2 (D6.6) and the updated Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation plan v2 (D6.2), this chapter outlines the IPR Strategy as developed in previous deliverables and details the IPR Strategy Actions implemented so far.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) encompass ownership privileges related to intellectual creations, including innovations, names, visual representations, and designs. These rights empower creators to benefit financially from their ideas. Striking a balance between the interests of creators and the general public fosters an environment conducive to creativity and innovation.

Each KER has the potential to involve IPR management. The comprehensive blueprint outlined in the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v2 (D6.6) provides a detailed strategy for each result, specifying the tangible steps that partners must take regarding IPR. Smart Droplets conducts thorough assessments of the protective measures required for any result intended for commercial or industrial exploitation. These evaluations inform decisions on how to safeguard these assets, considering feasibility, reasonability, and legitimacy.

Following the IPR Methodology depicted in the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v2 (D6.6), the initial two stages, Proposal Stage and Grant Preparation Phase, which focus on Background IP and the Consortium Agreement, have been completed. Building on the IPR framework established during these phases, Smart Droplets is now in the Project Implementation Phase of the IPR Strategy.

Figure 125: Smart Droplets' IPR Methodology

During the Project Planning and Proposal Stage, we meticulously considered each participant's background, assets, and potential IPRs, laying a solid foundation for harnessing these assets for the project's advancement and utilization of IPR-bound outcomes. This phase culminated in the creation of the Preliminary Results Ownership List.

In the Grant Preparation Phase, we addressed knowledge management and IPR administration, encapsulated within the robust Consortium Agreement (CA). This document rigorously defines confidentiality, Background & Sideground IP, ownership dynamics, legal safeguards for results, exploitation avenues, and access rights. The principle of Results Ownership is paramount, with each entity retaining ownership of its results. In cases of collaborative result generation, Joint Ownership mechanisms ensure equitable cooperation and strategic foresight for future exploitation.

In the Project Implementation Phase, we have undertaken several actions and activities. Initial work on formulating basic IP and IPR concepts has been completed. A dedicated IPR workshop for Smart Droplets Partners, as outlined in the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR Management Strategy v2 (D6.6), took place in January 2024 (M18). This workshop served as an introduction to IPR concepts, increasing the consortium's familiarity with IPR issues.

The IPR workshop aimed to elevate the consortium's readiness regarding IPR and IP concepts. The content covered:

IPR Thematics:

- Intellectual Property Concepts and Definitions on a Strategic Level.
- Main Intellectual Property Issues & Concepts.
- The Legal Environment of Horizon Europe.

Types of IPR:

- **Patent:** Exclusive rights for an invention, allowing the owner to control its use.
- **Trademark:** Signs distinguishing goods and services of one enterprise from another.
- **Industrial Design:** The aesthetic aspect of an object, including 2D features (patterns, lines, colours) and 3D features (shape, surface).
- **Copyright:** Legal rights over literary and artistic works, extending to databases, advertisements, maps, and technical drawings.
- **Trade Secret:** Commercially valuable confidential information, including technical or nontechnical data, formulas, patterns, methods, and customer lists.
- **Confidentiality:** Protection of information not publicly known.

The workshop emphasized the importance of understanding these IPR types for informed decision-making. Time was allocated to discuss the fundamental aspects and specifications for choosing the most suitable type of IPR for various activities and results.

Following the initial workshop, partners were tasked with completing the 1st iteration of the Smart Droplets **Exploitation & IP Catalogue**, as was previously mentioned. This online tool is designed to document and manage IP and KERs effectively. Each partner systematically recorded their innovations, tracking IP status and planning for future exploitation. The completion of the IP Catalogue is a critical step in ensuring that all potential IP is identified and properly managed. This collaborative effort ensures that the consortium is aligned on IPR issues and prepared to protect and exploit their innovations effectively.

Building on the groundwork laid in the first workshop, two additional workshops are planned. The **second workshop (Workshop A)**, scheduled for M25, will focus on developing robust business cases and value propositions for the project's joint assets. This session will address the best business models, organizational structures for commercialization, and legal challenges related to IPR.

The **third workshop (Workshop B)**, planned for M40, will emphasize operationalization and market engagement strategies. This session will include discussions on market entry strategies, potential risks, and funding opportunities, helping partners effectively position the project for successful market entry and growth.

5.4. Next Steps

Considering the delays in the project's pilots, adjustments to the exploitation plan are essential to ensure alignment with the revised timeline. The next steps will be organized into the following phases, highlighting what has been accomplished and outlining the planned activities once the delayed MVP2 phase begins.

Design & Plan MVP1 Phase

Duration: From project start date (M0) to December 2023 (M16) (initial planning)

During this phase, several significant activities have been completed. The Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue template has been developed and validated by the consortium. The first IP workshop was successfully conducted in January 2024 (M17), providing essential IP considerations to project partners. Furthermore, the overarching Exploitation and Sustainability strategy was presented to project partners and the validation of the initial version of the Exploitation and IP Catalogue was completed, including the seven identified KERs. Individual exploitation plans for each partner are well under way and will be validated by project partners in the coming months. Exploring available funding is an ongoing procedure and available funding opportunities are communicated to project partners

Field Deployment MVP2 Phase

Duration: From M17 to M28 (initial planning)

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

The start of MVP2 has been delayed, and the following activities will commence with its initiation. Workshop A will facilitate collaborative discussions on creating joint asset business cases, formulating business models, and addressing IPR considerations. An initial analysis of viable exploitation avenues for non-commercial results featured in the Exploitation and IP Catalogue will begin. A financial analysis will be conducted to forecast initial commercialization years, providing a foundation for the long-term viability of joint exploitation plans. An updated iteration of the Exploitation and IP Catalogue will consistently monitor the project's exploitable outcomes. These results will be included in D6.7, that will be focusing on individual and joint exploitation plan preparation, the Market Analysis, and Business Modelling considerations.

Field Deployment & Holistic Evaluation MVP3 Phase

Duration: From January 2026 (M29) to February 2028 (M42) (initial planning)

The third workshop scheduled for M40 will focus on operationalizing and engaging market strategies. Workshop B will focus on developing Lean Canvas for joint assets, discussing market entry strategies, and assessing associated risks. Discussions will include market entry strategies, potential risks, and funding opportunities. A holistic evaluation of the project's pilots will assess the effectiveness and scalability of Smart Droplets solutions in real-world environments.

Finally, the preparation of the final Exploitation and Sustainability Report will summarize the exploitation pathways, sustainability strategies, and lessons learned throughout the project.

By following these updated steps, Smart Droplets aims to effectively adapt to the pilot delays while ensuring the project's exploitation and sustainability goals are met.

6. Conclusions

This third version of the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (DEC) plan and reports (D6.3) represents a major step forward in the Smart Droplets project. It details a clear and ambitious strategy to not only spread the word about the project's innovations but also ensure their lasting impact and sustainability.

Throughout this document, we've laid out a thorough approach to reaching and engaging our diverse range of stakeholders. From farmers and agricultural technologists to policymakers and the general public, our goal is to make the benefits of Smart Droplets accessible and beneficial to all. The SOSTAC model has shaped our methodology, ensuring a structured and strategic approach to all dissemination and communication activities.

Our dissemination activities are designed to raise awareness and foster engagement. Through market and industry events, webinars, and the Smart Droplets Academy, we are actively demonstrating the practical applications and benefits of our technologies. These activities are crucial for building a strong network of users and supporters who will champion Smart Droplets well beyond the project's end.

Communication efforts are centered around creating a strong and recognizable brand for Smart Droplets. By leveraging digital channels, including a dynamic website and active social media presence, we are reaching a broad audience and ensuring continuous engagement. Regular newsletters and press releases keep our stakeholders informed about our progress and successes, while carefully crafted visual materials enhance our project's visibility and appeal.

Exploitation activities focus on maximizing the commercial and non-commercial potential of our innovations. Identifying and validating KERs ensures that we focus our efforts on the most promising aspects of the project. Detailed market analysis and the exploration of funding opportunities provide a solid foundation for developing joint and individual exploitation plans. These plans are crucial for ensuring that the benefits of Smart Droplets are realized in practical, impactful ways during and after the project's duration.

As we move forward, our focus will remain on continuous improvement and adaptation. Feedback from our stakeholders and partners will be essential in refining our strategies and activities. By staying responsive to the needs and insights of our community, we can ensure that Smart Droplets not only achieves its goals but exceeds them.

The plans laid out in this document reflect our commitment to making a significant and lasting impact in the agricultural sector. We are dedicated to driving sustainability, improving efficiency, and enhancing the quality of life for farmers and communities. The innovations developed through Smart Droplets have the potential to transform agricultural practices, and we are excited to continue this journey, working together towards a smarter, greener future.

In summary, this deliverable encapsulates our dedication to excellence in dissemination, communication, and exploitation. It sets a clear path for the remainder of the project, ensuring that Smart Droplets will leave a lasting legacy of innovation and improvement in the agricultural sector. We look forward to the continued collaboration and support from our partners and stakeholders as we work towards our goals.

Annex A: Smart Droplets brand book

BRAND GUIDELINES

Color palette

#C6D32D	#6F9925	#3A3A3A
#0D62AC	#3A88AF	#E3244F

BRAND GUIDELINES

Brand typography

Font name: **Harabara Mais**

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

FONT NAME: GEOMETOS ROUNDED

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z

FONT NAME: LATO

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

BRAND GUIDELINES

Logo variations

BRAND GUIDELINES

Brand applications

Annex B: Logo Variations

Annex C: Banner for Social Media

Annex D: Presentation Template

1

2

3

4

Annex F: Simple Text Template for text documents

Annex G: Brochures

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

OBJECTIVES |

Smart Droplets' main objective is to **advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical applications for resource optimisation and minimisation of chemical waste**. It will use existing technologies (i.e. RL7) developed within but not limited to the agricultural industry. The technologies need to accomplish the vision of delivering a complete system capable of translating large amounts of data from the field into meaningful information and impactful spraying commands in order to achieve the Green Deal goals.

THE ROAD TO ACHIEVING THE OBJECTIVES INCLUDES:

- 1. The innovative use of Intelligent Data Infrastructure and Digital Twins.
- 2. Introducing robotic solutions for autonomous spraying.
- 3. Optimizing technologies and demonstrating the Green Deal goals in real-life environments.
- 4. Community building, synergies, and results exploitation.

EXPECTED IMPACT |

IMPACT 1: Smart Droplets is creating added value in the agricultural industry and its supply chain, by leveraging the shift to reduce hazardous agrochemical application. Innovative and sustainable results of Smart Droplets will contribute to the resilience and competitiveness of the EU economy while identifying early opportunities and bottlenecks in the IP and exploitation aspects of such technologies.

#Resilience #Sustainability #Resilience #Competitiveness

IMPACT 2: Smart Droplets offers the necessary test bench for exploring disruptive technologies that can offer global excellence and reduction of agrochemicals. The leading position of the European industry will be validated through benchmarking of all technological aspects during the project implementation. Moreover, real environment demonstrations will showcase the technological progress made within the project and validate their contribution towards the Green Deal. A comprehensive exploitation strategy will advance the adoption rate of robotic, AI and Data solutions, thereby reinforcing European industry leadership in the digital food supply chain.

#ReductionOfAgrochemicals #Demonstrators #Exploitation

IMPACT 3: Smart Droplets takes a multi-layer complementary approach to tackle key parts of the supply chain, incorporating different components such as Digital Data Twins, robotics, AI, and Data Platforms to create an optimized spraying solution. This data-centric approach includes historic field data, 3rd party information services, and real-time sensory data of the deployed robotic system. Robust European industrial and technology presence requires strong engagement by stakeholders. Therefore, community and capacity-building activities will ensure proper transition and adoption of technologies.

#Multi-layerApproach #SprayingSolution #Data-centric #Capacity-building

PARTNERS

Visit our website for more!
smartdroplets.eu

COORDINATOR

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kalliopi.koumani@auz.gr

smartdroplets.eu

Co-funded by the European Union

Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticides and fertilizer reduction through AI, data, and robotic technologies

Co-funded by the European Union

LEADER-IP-CA-2022
Duration: 01/01/2022 - 31/03/2024
Project ID: 101018076

Annex H: Posters

Smart Droplets

SMART DROPLETS TURNING LESS INTO MORE!

- ▶ An environmental, socially responsible, and economically inclusive tech-solution for the overuse of fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture
- ▶ Fast-tracking the EU Green Deal Objectives and targets of 2030
- ▶ Showcasing the sustainable solution with two multi-actor live pilots in complementary yet diverse environments
- ▶ Demonstrating the scalability and success of deep tech solutions on apple orchards and wheat fields.

▶ TECHNOLOGICAL BUILDING BLOCKS FOR NOVEL CROP CARE

 OBJECT DETECTION (SPRAYING ZONE) Smart Droplets will implement machine learning systems and algorithms for the detection of the spraying zone.				
---	--	--	--	--

With the global need for food constantly rising, the pressure on the food production industry is ever more present to develop more sustainable approaches with lesser ecological footprints. Smart Droplets brings a novel approach to chemical applications in farm processes by advancing both hardware and software capabilities for resource optimization and minimization of chemical use and waste. Smart Droplets aspires to deliver a complete system capable of translating large amounts of data from the field into meaningful information and impactful spraying commands to help farmers, society and the planet.

Follow us and find out more about apple orchards and wheat fields that are moving towards the Green Deal objectives and the next level with AI, deep tech and robotics solutions.

smartdroplets.eu

Co-funded by the European Union

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

Smart Droplets

SMART DROPLETS TURNING LESS INTO MORE!

Co-funded by the European Union

Apple Orchard Pilot Facts

Why?
Apples are among the crops where the highest amounts of pesticides are used. Insufficient control measures of apple scabs and other fungal diseases can lead to economic losses.

How?
By automating a tractor capable of working 24/7 in order to perform the spraying operations, together with sensors to detect the health of the plant to apply the right kind and amount of fungicides, at the right time, in the right place.

For who?
Farmers, farmers' associations & cooperatives, agronomists & advisors, agri-food technology manufacturers, AI/Data/Robotics providers, AI/Data/Robotics DfEs, Policy Makers & Standardisation Bodies

Where?
The Mediterranean region: Spain

SPAIN

SMART DROPLETS PROJECT EXPECTS TO DECREASE THE WASTE CREATED BY INFECTED AND UNUSABLE APPLES WHILE CREATING BETTER CONDITIONS FOR FARMERS, EUROPE AND THE PLANET!

Follow us and find out more about apple orchards and what farms that are moving towards the Green Deal objectives and the next level with AI, deep tech and robotics systems!

smartdroplets.eu

Smart Droplets

SMART DROPLETS TURNING LESS INTO MORE!

Co-funded by the European Union

Wheat Farm Pilot Facts

Why?
Wheat accounts for almost half of the main cereal production in the EU, while weeds can reduce wheat yield by 15%-20% per annum, with nitrogen application needing to be re-evaluated.

How?
By focusing on chemical weeding, nitrogen fertilization and fungicide applications, while utilizing state-of-the-art technologies and especially the most relevant advances in AI/Data/Robotics, Smart Droplets will optimise farm operation working towards the EU Green Deal Targets.

For who?
Farmers, farmers' associations & cooperatives, agronomists & advisors, agri-food technology manufacturers, AI/Data/Robotics providers, AI/Data/Robotics DfEs, Policy Makers & Standardisation Bodies.

Where?
Central Lithuania, Baltic area

LITHUANIA

SMART DROPLETS PROJECT EXPECTS TO INCREASE YIELDS, DECREASE CHEMICAL USE AND OPERATIONAL COSTS ALL WHILE CREATING BETTER CONDITIONS FOR FARMERS, EUROPE AND THE PLANET!

Follow us and find out more about apple orchards and what farms that are moving towards the Green Deal objectives and the next level with AI, deep tech and robotics systems!

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Annex I: Factsheets

Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotic technologies.

▶ AT A GLANCE

PROJECT TITLE:	Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotic technologies (Smart Droplets)	DURATION:	September 2022 - February 2026 (42 months)
PROGRAMME:	HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-09	COORDINATOR:	Agricultural University of Athens (AUA), Greece
INSTRUMENT:	HORIZON Innovation action	CONSORTIUM:	9 Partners from six European countries
TOTAL BUDGET:	€2 998 370,00	SOCIAL MEDIA:	

▶ THE CHALLENGE

Agricultural environments are characterized by rapid changes, while crop care tasks have always been repetitive, tedious, and potentially hazardous. Consequently, the sector is shifting towards more selective treatment applications to improve the quality and efficiency of chemical spraying. To mitigate environmental pollution and de facto negative implication on human health, there is an urgent need to improve the use of pesticide and fertilizer use. The EU Green Deal has set ambitious targets to reduce the use of pesticide and fertilizer by 2030, which cannot be reached without the use of advanced technologies. AI Data and robotic advances on SFTs (Smart Farming Technologies) can contribute in fulfilling this ambition bringing benefits in terms of reduced pesticide use, low carbon emissions, low water use, reduced food waste, thus enabling environmental sustainability.

▶ PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The Smart Droplets project introduces a novel approach for crop care tasks, by connecting key-technological aspects during open field spraying. Based on the scope of the EU Green Deal and the recently reformed Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), Smart Droplets is committed to advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical application, in order to meet the sustainability goals. Smart Droplets' solution relies upon critical technological building blocks, that constitute a novel crop care approach through the use of:

- Data infrastructures
- Robotic systems
- AI models
- Digital twins
- Direct Injection Spraying (DIS)

smartdroplets.eu

Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotic technologies.

▶ AT A GLANCE

PROJECT TITLE:	Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotic technologies (Smart Droplets)
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SOCIAL MEDIA:	

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Agricultural environments are characterized by rapid changes, while crop care tasks have always been repetitive, tedious, and potentially hazardous. Consequently, the sector is shifting towards more selective treatment applications to improve the quality and efficiency of chemical spraying. To mitigate environmental pollution and de facto negative implication on human health, there is an urgent need to improve the use of pesticide and fertilizer use. The EU Green Deal has set ambitious targets to reduce the use of pesticide and fertilizer by 2030, which cannot be reached without the use of advanced technologies. AI Data and robotic advances on SFTs (Smart Farming Technologies) can contribute in fulfilling this ambition bringing benefits in terms of reduced pesticide use, low carbon emissions, low water use, reduced food waste, thus enabling environmental sustainability.

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- Data infrastructures
- Robotic systems
- AI models
- Digital twins
- Direct Injection Spraying (DIS)

Annex J: Roll-up Banner

Annex K: Dissemination and Communication Material

Annex L: Zoom Background

Annex M: Press release template

<p style="text-align: right;">Press Release</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Co-funded by the European Union</p>	Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.																
Smart Droplets in a nutshell - Important details																	
Funding	Horizon Europe																
Total budget																	
Duration																	
Consortium																	
Project coordination																	
Project communication																	
<p>Co-funded by the European Union</p>	Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.																

Annex N: Event Planning Template

Smart Droplets Event Planning

Please complete the following form with events that you are already planning on attending over the next 6 months, or any that you are aware of, and feel would be well suited for Smart Droplets participation.

#	Date	Partner	Name of event	Location	Role / Description and Links	Scale, Target Groups

Annex O: Synergy Mapping Template

Smart Droplets Synergy Mapping

Please complete the following form with projects, initiatives and/or networks that you are involved with or are aware of and that could provide an opportunity for joint activities and collaboration.

Smart Droplets Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of Initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						

Annex P: Publication Planning Template

Smart Droplets PUBLICATION PLANNING

Please complete the following form with peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, any other publication you plan to make.

Smart Droplets Publication Planning			
#	Type of publication	Publication website	Estimated submission date
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
...			

Annex Q: Template of Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)	Scope of exploitation		Target groups [to whom]	Means of exploitation	Linked IPRs to the KERs	
<i>Please validate the already identified KERs (1-5) and add any other exploitable results if relevant</i>	<i>Please validate (for further explanation of the scope, please see note)</i>		<i>Please validate (see note for the list of target groups)</i>	<i>Please indicate the means of exploitation, where relevant</i>	<i>Please indicate what might be the possible IPRs, where relevant</i>	
	<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>			<i>If "other", please identify</i>	<i>Other</i>
1 KER 1						
2 KER 2						
3 KER 3						
4 KER 4						
5 KER 5						

Annex R: Strategic analysis tools

PESTLE Factor	Your notes	Potential impact	Implications and Importance			
			Time Frame: Short/Medium/Long	Type: Opportunity/Threat	Implication: Increasing/ Reducing/ Not yet determined	Relative Importance: H = High M = Medium L = Low
	<i>About your organisation and how the factors listed on the left might impact on marketing for your organisation/SBU</i>	<i>H = High M = Medium L = Low U = Undecided</i>				
P Political						
E Economic						
S Sociological						
T Technological						
E Environmental						
L Legal						

D6.3: Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v3

<p>Internal factors</p> <p>External factors</p>	<p>Strengths (S)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S1. • S2. • S3. • S4. • S5. • S6. • S7. 	<p>Weakness (W)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • W1. • W2. • W3. • W4. • W5. • W6. • W7.
<p>Opportunities (O)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • O1. • O2. • O3. • O4. • O5. • O6. • O7. 	<p>S-O strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S..O.. 	<p>W-O strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • W..O..
<p>Threats (T)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T1. • T2. • T3. • T4. • T5. • T6. • T7. 	<p>S-T strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S..T.. 	<p>W-T strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • W..T..

Annex S: Business model canvas

Annex T: Vodcast Questions per episode

Episode 1

Title: How come those Droplets are so Smart?

Theme: Introductory

Partner: AUA

Interviewee: Kalliopi Kounani

Interviewer: Antonis Andronikakis

Questions

1. Kalliopi could you please briefly explain the core concept of Smart Droplets for our audience?
2. Can you describe your role as a coordinator and guide us through the consortium?
3. What are the different technologies developed by the consortium partners? How are these technologies integrated into the Smart Droplets solution?
4. What are the primary benefits of the SD technology solution? How will you test the solution to ensure it actually works?
5. But Smart Droplets offers more than just a technological solution, doesn't it? Can you tell us more about the SD Academy concept and who can benefit from this initiative?
6. What are the challenges in the development of the project so far and what are the next steps?

Episode 2

Title: How is this tractor moving on its own? The Smart Droplets Autonomous technology

Theme: Tech focused, autonomous movement

Partner: EUT

Interviewee: Pau Reverté Martínez

Interviewer: Antonis Andronikakis

Questions

1. Can you start by telling us about EURECAT, its role in the project?
2. Can you explain what an autonomous tractor is and why it's important for the Smart Droplets project?
3. What specific technologies are used to enable the retrofit tractor to move on its own? How do they work together?
4. Could you share the story of how the autonomous movement system for the retrofit tractor was developed? What were the biggest challenges you faced?
5. How will this autonomous tractor revolutionise farming? What benefits can farmers expect to see in their day-to-day operations?
6. What future improvements or new features are you excited about for the autonomous tractor? How will these enhancements make it even more effective for farmers?

Episode 3

Title: Digital Twins - Wheat Fields and Apple Orchards on the other side of the data stream

Theme: Tech focused, Digital Twins, AI

Partner: WU

Interviewee: Michiel Kallenberg

Interviewer: Antonis Andronikakis

Questions

1. Can you start by explaining in simple terms what digital twins are and how they are used in the Smart Droplets project?
2. How does artificial intelligence enhance the capabilities of digital twins in this project? Could you give us some everyday examples of AI in action?
3. What were the key steps in creating the AI and digital twins for Smart Droplets, and what makes them special?
4. How will digital twins and AI change the way farmers work? What are the biggest benefits they can expect?
5. Can you share a success story or example where these technologies have made a real difference in farming?
6. What exciting developments or new features do you see coming for digital twins and AI in agriculture?

Episode 4

Title: Internet of Things - How the field talks to us through data

Theme: Tech focused, IoT & Data

Partner: VLF

Interviewee: Milenko Tomic and Mihailo Ilic

Interviewer: Antonis Andronikakis

Questions

1. Please tell us about VLF and its role in the project.
2. Can you explain what IoT (Internet of Things) is and how it's being used in the Smart Droplets project?
3. How does data collection work in the context of Smart Droplets? What types of data are being collected from the fields?
4. How does IoT and data collection improve farming practices? What are the main benefits for farmers using these technologies?
5. What are farmers thinking about the adoption of IoT and smart farming solutions? Are there any obstacles or shortcomings? Can you share a real-world example or success story?
6. What are the main challenges for wider adoption of the IoT and general digital technologies in agrifood?

Episode 5

Title: Direct Injection Spraying - On-field Brewing

Theme: Tech focused, Direct Injection Spraying

Partner: AGROMA

Interviewee: Nikos Petkos

Interviewer: Antonis Andronikakis

Questions

1. Can you start by explaining what direct injection spraying is and how it differs from traditional spraying methods?
2. What technologies are involved in direct injection spraying, and how do they work together to achieve better results?
3. Could you describe the development process of the direct injection spraying system for Smart Droplets? What challenges did you encounter?
4. Is this technology widely adopted by farmers? Why? How does it benefit farmers and the environment?
5. Do you have any real-world examples or case studies where direct injection spraying has been successfully implemented and its impact?
6. What future improvements or new features are you excited about for direct injection spraying technology? How will these advancements enhance its effectiveness?

Episode 6

Title: How would you like your Smart Droplets Solution? Mapping User Requirements

Theme: Requirements mapping

Partner: FEMAC

Interviewee: Enric Pedros

Interviewer: Antonis Andronikakis

1. To start, can you give us an overview of FEMAC's role in the Smart Droplets project and how your team's expertise is guiding the project's development and implementation?
2. How did FEMAC's research into what farmers and industry leaders need help shape the direction of the Smart Droplets project?
3. What are some of the key user requirements you've identified so far, particularly from farmers and industry stakeholders?
4. Based on those key requirements, can you share any interesting insights from farmers regarding their expectations for the Smart Droplets solution?
5. Considering FEMAC's extensive experience in agricultural innovation, how do you see the industry evolving in the next few years?
6. From your perspective, how is the market for smart agricultural technologies developing, and what opportunities do you foresee for projects like Smart Droplets?

Episode 7

Title: My Old Tractor Started moving on its own - Developing the Retrofit Kit

Theme: Implementation, manufacturing

Partner: AGC

Interviewee: Suzanne Baron

Interviewer: Antonis Andronikakis

1. Can you describe AGC's role in the Smart Droplets project and what your main objectives are?
2. Can you describe what a retrofit tractor is and what technologies are involved in it?
3. The retrofit tractor uses AGC's autonomous navigation system, the AGCbox. Can you tell us how the AGCbox works and what makes it a game-changer for modern farming?
4. What were some of the key challenges you faced during the development of the retrofit tractor, and how did you overcome them?
5. What benefits do you anticipate farmers will see once the retrofit tractor solution is fully tested and implemented?
6. What future trends or advancements do you foresee in agricultural technology that could impact projects like Smart Droplets?